

DL5.2 - 'Forestry Plant Health' and 'Regional' Workshops

EUPHRESCO-II

**DEEPENED AND ENLARGED COOPERATION BETWEEN PHYTOSANITARY
(STATUTORY PLANT HEALTH) RESEARCH PROGRAMMES**

COORDINATION ACTION (ERA-NET)

Grant No: 266505

DL 5.2 – Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems and increased inclusion of plant-producing sectors under-represented in EUPHRESKO-1

Three workshops were held and their main conclusions and associated reports are presented below:

- **A workshop exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic Countries was held in Tallinn 1–2 December 2011.**

The report from the workshop, including Annexes is provided here:

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Participants

All EUPHRESCO partners and observers in the Baltic-Nordic region were invited to the workshop. The Swedish member had to cancel the participation, but provided all requested background material for the analysis. Russia belongs both to the Baltic-Nordic region and the Eastern Europe-Balkan region, and Russia informed not to have capacity to participate in both workshop and has chosen the Eastern Europe-Balkan regional workshop. Norway did not respond on invitations and on request to provide information for the background material.

The following persons participated:

List of participants:

Anna Tratwal	Poland
Gunita Bokuma	Latvia
Silke Steinmüller	Germany
Steen Lykke Nielsen	Denmark
Tuula. Maki-Valkama	Finland
Zita Duchovskiene	Lithuania
Evelin Loit	Estonia
Karme Petrutis	Estonia
Küllli Kaare	Estonia
Olga Lavrentjeva	Estonia
Riina Koidumaa	Estonia

Annexes

Programme.

Introduction and overview of background material.

Analysis of the background materials.

Annex 1. The list of the harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC.

Annex 2. The pests from Annex 1 classified to crop sectors and split into crops.

Annex 3. Topic calls from EUPHRESCO-1 and EUPHRESCO-2 (2011) split on crops.

Annex 4. EPPO's Alert List split on crops.

Annex 5. Lists of most important crops (other than forestry) in countries in the Baltic Sea-Nordic countries Region.

Annex 6. The lists of Appendix 5, sorted after how many countries have included the specific crop in their list.

Annex 7. Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary threats (other than forestry) according to NPPO's in countries in the Baltic Sea-Nordic countries Region sorted after importance by each NPPO.

Annex 8. The list of Annex 7 split on crop sectors and crops and listed in descending order of numbers of countries listing the pest.

Annex 9. List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests.

Annex 10. Interceptions per pest of harmful organisms in EU 2007-09.

Annex 11. Examples on different factors influencing on why certain q-pests have higher priority than other.

Annex 12. List of EU Frame Work Programme (FP) 6 and FP7 plant health projects and plant health related projects.

Notes from the workshop's day 1, the 1st December 2011.

Concerning: Problems to clarify: underrepresented plant sectors

Problem 1. Are there some specific plant sectors/crops in the Baltic/Nordic-region, which have been underrepresented in the EUPH-1 and the EUPH-2 (2011) topic identification and project initiation activities?

Comments by the Nordic-Baltic workshop: Strawberry and Vaccinum species could be the Baltic-Nordic regional specialty.

Problem 2. If some sectors/crops have been underrepresented, could it be due to that there are not as many problems with plant health in the specific sector/crop than in other sectors/crops?

Comments by the Nordic-Baltic workshop: Cereals are common and economical very important in the Baltic-Nordic region. There has been no EUPHRESKO-projects on cereals, but on the other hand there are very few pests in cereals listed in the Directive 2000/29/EC, which explains the underrepresentation.

General topics:

Comments by the Nordic-Baltic workshop:

- In some productions, for example glasshouse productions, where the properties are located in colonies, it is important to have an overview of all of the production processes (waste management etc), to see the weak points where the (re)introduction of pests could occur.
- Trade with growth media inclusive composts inside EU is not regulated. Plant health risks should be analysed.
- It is important to distinguish between problems belonging to plant health and to plant protection. Currently there has been only little coordination and collaboration between the two topics, both in policy and science. More synergy is needed!
- Why are much more pests moving from **South to North**? One explanation is there are more plants and plant products moving from south to north. There is an expectation of an increased movement of pests east-west after the cold war has ended.

Notes from the workshop's 2nd day the 2nd December 2011 and conclusions and recommendations

A general discussion of specific and general plant health problems based on the analysis of the background material presented yesterday was carried out. The following topics were highlighted:

Travellers bringing in plants and internet trade: people illegally import plant material (includes also invasive alien species). It is a legislation problem but also a knowledge problem, meaning that people do not know the rules, so information of the public with for example poster information in the airports

could help to minimise the problem. The Nordic-Baltic workshop recommends a topic on a PRA on internet trade and illegal private “import” as a future EUPHRESKO-project.

Annual meetings between NPPOs and their associated diagnostic laboratories in the Nordic-Baltic Region. Representatives from the Nordic-Baltic Region’s NPPOs comprising Finland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Denmark, Sweden and Norway meet annually and discuss matters of mutual interest. The Nordic-Baltic NPPOs’ diagnostic laboratories independently also meet annually. The Nordic-Baltic workshop recommends the two meetings to discuss ideas for future actual topics for EUPHRESKO transnational projects. The Nordic-Baltic workshop also recommends the Nordic-Baltic NPPOs to spread the knowledge about these yearly meeting to other NPPOs.

Climatic changes: The Nordic-Baltic workshop recommends to initiate an approach to collect first information on future threats connected to climatic changes by initiating a EUPHRESKO project. The Nordic-Baltic workshop recognises that climatic changes’ influence on plant health is of general interest for all EUPHRESKO partners but it is also of regional interest because the predicted changes are different in different regions, because among other things the possibility of introducing new crops are also regionalised. The work should focus on plant health threats and NOT on climate science. The EUPHRESKO project should be a pilot activity analysing the main problems and serve as basis for lobbying for a big FP8 project on climatic changes influence on plant health.

Cost-benefit analysis: ex. having worked out extended PRAs (including economics and cost-benefit) for selected pests. This could be a topic for a future EUPHRESKO-topic selection round. The topic is not a specific regional one, but includes all EUPHRESKO regions.

General plant health topics (compared to topics focusing on only one specific pest): The responses from the Nordic-Baltic region’s NPPOs on which plant health problems they consider as the most important, showed many topics of more general character as for example climatic changes, use of integrated pest management systems, problems with plant products for energy production (for example wood chip) and handling of big amounts of infected crops. The Nordic-Baltic workshop recommends EUPHRESKO to include more general topics in future topic call rounds.

Specific crops and plant products:

Potato is a very important crop in the Nordic-Baltic region and it has been covered satisfactory and in high degree by EUPHRESKO until now, but there seem to be a nearly endless need of new projects in potato.

Strawberry: The Nordic-Baltic workshop recognised that strawberry is an important high value crop in all partner countries and recommends to initiate a general common (not regional) project on plant health problems in strawberry, among other things comprising *Phytophthora fragaria* and *Xanthomonas fragaria*.

Berry production in general. The Nordic-Baltic workshop recognised that berries other than strawberry are important crops and natural resources in most partner countries and requested more information of

possible threats (ex. import of big fruited *Vaccinium* species from North America) in among other species for example blueberry before any topic proposal can be formulated. This is up to each partner to take initiative to provide this information.

Peat moss: Partners producing growth media based on peat moss recognise problems with validation of test of different pests, ex. *Globodera* cyst nematodes, because standard tests methods do not work in this special growth medium. The Nordic-Baltic workshop suggests it as a new coming topic for EUPHRESCO.

Conclusion on if one or more plant sectors/crops have been underrepresented until now: The Nordic-Baltic workshop concluded that only strawberry and *Vaccinium* species but else no other crops have been underrepresented in the EUPHRESCO initiated projects until now. Another specific problem mentioned is test of peat moss.

Conclusion on if the region has specific plant health problems, which EUPHRESCO should include in the topic selection and project initiation procedure: because in EUPHRESCO-2 much more partners from the Nordic-Baltic region have joined the network, the specific regional problems have been covered in a more satisfactory way than under EUPHRESCO-1. However the Nordic-Baltic workshop recommends to include much more general plant health topics as for example climatic changes influence on plant health in the future call rounds.

The Nordic-Baltic region partners invite Russia to join the group, because many plant health problems are identical and the same goes for the economical most important crops grown in the region. (At the moment Russia has chosen to participate in the working group on the Eastern European-Balkan region).

EUPHRESCO-2 WP5-Workshop Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Tuesday 1st December

Chair: Evelin Loit / Olga Lavrentjeva

12.30 Registration and light lunch

13.30 Welcome by Külli Kaare

13.35 Welcome and short introduction to the workshop by Steen Lykke Nielsen

- Presentation round among the participants
- Short introduction to WP5
- Introduction to WP5.2 Exploring regionalisation and underrepresented plant sectors
- The aim of the workshop

14.30 Presentation of the back ground material by Tuula Maki-Valkana & Steen

- Lists of Council directive 2000/29/EC
- List of EUPHRESCO initiated projects
- EPPO Alert List
- List of the most important crops in the Baltic-Nordic region
- The NPPO list of the present most important phytosanitary threats
- List of EU-funded research projects on plant sectors/crops in FP6 and FP7
- List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests
- List of interceptions in EU

15.00 Coffee brake

15.30 Continue presentation of the back ground material

17.30 Information of the night's dinner by Külli Kaare

17.35 Departure for the hotel

18.30 Dinner at Restaurant Ribe, Vene 7, Tallin

EUPHRESCO-2 WP5-Workshop Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Friday 2nd December

Chair: Evelin Loit / Olga Lavrentjeva

08.30 Recapitulation from yesterday by Steen and Tuula

08.45 Introduction to work in two working parties by Steen and Tuula

09.30 Discussions in two working parties

Party 1: is a regionalised approach needed?

Party 2: are certain plant sectors underrepresented?

10.00 Coffee brake

10.20 Continue discussions in two working parties

11.30 Plenum.

- **Presentations from the two parties**

- **Common discussion**

- **Conclusions and recommendations to EUPHRESCO**

12.45 Practical information on reimbursement by Steen

12.50 Closing the meeting by Külli

13.00 Lunch in the cafeteria of the Ministry

Departure

EUPHRESCO-2 WP5-Workshop Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

**The conference venue will be
The Ministry of Agriculture:
Lai Street 39/ Lai Street 41
Tallinn 15056**

List of participants:

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EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Background:

In the application for EUPHRESCO-2 the work package 5 (WP5) includes activities on regionalisation and the partners mentioned below are involved.

In the following is described the part of the activities comprising regionalisation and underrepresented plant sectors in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries. A corresponding activity is planned for the region of the Balkan & Eastern European countries and the plant sector: forestry.

Extract from the WP5 application text:

This sub-workpackage will analyse and explore the potential and relevance of a regionalised approach to specific plant health topics. Concerning regionalisation, it is well-known that certain crops in Europe are grown more regionally, based on climate, e.g. olives and citrus crops. Other crops are produced in most parts of Europe, but with very different importance and quantity, e.g. winter cereals, potatoes, vines and seeds.

- An analysis will be done to elucidate if it will be a useful tool for EUPHRESCO to include regionalisation for certain plant health topics. There will be focused on regions where several important member states, associated states and other countries (e.g. ICPC countries) were missing as full partners in EUPHRESCO-I:

Furthermore an analysis identifying possible plant-production sectors (other than forestry), which during EUPHRESCO-I may have been underrepresented in trans-national projects. The analysis will determine if a broader sector-based approach (e.g. potatoes, vines, glasshouse crops) may be relevant for plant health.

- Workshops exploring benefits of regionally-based approaches for the three regions mentioned above will be organised.
- Where opportunities for regionalised collaboration are identified, these will be fed into WP3.

Deliverable 5.2: 'Regional' workshop: Workshops for exploring benefit of increased regional collaboration held and action plan produced [month 14].

Aims of the exploration

The part consists of two tasks: regionalisation and highlighting underrepresented plant sectors (except forestry, which is dealt with in another working group).

Regionalisation

The aims are

- to analyse whether a regionalised approach to specific plant health topics is relevant for EUPHRESCO with the Baltic/Nordic-region as starting point.
- to propose a solution to EUPHRESCO-2 (Project Management Group, assembly) to include regionalisation in the topic proposal and selection procedure if the previous analysis shows it is relevant.

Underrepresented plant sectors

The aims are

- to identify the degree of underrepresentation of certain plant-production sectors (other than forestry, e.g. potatoes, vines, glasshouse crops), which during EUPHRESCO-1 may not (or only very rarely) have been included as topics or in trans-national projects.

- to explore the reasons for the underrepresentation (if it is found).
- in light of the previous two dots to analyse if a broader plant sector-based approach (e.g. potatoes, vines and glasshouse crops) may be relevant as a factor for topic proposal and selection.
- to propose a solution/solutions to EUPHRESCO-2 to increase the representation of plant health problems in certain plant-production sectors in the proposed topics and EUPHRESCO-initiated projects.

Problems to clarify: regionalisation

Problem 1. Could it be that a certain region has specific plant health problems due to that certain important crops/plant sectors are more prevailing than in other regions, because of, among other things, climatic factors and tradition.

Problem 2. Could it be that a certain region has potential specific plant health problems because of natural spread of regulated pests and prevalent import or transit of plant products from nearby neighbouring regions.

Others?

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Problems to clarify: underrepresented plant sectors

Problem 1. Are there some specific plant sectors/crops in the Baltic/Nordic-region, which have been underrepresented in the EUPH-1 and the EUPH-2 (2011) topic identification and project initiation activities?

Problem 2. If some sectors/crops have been underrepresented, could it be due to that there are not as many problems with plant health in the specific sector/crop than in other sectors/crops?

Problem 3. If some sectors/crops have been underrepresented, could it be due to that in the last few years many FP6 and FP7 research projects and regional funded projects in that sector/crop have been initiated, so there has been/is a lesser demand to initiate new projects in the specific sector/crop than in other crops/sectors?

Others?

Aims of the Baltic/Nordic regional workshop

The overall aim is to discuss the analyses worked out as background material to the workshop, to draw conclusions and agree on these, and to recommend if a regionalised approach to specific plant health topics is relevant for EUPHRESCO and further on, if it is concluded that certain plant sectors/crops have been underrepresented, to recommend how EUPHRESCO could handle that.

Sub-aims:

Regionalisation:

- Approve or reject the problem that the region has specific plant health problems, which EUPHRESCO should include in the topic selection and project initiation procedure.
- Propose solutions, hereunder
 - o Under the condition that regionalisation is relevant:
 - Should EUPHRESCO initiate separate rounds of topic selection and project initiation for the Baltic/Nordic region or will it be sufficient to include specific regional related topics under the regular EUPH-2 topic identification rounds?

- Would it be relevant to settle permanent regional working groups under EUPH to secure specific regional plant health problems not are neglected?
- Other solutions?
- If the conclusion is that regionalisation is not relevant, there will be no need for special initiative.

Underrepresented plant sectors/crops:

- Approve or reject the problem that plant health problems in one or more plant sectors/crops have been underrepresented until now.
- Propose solutions, hereunder
 - Under the condition that one or more plant sectors/crops has been underrepresented until now:
 - Should EUPHRESCO initiate separate rounds of topic selection and project initiation for selected plant sectors/crops or will it be sufficient to include these underrepresented areas under the regular EUPH-2 topic identification rounds?
 - Would it be relevant to settle permanent working groups for selected crops under EUPH to secure that plant health problems in specific sectors/crops are not neglected?
 - Other solutions?
 - If the conclusion is that focus on specific sectors/crops is not relevant, there will be no need for special initiative.

Background materials worked out to the workshop

Annex 1. A list of the harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. The listing follows the order of the Annexes and the order of pests in the Annexes. A column titled “crop sector” classified into Agriculture, Fruit, Citrus fruit, Viticulture, Glasshouse, Tomato, Plants for planting and Forestry is added. The list includes 189 pests.

Annex 2. The pests from Annex 1 classified to crop sectors and split into crops. The crop sectors are agriculture with 59 pests, fruits with 89 pests, viticulture with 7 pests, glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato) and field ornamentals with 27 pests, tomato with 13 pests, plants for planting with 22 pests and forestry with 27 pests.

Annex 3. Topic calls from EUPHRESCO-1 and EUPHRESCO-2 (2011) split on crops. The list shows the 20 projects initiated by EUPHRESCO until now. Split on crops/crop sectors the topics spread as follows: 8 on potato, 1 on maize, 1 on field vegetables, 2 on tomato, 2 on glasshouse ornamentals, 5 on fruit, 2 on vine, 4 on plants for planting, 3 on forestry and 3 on other more general aspects.

Annex 4. EPPO’s Alert List split on crops: The September 2011 version includes 37 pests with 10 pests on tomato, 3 on potato, 4 on maize, 4 on other agricultural crops (cotton, sunflower, lettuce), 1 on glasshouse ornamentals, 5 on fruit and citrus fruit, 6 on plants for planting and 8 on forestry.

Annex 5. Lists of most important crops (other than forestry) in countries in the Baltic Sea-Nordic countries Region. The list comprises input from 8 countries. Input from Norway and Russia is missing. The crops are listed in descending order of economically importance in each of the crop sectors: agricultural crops, field vegetables, fruits and berries, glasshouse crops and nursery (garden plants for planting) crops.

Annex 6. The lists of Appendix 5, now sorted after how many countries have included the specific crop in their list. There is a very high degree of accordance in the crops listed by all 8 countries.

Annexes 7. Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary threats (other than forestry) according to NPPO's in countries in the Baltic Sea-Nordic countries Region sorted after importance by each NPPO. However not much weight should be laid on the sorting after importance. Most NPPO's mention that it is not possible to differentiate between importance in different crops and crop sectors and different criteria could be used.

Annex 8. The list of Annex 7 split on crop sectors and crops and listed in descending order of numbers of countries listing the pest. The crop sectors comprise agriculture, glasshouse, fruit, plants for planting and forestry besides more general phytosanitary problems as for example diagnostics, climatic changes and bio control.

Annex 9. List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests. The list comprises 11 pests. The crop sectors comprise agriculture, glasshouse, fruit, plants for planting and forestry.

Annex 10. Interceptions per pest of harmful organisms in EU 2007-09. The list comprises 21 pests or pest groups. Above the pests listed after number of interceptions and below list sorted after crop sectors.

Annex 11. Examples on different factors influencing on why certain q-pests have higher priority than other. Many factors influence on how people working with phytosanitary problems regard the threat and importance of a specific q-pest. Eleven examples of different q-pests with different priorities in phytosanitary importance are given.

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.
Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 1.

Overview of harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Classification
1. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Forestry	Conifers	Insect	<i>Acleris</i> spp.	Annex I part A I
5. Ornamentals, cut flowers	Asters	Insect	<i>Amauromyza maculosa</i>	Annex I part A I
6. Agriculture	Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Glasshouse	Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Viticulture, fruit	Vine, fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
9. Forestry	Conifers	Insect	<i>Choristoneura</i> spp	Annex I part A I
10. Plants for planting	Rosea family	Insect	<i>Conotrachelus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
11. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica barberi</i>	Annex I part A I
12. Agriculture	Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
13. Agriculture	Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
14. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	Annex I part A I
15. Agriculture	Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I
16. Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	<i>Hirschmaniella</i> spp	Annex I part A I
17. Agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I

18. Fruit, Viticulture	Peach, vine	Nematode	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
19. Forestry	Conifers (vector of pine wood nematode)	Insect	<i>Monochamus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
20. Plant for planting	Palm (vector of palm lethal yellowing phytoplasma)	Insect	<i>Myndus crudus</i>	Annex I part A I
21. Agriculture	Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
22. Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
24. Forestry	Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus minutissimus</i>	Annex I part A I
25. Forestry	Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus pruinus</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Forestry, plants for planting	Elm (vector of elm phloem necrosis phytoplasma)	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus luteolus</i>	Annex I part A I
27. Agriculture, glasshouse	Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
28. Agriculture	Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
29. Glasshouse, agriculture	Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I
30. Glasshouse, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
31. Fruit	Fruit	Insect	<i>Tephritidae</i> (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
32. Agriculture, fruit	Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematode	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
33. Agriculture, fruit	Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematode	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
34. Viticulture	Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	Annex I part A I
35. Forestry	Oak	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	Annex I part A I
36. Forestry	Picea	Fungi	<i>Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli</i>	Annex I

				part A I
37. Forestry	Conifers	Fungi	<i>Cronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
38. Forestry	Conifers	Fungi	<i>Endocronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
39. Forestry	Larix	Fungi	<i>Guignardia laricina</i>	Annex I part A I
40. Fruit	Fruit, Juniperus	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
41. Forestry	Conifera	Fungi	<i>Inonotus weirii</i>	Annex I part A I
42. Forestry	Tsuga	Fungi	<i>Melampsora farlowii</i>	Annex I part A I
43. Fruit	Stonefruit	Fungi	<i>Monilinia fructicola</i>	Annex I part A I
44. Forestry	Larix	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella larici-leptolepsis</i>	Annex I part A I
45. Plants for planting	Populus	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella populorum</i>	Annex I part A I
46. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Phoma andina</i>	Annex I part A I
47. Fruit	Apple	Fungi	<i>Phyllosticta solitaria</i>	Annex I part A I
48. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex I part A I
49. Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
50. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	Annex I part A I
51. Agriculture	Cereals	Fungi	<i>Tilletia indica</i>	Annex I part A I
52. Agriculture	Cotton	Fungi	<i>Trechispora brinkmannii</i> (Phymatotrichopsis omnivora)	Annex I part A I
53. Forestry	Elms	Virus etc	Elm phloem necrosis mycoplasma	Annex I part A I
54. Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato viruses non European	Annex I part A I
55. Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato spindle tuber viroid	Annex I part A I
56. Agriculture, glasshouse, plants for planting, fruit	Soybean, tobacco, cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
57. Fruit, viticulture	Stonefruit, apple, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
58. Fruit	Fruit and berries	Virus etc	Virus and phytoplasmas infecting <i>Cydonia</i> Mill., <i>Fragaria</i> L., <i>Malus</i> Mill.,	Annex I part A I

			<i>Prunus</i> L., <i>Pyrus</i> L., <i>Ribes</i> L., <i>Rubus</i> L. og <i>Vitis</i> L.	
59. Glasshouse, agriculture	Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
60. Agriculture	Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
61. Agriculture	Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
62. Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
63. Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i>	Annex I part A II
64. Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Opogona sacchari</i>	Annex I part A II
65. Agriculture, fruit, forestry, plants for planting	Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
66. Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	Annex I part A II
67. Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Rhizoecus hibisci</i>	Annex I part A II
68. Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	Annex I part A II
69. Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i>	Annex I part A II
70. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
71. Forestry, plants for planting	Populus, conifera	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
72. Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	Annex I part A II
73. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	Annex I part A II
74. Fruit	Apple	Mycoplasma	Apple proliferation mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
75. Fruit	Stone fruit	Mycoplasma	Apricot chlorotic leafroll mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
76. Fruit	Pear	Mycoplasma	Pear decline mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
77. Glasshouse	Ornamental	Insect	<i>Aculops fuchsiae</i>	Annex II part A I
78. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Aleurocanthus</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
79. Fruit	Strawberry	Insect	<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i> and <i>A. signatus</i>	Annex II part A I
80. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Aonidiella citrina</i>	Annex II

				part A I
81. Agriculture	Rice	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A I
82. Plants for planting	Juniper	Insect	<i>Aschistonyx eppo</i>	Annex II part A I
83. Forestry	Conifera	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
84. Fruit	Pear	Insect	<i>Carposina niponensis</i>	Annex II part A I
85. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	Annex II part A I
86. Fruit	Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	Annex II part A I
87. Fruit, plants for planting	Pome, stonefruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I
88. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	Annex II part A I
89. Fruit	Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Grapholita inopinata</i>	Annex II part A I
90. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Hishomonus phycitis</i>	Annex II part A I
91. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Leucaspis japonica</i>	Annex II part A I
92. Agriculture	Brassicas, clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I
93. Viticulture	Vine	Insect	<i>Margarodes</i> spp	Annex II part A I
94. Fruit	Pear	Insect	<i>Numonia pyrivorella</i>	Annex II part A I
95. Plants for planting	Juniper	Insect	<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	Annex II part A I
96. Forestry	Conifera	Insect	<i>Pissodes</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
97. Citrus fruit, glasshouse	Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
98. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Saissetia nigra</i>	Annex II part A I
99. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Scirtothrips</i> 3 species	Annex II part A I
100. Forestry	Conifera	Insect	<i>Scolytidae</i> spp	Annex II part A I
101. Fruit	Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Tachypterellus quadrigibbus</i>	Annex II part A I
102. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>	Annex II part A I
103. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Trioza erytrae</i>	Annex II

					part A I
104.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Unaspis citri</i>	Annex II part A I
105.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus greening bacterium	Annex II part A I
106.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus variegated chlorosis	Annex II part A I
107.	Agriculture	Maize	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia stewartii</i>	Annex II part A I
108.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i>	Annex II part A I
109.	Agriculture	Rice	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>Oryzae & orizicola</i>	Annex II part A I
110.	Fruit	Pome	Fungi	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Annex II part A I
111.	Fruit, plants for planting	Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I
112.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Apiosporina morbosa</i>	Annex II part A I
113.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Atropellis</i>	Annex II part A I
114.	Forestry, plants for planting	Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
115.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Cercoseptoria pini-densiflorae</i>	Annex II part A I
116.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Cercospora angolensis</i>	Annex II part A I
117.	Glasshouse	Camelia	Fungi	<i>Ciborinia camelliae</i>	Annex II part A I
118.	Fruit	Blueberry	Fungi	<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	Annex II part A I
119.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Elsinoe</i> spp	Annex II part A I
120.	Fruit, plants for planting	Date palm	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>albedines</i>	Annex II part A I
121.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	Annex II part A I
122.	Fruit	Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
123.	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	Annex II part A I
124.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia acicola</i>	Annex II part A I
125.	Fruit	Pear	Fungi	<i>Venturia nashicola</i>	Annex II part A I
126.	Agriculture	Beet	Virus etc.	Beet curly top virus	Annex II

					part A I
127.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Black raspberry latent virus	Annex II part A I
128.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Blight and blight-like	Annex II part A I
129.	Fruit	Coconut	Virus etc.	Cadang-cadang viroid	Annex II part A I
130.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Cherry leaf roll virus	Annex II part A I
131.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus mosaic virus	Annex II part A I
132.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A I
133.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Leprosis	Annex II part A I
134.	Fruit	Stonefruit	Virus etc.	Little cherry pathogen	Annex II part A I
135.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Naturally spreading psorosis	Annex II part A I
136.	Fruit	Coconut	Virus etc.	Palm lethal yellowing mycoplasma	Annex II part A I
137.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Prunus necrotic ringspot virus	Annex II part A I
138.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Satsuma dwarf virus	Annex II part A I
139.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Tatter leaf virus	Annex II part A I
140.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Witches' broom	Annex II part A I
141.	Fruit	Strawberry	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A II
142.	Viticulture	Vine	Insect	<i>Daktulosphaira vitifoliae</i>	Annex II part A II
143.	Field, glasshouse	Ornamental bulbs	Insect	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>	Annex II part A II
144.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer haematoceps</i>	Annex II part A II
145.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer tenellus</i>	Annex II part A II
146.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus orientalis</i>	Annex II part A II
147.	Glasshouse	Ornamental cut flowers	Insect	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Annex II part A II
148.	Glasshouse	Pot plants	Insect	<i>Radopholus similis</i>	Annex II part A II
149.	Glasshouse, field	Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>	Annex II part A II

150.	Glasshouse, field	Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Lirimyza trifolii</i>	Annex II part A II
151.	Agriculture	Alfalfa	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> spp. <i>insidiosus</i>	Annex II part A II
152.	Glasshouse, field	Tomato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>michiganensis</i>	Annex II part A II
153.	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
154.	Glasshouse	Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia chrysanthemi</i> pv. <i>Dianthicola</i> (<i>Pectobacterium dianthicola</i>)	Annex II part A II
155.	Glasshouse	Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas caryophylli</i>	Annex II part A II
156.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>persicae</i>	Annex II part A II
157.	Vegetables	Beans	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>phaseoli</i>	Annex II part A II
158.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>	Annex II part A II
159.	Glasshouse, field	Tomato, chili	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesicatoria</i>	Annex II part A II
160.	Fruit	Strawberry	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
161.	Viticulture	Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylophilus ampelinus</i>	Annex II part A II
162.	Plants for planting	Platanus	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i> f. sp. <i>platani</i>	Annex II part A II
163.	Plant for planting, fruit	Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
164.	Glasshouse, field	Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Didymella ligulicola</i>	Annex II part A II
165.	Glasshouse	Cut flowers (carnation)	Fungi	<i>Phialophora cinerescens</i>	Annex II part A II
166.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Phoma tracheiphila</i>	Annex II part A II
167.	Fruit	Strawberry	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
168.	Plants for planting	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex II part A II
169.	Agriculture	Sunflower	Fungi	<i>Plasmopara halstedii</i>	Annex II part A II
170.	Glasshouse, field	Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>	Annex II part A II
171.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia pini</i>	Annex II part A II

172.	Vegetable	Hop	Fungi	<i>Verticillium albo-atrum</i>	Annex II part A II
173.	Vegetable	Hop	Fungi	<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>	Annex II part A II
174.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Arabis mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
175.	Agriculture	Beet	Virus etc.	Beet leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II
176.	Glasshouse	Chrysanthemum	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid	Annex II part A II
177.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A II
178.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus vein enation woody gall	Annex II part A II
179.	Viticulture	Vine	Phytoplasma	Grapevine flavescence dorée MLO	Annex II part A II
180.	Glasshouse, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
181.	Fruit	Stonefruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus	Annex II part A II
182.	Agriculture	Potato	Phytoplasma	Potato stolbur mycoplasma	Annex II part A II
183.	Fruit	Strawberry, Rubus	Virus etc.	Raspberry ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
184.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	<i>Spiroplasma citri</i>	Annex II part A II
185.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry crinkle virus	Annex II part A II
186.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry latent ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
187.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry mild yellow edge virus	Annex II part A II
188.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Tomato black ring virus	Annex II part A II
189.	Glasshouse, vegetables, agriculture	Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
190.	Glasshouse, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 2.

Overview of harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Sorted after the crop sector and split on crops.

Agriculture

Potato			
1. Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
4. Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
6. Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
7. Potato	Fungi	<i>Phoma andina</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Potato	Fungi	<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	Annex I part A I
9. Potato	Virus etc	Potato viruses non European	Annex I part A I
10. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
11. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
12. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
13. Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i>	Annex I part A II
15. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
16. Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	Annex I part A II
17. Potato	Fungi	<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	Annex II part A I
18. Potato	Phytoplasma	Potato stolbur mycoplasm	Annex II part A II
19. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
Vegetables (field grown)			
20. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
21. Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
22. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I

24. Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I
25. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
27. Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I
28. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
29. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
30. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
31. Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
32. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
33. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
34. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
35. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
Maize			
36. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
37. Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica barberi</i>	Annex I part A I
38. Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
39. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
40. Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	Annex I part A I
41. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I
42. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
43. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
Cereals including rice			
44. Rice	Nematod	<i>Hirschmaniella</i> spp	Annex I part A I
45. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
46. Cereals	Fungi	<i>Tilletia indica</i>	Annex I part A I
47. Rice	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A I
Grasses, clover and alfalfa			
48. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
49. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
50. Brassicas, clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I

51. Alfalfa	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> spp. <i>insidiosus</i>	Annex II part A II
Beets			
52. Beet	Virus etc.	Beet curly top virus	Annex II part A I
53. Beet	Virus etc.	Beet leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II
Sunflower, soybean, Tobacco, Brassica, Cotton			
54. Tomato, <i>tobacco</i> , strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
55. Tomato, tobacco , strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
56. Cotton	Fungi	<i>Trechispora brinkmannii</i> (Phymatotrichopsis omnivora)	Annex I part A I
57. Soybean, tobacco , cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
58. Brassicas , clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I
59. Sunflower	Fungi	<i>Plasmopara halstedii</i>	Annex II part A II
Fruit			
1. Peach, Vine	Nematod	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Fruit	Insect	<i>Tephritidae</i> (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
3. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
4. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Fruit, Juniperus	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Soybean, tobacco, cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
7. Stonefruit, pome, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
8. Fruit and berries	Virus etc	Virus and phytoplasmas infecting <i>Cydonia</i> Mill., <i>Fragaria</i> L., <i>Malus</i> Mill.,	Annex I part A I

		<i>Prunus</i> L., <i>Pyrus</i> L., <i>Ribes</i> L., <i>Rubus</i> L. og <i>Vitis</i> L.,	
9. Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
10. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
11. Blueberry	Fungi	<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	Annex II part A I
12. Coconut	Virus etc.	Cadang-cadang viroid	Annex II part A I
13. Coconut	Virus etc.	Palm lethal yellowing mycoplasm	Annex II part A I
14. Date palm	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>albedines</i>	Annex II part A I
15. Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I
16. Rubus	Virus etc.	Black raspberry latent virus	Annex II part A I
17. Rubus	Virus etc.	Cherry leaf roll virus	Annex II part A I
18. Rubus	Virus etc.	Prunus necrotic ringspot virus	Annex II part A I
19. Pear	Mycoplasma	Pear decline mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
20. Pear	Insect	<i>Carposina niponensis</i>	Annex II part A I
21. Pear	Insect	<i>Numonia pyrivorella</i>	Annex II part A I
22. Pome	Fungi	<i>Phyllosticta solitaria</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Pome	Mycoplasma	Apple proliferation mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
24. Pome	Fungi	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Annex II part A I
25. Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
26. Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
27. Pome, stone fruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I
28. Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Grapholita inopinata</i>	Annex II part A I
29. Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Tachypterellus quadrigibbus</i>	Annex II part A I
30. Vine, stone fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
31. Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Monilinia fructicola</i>	Annex I part A I
32. Stone fruit	Mycoplasma	Apricot chlorotic leafroll mycoplasm	Annex I part A II
33. Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Apiosporina morbosa</i>	Annex II part A I
34. Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Little cherry pathogen	Annex II part A I
35. Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>persicae</i>	Annex II part A II
36. Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>	Annex II part A II
37. Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus	Annex II part A II
38. Strawberry	Insect	<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i> and <i>A. signatus</i>	Annex II part A I
39. Strawberry	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A II
40. Strawberry	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
41. Strawberry	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
42. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Arabis mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
43. Strawberry, Rubus	Virus etc.	Raspberry ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
44. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry crinkle virus	Annex II part A II
45. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry latent ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
46. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry mild yellow edge virus	Annex II part A II

47. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Tomato black ring virus	Annex II part A II
48. Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	Annex II part A I
49. Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
50. Citrus	Insect	<i>Aonidiella citrina</i>	Annex II part A I
51. Citrus	Insect	<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	Annex II part A I
52. Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	Annex II part A I
53. Citrus	Insect	<i>Hishomonus phycitis</i>	Annex II part A I
54. Citrus	Insect	<i>Leucaspis japonica</i>	Annex II part A I
55. Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
56. Citrus	Insect	<i>Saissetia nigra</i>	Annex II part A I
57. Citrus	Insect	<i>Scirtothrips</i> 3 species	Annex II part A I
58. Citrus	Insect	<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>	Annex II part A I
59. Citrus	Insect	<i>Trioza erytrae</i>	Annex II part A I
60. Citrus	Insect	<i>Unaspis citri</i>	Annex II part A I
61. Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus greening bacterium	Annex II part A I
62. Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus variegated chlorosis	Annex II part A I
63. Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i>	Annex II part A I
64. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Cercospora angolensis</i>	Annex II part A I
65. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Elsinoe</i> spp	Annex II part A I
66. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	Annex II part A I
67. Citrus	Virus etc.	Blight and blight-like	Annex II part A I
68. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus mosaic virus	Annex II part A I
69. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A I
70. Citrus	Virus etc.	Leprosis	Annex II part A I
71. Citrus	Virus etc.	Naturally spreading psorosis	Annex II part A I
72. Citrus	Virus etc.	Satsuma dwarf virus	Annex II part A I
73. Citrus	Virus etc.	Tatter leaf virus	Annex II part A I
74. Citrus	Virus etc.	Witches' broom	Annex II part A I
75. Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer haematoceps</i>	Annex II part A II
76. Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer tenellus</i>	Annex II part A II
77. Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus orientalis</i>	Annex II part A II
78. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Phoma tracheiphila</i>	Annex II part A II
79. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A II
80. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus vein enation woody gall	Annex II part A II
81. Citrus	Virus etc.	<i>Spiroplasma citri</i>	Annex II part A II
Viticulture			
1. Vine, fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
2. Peach, vine	Nematod	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Stonefruit, apple, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
5. Vine	Insect	<i>Margarodes</i> spp	Annex II part A I
6. Vine	Insect	<i>Daktulosphaira vitifoliae</i>	Annex II part A II

7. Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylophilus ampelinus</i>	Annex II part A II
Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato) and field ornamentals			
1. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Opogona sacchari</i>	Annex I part A II
2. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Rhizoecus hibisci</i>	Annex I part A II
3. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	Annex I part A II
4. Ornamental	Insect	<i>Aculops fuchsiae</i>	Annex II part A I
5. Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
6. Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Soybean, tobacco, cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
9. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
10. Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
11. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
12. Soybean, tobacco, cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
13. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
14. Ornamental bulbs	Insect	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>	Annex II part A II
15. Ornamental cut flowers	Insect	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Annex II part A II
16. Pot plants	Insect	<i>Radopholus similis</i>	Annex II part A II
17. Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>	Annex II part A II
18. Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Liriomyza trifolii</i>	Annex II part A II
19. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus	Annex II part A II
20. Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia chrysanthemi</i> pv. <i>Dianthicola</i> (<i>Pectobacterium dianthicola</i>)	Annex II part A II
21. Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas caryophylli</i>	Annex II part A II
22. Cut flowers (carnation)	Fungi	<i>Phialophora cinerescens</i>	Annex II part A II
23. Asters	Insect	<i>Amauromyza maculosa</i>	Annex I part A I
24. Camelia	Fungi	<i>Ciborinia camelliae</i>	Annex II part A I
25. Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Didymella ligulicola</i>	Annex II part A II
26. Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>	Annex II part A II
27. Chrysanthemum	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid	Annex II part A II
Tomato			

1. Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
6. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
9. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
10. Tomato, chili	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesicatoria</i>	Annex II part A II
11. Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
12. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
13. Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II
Plants for planting			
1. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Rosea family	Insect	<i>Conotrachelus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
5. Fruit, Juniper	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Populus	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella populorum</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Soybean, tobacco, cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
9. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
10. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
11. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
12. Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	Annex I part A II
13. Populus, conifera	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Juniper	Insect	<i>Aschistonyx eppo</i>	Annex II part A I
15. Pome, stonefruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I

16. Juniper	Insect	<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	Annex II part A I
17. Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I
18. Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
19. Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
20. Platanus	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i> f. sp. <i>platani</i>	Annex II part A II
21. Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
22. Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex II part A II
Forestry			
1. Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
2. Conifers	Insect	<i>Acleris</i> spp.	Annex I part A I
3. Conifers	Insect	<i>Choristoneura</i> spp	Annex I part A I
4. Conifers (vector of pine wood nematode)	Insect	<i>Monochamus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
5. Conifers	Fungi	<i>Cronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Conifers	Fungi	<i>Endocronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
7. Conifera	Fungi	<i>Inonotus weirii</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Conifera	Insect	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
9. Conifera	Insect	<i>Pissodes</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
10. Conifera	Insect	<i>Scolytidae</i> spp	Annex II part A I
11. Elms	Virus etc	Elm phloem necrosis mycoplasma	Annex I part A I
12. Elm (vector of elm phloem necrosis phytoplasma)	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus luteolus</i>	Annex I part A I
13. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Larch	Fungi	<i>Guignardia laricina</i>	Annex I part A I
15. Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus minutissimus</i>	Annex I part A I
16. Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus pruinosis</i>	Annex I part A I
17. Oak	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	Annex I part A I
18. Spruce	Fungi	<i>Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli</i>	Annex I part A I
19. Pine	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	Annex I part A II
20. Pine	Fungi	<i>Atropellis</i>	Annex II part A I
21. Pine	Fungi	<i>Cercoseptoria pini-densiflorae</i>	Annex II part A I
22. Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia acicola</i>	Annex II part A I
23. Poplar, conifer	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
24. Tsuga	Fungi	<i>Melampsora farlowii</i>	Annex I part A I
25. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
27. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I

EUPHRESKO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 3.

Topic calls from EUPHRESKO-1 and EUPHRESKO-2 (2011) split on crops

Call title	Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
		Potato		
Potato brown rot and potato ring rot. Validation of methods that can be approved for use via control directives.	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> , <i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>
Potato cyst nematodes. Ringtesting methods for identification and resistance testing.	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	Potato cyst nematodes
<i>Dickeya</i> species in potato and management strategies.	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Dickeya dianthicola</i> , <i>D. solani</i>
Use of novel molecular methods to understand population diversity and its implication on disease management through use of resistant potato varieties	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	Potato cyst nematodes
Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for detection and identification of <i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i> in support of integrated plant protection strategies	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i>
Diagnostic methods for <i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i> , especially for pathotype identification	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>
Epidemiology and diagnosis of potato phytoplasmas and Candidatus <i>Liberibacter solanacearum</i> and their contribution to risk management	Agriculture	Potato	Mycoplasma	Potato mycoplasmas
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals, tomato, potato	Virus etc.	<i>Potato spindle tuber viroid</i> <i>a.o. pospiviroids</i>
		Various ag-		

		gricultural crops		
<i>Erwinia stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i> , maize bacterial blight. Validation and ring testing of diagnostic methods.	Agriculture	Maize	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i>
Validation of diagnostic methods for the detection and identification of whitefly transmitted viruses of regulatory or quarantine concern to EU.	Field crops, glasshouse	Ornamentals, vegetables	Viruses	Bean golden mosaic, Lettuce infectious yellows, Pepper mild tigré, Euphorbia mosaic a.o. viruses
		Tomato		
Assessment of the risk posed by ornamentals and tomato seeds infected by Pospiviroids to tomato crops and evaluation of Pospiviroid detection protocols for seed testing in tomato	Glasshouse, field crop	Tomato	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals, tomato, potato	Virus etc.	<i>Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids</i>
		Ornamentals		
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals, tomato, potato	Virus etc.	<i>Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids</i>
Validation of diagnostic methods for the detection and identification of whitefly transmitted viruses of regulatory or quarantine concern to EU.	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals, vegetables	Viruses	Bean golden mosaic, Lettuce infectious yellows, Pepper mild tigré, Euphorbia mosaic a.o. viruses
		Fruit		
Interlaboratory comparison and validation of detection methods for phytoplasmas of phytosanitary concern in European orchards.	Fruit	Fruit trees	Phytoplasma	Phytoplasmas
Evaluation of factors determining distribution, impact, detection and characterization of apple proliferation and other fruit tree phytoplasmoses in the European Community	Fruit	Fruit trees	Mycoplasmas	Apple proliferation and other fruit tree phytoplasmoses

Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for the detection of fire blight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>).	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, ornamental trees	Bacteria	<i>Malus, Pyrus, Crataegus, Cotoneaster a.o.</i>
Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight	Fruit and plants for planting	Fruit trees, hawthorn etc	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
Damage potential of <i>Drosophila suzukii</i> and development of phytosanitary measures	Fruit	Fruit trees, grapevine	Insect	<i>Drosophila suzukii</i>
		Vine		
Evaluation of the risk of spread of <i>Scaphoideus titanus</i> , the vector of grapevine flavescence dorée, with commercial grapevine propagation material.	Viticulture	Vine	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus titanus</i>
Epidemiological studies on reservoir hosts and potential vectors of Grapevine flavescence dorée (GFD) and validation of different diagnostic procedures for GFD	Viticulture	Vine	Mycoplasma	Grapevine flavescence dorée
		Plants for planting		
Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for the detection of fire blight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>).	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, ornamental trees	Bacteria	<i>Malus, Pyrus, Crataegus, Cotoneaster a.o.</i>
Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight	Fruit and plants for planting	Fruit trees, hawthorn etc	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
Risk management for the EC listed <i>Anoplophora</i> species, <i>A. chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>
Current and emerging <i>Phytophthora</i> : research supporting risk assessment and risk management	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Fungi	<i>P. ramorum, kernoviae, lateralis</i>
		Forestry		
Phytosanitary Efficacy of Kiln Drying.	Forestry	Various trees	Various	Various
Risk management for the EC listed <i>Anoplophora</i> species, <i>A. chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>
Current and emerging <i>Phytophthora</i> : research supporting risk assessment and risk management	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Fungi	<i>P. ramorum, kernoviae, lateralis</i>

		Other topics		
Strategies for Ambrosia control.	Agriculture	Various	Weed plant	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>
Whole genomic amplification methods	All	All	Various	Various
Management of invasive alien aquatic/riparian weeds.	None	None	Plant	Various

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 4

Overview of harmful organisms listed in EPPO's Alert List (last updated September 2011).

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
Tomato	Tomato		
1. Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Insect	<i>Keiferia lycopersicella</i>
2. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<i>Pepino mosaic virus</i>
3. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<i>Tomato apical stunt pospiviroid</i>
4. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<i>Tomato torrado virus</i>
5. Potato, agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	<i>Leucinodes orbonalis</i>
6. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato, chilli, sweet pepper	Bacteria	' <i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i> '
Potato	Potato		
7. Potato, agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	<i>Leucinodes orbonalis</i>
8. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato, chilli, sweet pepper	Bacteria	' <i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i> '
9. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>
Maize	Maize		
10. Agriculture	Maize	Bacteria	<i>Spiroplasma kunkelii</i>
11. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>
12. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>
13. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>
Other agriculture crops	Other agriculture crops		

14. Agriculture	Sunflower	Insect	<i>Strauzia longipennis</i>
15. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>
16. Agriculture, glass-house, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>
17. Agriculture, glass-house	Lettuce	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. lactucae</i>
Glasshouse	Glasshouse		
18. Glasshouse	Ornamental pot plant	Fungi	<i>Melampsora euphorbiae</i>
Fruit	Fruit		
19. Citrus fruit, agriculture	Citrus, melon	Bacteria	<i>Acidovorax citrulli</i>
20. Fruit	Ficus, morus	Insect	<i>Psacotheta hilaris</i>
21. Fruit	Kiwi	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae pv. actinidiae</i>
22. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>
23. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i>
Plants for planting	Plants for planting		
24. Plants for planting	Horse chestnut	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae pv. aesculi</i>
25. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>
26. Forestry, plants for planting	Beech, rhododendron	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora kernoviae</i>
27. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum, oak	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>
28. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>
29. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i>
Forestry	Forestry		
30. Forestry	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	Insect	<i>Chrysophtharta bimaculata</i>

31. Forestry	Oak species	Insect	<i>Enaphalodes rufulus</i>
32. Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora pinifolia</i>
33. Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i>
34. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>
35. Forestry, plants for planting	Beech, rhododendron	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora kernoviae</i>
36. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum, oak	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>
37. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i>

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 5.

Lists of most important crops (other than forestry) in countries in the Baltic Sea-Nordic countries Region

	Estonia	Denmark	Finland	Germany	Latvia	Lithuania	Sweden	Poland
Agricultural crops	Spring barley Winter barley Spring wheat Winter wheat Oat Rye Triticale Mixed grain Potato Spring oil rape Winter oil rape Grass fodder Clover Legumes Lucerne	Grass (for fodder) Legumes (for fodder) Maize (for fodder) Winter wheat Winter barley Sugar beet Potato Winter oil seed rape Seed (grass, clover and spinach) Rye Oat Triticale	Grass (for fodder) Barley (for fodder) Oat Spring wheat Potato Barley (for malting) Oil seed rape Winter wheat Rye Sugar beets	Corn Winter wheat Winter barley Oil seed rape Potato Sugar beet Forage crops / Leguminous	Potato Winter wheat Barley Oil seed rape Grass (for fodder) Rye Oat Seed (grass, clover) Maize (for fodder)	Spring barley Winter wheat Spring oil seed rape Oat Triticale Spring wheat Rye Winter oil seed rape Potato Legumes (for fodder) Maize (for fodder) Sugar beet Winter barley	Grass (for fodder) Wheat Barley Oat Oil seed rape Sugar beet Potato	Wheat (Winter, Spring) Rye Barley Oat Oil seed rape Sugar beet Potato Triticale Cereals mixtures Buckwheat, millet and other cereals Maize Oil rape Potato Sugar Beet Tobacco Hops Clover Lucerne Esparcet Mixtures Perennial

								grasses Forage grasses Lupine Pea Bean
Vegetables in field	Carrots Cabbages Root beet Cucumber Onion Swedish turnip		Carrots Cabbages Onion Pea	Cabbage Spinach Onions (Asparagus)	Cabbages Carrots Onion Root beet Cucumbers	Carrots Onion Cabbages Red beet Cucumber Leaf and stem vege- tables	Lettuce Carrots Onion Cabbages Root beet Leek	Pea Bean Cabbage Onion Carrot Red beet Tomato Cucumber Chinese cabbage
Fruit and berries	Apples and pears Strawberry Black cur- rants Plums	Strawberry	Strawberry	Apple Cherry Strawberry	Apples Strawberry	Apple Strawberry Blackberry	Pears Apples Plums Cherries Strawberry	Apple Cherry Plum Pear Peach Apricot Walnut Hazelnut Grape Strawberry Black cur- rant Raspberry Red and White Cur- rents Gooseberry

								Blueberry Black chokeberry
Protected crops (glasshouse)		Pot plants	Tomato Cucumber Ornamental pot plants		Pot plants		Cucumber Tomatoes Potted let- tuce Potted herbal spic- es Cutflowers from bulbs, mainly tu- lips: Pot plants Small plants and cuttings	Tomato Cucumber Mushroom Pot plants
Nurseries garden plants							Nursery plants	

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 6

Lists of most important crops (other than forestry) in countries in the Baltic Sea-Nordic countries Region

Sorted after how many countries have included the crop in their list

	Estonia	Denmark	Finland	Germany	Latvia	Lithuania	Sweden	Poland
Agricultural crops								
Barley	Winter barley Spring barley	Winter barley	Barley	Winter barley	Barley	Winter barley Spring barley	Barley	Winter barley Spring barley
Wheat	Winter wheat Spring wheat	Winter wheat	Winter wheat Spring wheat	Winter wheat	Winter wheat	Winter wheat Spring wheat	Wheat	Winter wheat Spring wheat
Oat	Oat	Oat	Oat		Oat	Oat	Oat	Oats
Rye	Rye	Rye	Rye		Rye	Rye		Rye
Triticale	Triticale	Triticale				Triticale		Triticale
Mixed grain	Mixed grain							Mixed grain
Grass fodder	Grass fodder	Grass fodder	Grass fodder	Grass fodder	Grass fodder		Grass fodder	Grass fodder
Legumes fodder	Legumes fodder	Legumes fodder		Legumes fodder		Legumes fodder		Legumes fodder
Potato	Potato	Potato	Potato	Potato	Potato	Potato	Potato	Potato
Winter rape	Winter rape	Winter rape	Oil seed rape	Oil seed rape	Oil seed rape	Winter rape	Oil seed rape	Oil rape
Spring rape	Spring rape					Spring rape		
Maize fodder		Maize fodder		Maize	Maize fodder	Maize fodder		Maize
Sugar beets		Sugar beet	Sugar beets	Sugar beet		Sugar beet	Sugar beet	Sugar Beet
Seeds		Seed (grass, clover and spinach)			Seed (grass, clover)			
Other cereals								Buckwheat, millet and other cereals
Tobacco								Tobacco
Hops								Hops

Field vegetables Cabbages Carrots Onion Root beet Cucumber Leaf & stem vegetables Pea Bean Tomato	Cabbages Carrots Onion Root beet Cucumber Swedish turnip	Cabbages Carrots Onion Root beet Leek Pea	Cabbages Carrots Onion Pea	Cabbages Onions Spinach Asparagus	Cabbages Carrots Onion Root beet Cucumbers	Cabbages Carrots Onion Root beet Cucumber Leaf & stem vegetables	Cabbages Carrots Onion Root beet Lettuce Leek	Cabbage Carrot Onion Root beet Cucumber Chinese cabbage Pea Bean Tomato
Fruit and berries Strawberry Apple Pear Black currant Cherry Plums Other stone fruit Nuts Other berries	Strawberry Apples Pears Black currant Plums	Strawberry	Strawberry	Strawberry Apple Cherry	Strawberry Apples	Strawberry Apple Black currant	Strawberry Apples Pears Cherry Plums	Strawberry Apple Pear Black currant Cherry Plums Peach Apricot Walnut Hazelnut Raspberry Red currants Gooseberry Blueberry Black chokeberry Grape
Glasshouse crops Pot plants Tomato		Pot plants	Pot plants Tomato		Pot plants		Pot plants Tomatoes	Pot plants Tomato

Cucumber Potted vegetables			Cucumber				Cucumber Potted lettuce Potted herbal spices Cut flowers	Cucumber
Cut flowers Mushroom								Mushroom
Nurseries garden plants							Nursery plants	

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 7

Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary threats (other than forestry) according to NPPO's in countries in the Baltic Sea-Nordic countries Region sorted after importance by each NPPO

	Estonia	Denmark	Finland	Germany	Latvia	Lithuania	Sweden	Poland
		<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Virus diseases in cherries (e.g. Little Cherry Disease)	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>sepedonicus</i>	<i>Tuta absoluta</i>	<i>Clavibacter michiganense</i> ssp. <i>sepedonicus</i>
		<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Viruses and viroids in greenhouse vegetable production	Phytoplasma in fruit trees	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	<i>Globodera ros-tochiensis</i> and <i>G. pallida</i>	<i>Epitrix</i> sp.	<i>Globorera</i> sp.
		<i>Agrilus sinu-atus</i>	Tomato tor-rado virus	Colorado beetle	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	<i>Ditylenchus destructor</i>	<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp, i.e <i>Meloidoygne chitwoodi</i>	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>
		<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> and <i>P.kernoviae</i> a.o. species on woody plants	Pelargonium zonate spot virus	Potato nema-todes	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> and <i>P.kernoviae</i>	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	Insect borne virus diseases, which we can see in the per-spective of cli-mate change	<i>Dickeya</i>
		Plum pox virus	Potato spin-dle tuber vi-roid	Common Pollen Bee-tle	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> ssp. <i>sepedonicus</i>	Phytoplasma (apple and pear)	Pests and dis-eases on maize	<i>Pectobacterium atrosepticum</i>

		<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i> var. <i>rubi</i>	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Resistances against insecticides	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	<i>Pectobacterium carotovorum</i> subsp. <i>carotovorum</i>
		<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	<i>Agrilus anxius</i>	Rapid molecular diagnostic methods for quarantine pests	<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	<i>Plum pox virus</i>	<i>Scirrhia acicola</i> , syn. <i>Mycosphaerella dearnessii</i>	<i>Clavibacter michiganense</i> ssp. <i>michiganensis</i>
		<i>Agrilus planipennis</i>	<i>Epitrix</i>			<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>
		<i>Agrilus anxius</i>	<i>Syncytrium endobioticum</i>			<i>Liriomyza</i> sp.	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Potato Virus Y
		<i>Mycosphaerella pini</i>	Risk to natural environment caused by increased import of <i>Vaccinium</i> species (<i>Dasineura oxycoccana</i> , <i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i> and <i>Blueberry scorch virus</i>)			<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	Influence of climatic changes and agricultural practice
		<i>Mycosphaerella dearnessii</i>	Influence of climatic changes			Pepino mosaic potexvirus	<i>Globodera ros-tochiensis</i> and <i>G. pallida</i>	Influence of new pathogen populations on crop resistance and its chemical protection
		<i>Epitrix</i> spp.	Suitability of			<i>Phytophthora</i>	<i>Phytophthora</i>	Introduction,

			biological control for harmful organisms			<i>ramorum</i>	<i>ramorum</i> a.o. <i>Phytophthora</i> species	development and modification of IPM systems
		<i>Apple proliferation phytoplasma</i>	Applications of image analysis and computer vision in plant health inspections			<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> spp. <i>michiganensis</i>	Sustainable use of plant protection products (IPM)	Complex studies on quarantine diseases and pests
		PSTVd				<i>Puccinia horiana</i>	Cost-benefit analysis on control strategies	Preventive measures applied including new developments in diagnostics, studies on IPM, new methods for utilization of infected crop
		<i>Ca. Liberibacter solanacearum</i>				<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	Management options and decision-making schemes	Development of multi aspects system of pathogen control
		Biofuel				<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>		Exploitation of genetic crop resistance
		Bark				<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>		
		Wood package				<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>		
						<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>		
						<i>Mycosphaerella</i> sp.		

						Potato spindle tuber viroid		
						<i>Thrips palmi</i>		

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.
Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 8

NPPO's in countries in the Baltic Sea-Nordic countries Region split on crop sectors and crops in descending order of numbers of countries (7) listing the pest.

No. of countries listing the pest	Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
4	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> , <i>G. pallida</i> a.o. potato nematodes
3	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Syncytrium endobioticum</i>
3	Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Epitrix</i> spp.
3	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>sepedonicus</i>
1	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp, i.e <i>Meloidogyne</i> <i>chitwoodi</i>
1	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Dickeya</i> sp.
1	Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato VirusY
1	Agriculture	Potato	Insect	Colorado beetle
1	Agriculture	Potato, vegeta- bles	Bacteria	<i>Ca. Liberibacter solanacearum</i>
1	Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegeta- bles	Nematode	<i>Ditylenchus destructor</i>
1	Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>
1	Agriculture	Maize	Several	Pests and diseases on maize
1	Agriculture	Crucifera	Insect	Common Pollen Beetle (<i>Meligethes</i> <i>aeneus</i>)
2	Glasshouse	Tomato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>michiganensis</i>
1	Glasshouse	Tomato	Insect	<i>Tuta absoluta</i>
1	Glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato torrado virus
1	Glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic potexvirus
3	Glasshouse	Tomato, orna- mentals	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid
1	Glasshouse	Vegetables	Virus etc.	Viruses and viroids in greenhouse vegetable production
1	Glasshouse	Vegetables, or- namentials	Insect	<i>Liriomyza</i> sp.

1	Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>
1	Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>
1	Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Virus etc.	Pelargonium zonate spot virus
1	Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>
3	Fruit	Apple and pear	Virus etc.	Phytoplasma in fruit trees, <i>Apple proliferation phytoplasma</i>
2	Fruit	Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus
2	Fruit	Blueberry cranberry	Fungi	<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>
2	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
1	Fruit	Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Virus diseases in cherries (e.g. Little Cherry Disease)
1	Fruit	Strawberry	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i> var. <i>rubi</i>
1	Fruit	Strawberry	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>
6	Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> , <i>P.kernoviae</i> a.o. <i>Phytophthora</i> species on woody plants
4	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>
4	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>
1	Plants for planting	Hawthorn	Insect	<i>Agrilus sinuatus</i> (hawthorn jewel beetle)
3	Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella pini</i> , <i>M. dearnessii</i>
2	Forestry	Conifers	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>
2	Forestry	Birch	Insect	<i>Agrilus anxius</i> (bronze birch borer)
1	Forestry	Ash	Insect	<i>Agrilus planipennis</i> (emerald ash borer)
1	Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>
No. of countries listed the topic	General problem	General topic		Specific description
3	The ecosystem	Climatic changes		Influence of climatic changes. Influence of climatic changes and agricultural practice. Insect borne virus diseases, which we can see in the perspective of climate change.
3	Pests	Diagnostics		Rapid molecular diagnostic methods for quarantine pests.

				New developments in diagnostics. Applications of image analysis and computer vision in plant health inspections.
2	Plant growing	IPM, integrated plant management		Sustainable use of plant protection products. Introduction, development and modification of IPM systems.
2	Pests and crops	Resistance		Resistances against insecticides. Influence of new pathogen populations on crop resistance and its chemical protection. Exploitation of genetic crop resistance.
2	Control	Management and cost benefit		Management options and decision-making schemes. Cost-benefit analysis on control strategies. Development of multi aspects system of pathogen control. New methods for utilization of infected crop
2	Pests	Complex studies		Complex studies on quarantine diseases and pests. Risk to natural environment caused by increased import of <i>Vaccinium</i> species (<i>Dasineura oxycoccana</i> , <i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i> and <i>Blueberry scorch virus</i>)
1	Pests	Bio control		Suitability of biological control for harmful organisms.
1	Forestry	Bio fuel, wood packaging, bark		Wood chips imported from other continents. Wood packaging. Bark as component in growing media and for groundcover.

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.
Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 9.

List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Comments
191. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	
192. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	
193. Glasshouse, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	As regards Thailand
194. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	
195. Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid	
196. Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	
197. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Import from Egypt
198. Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	
199. Forestry	Conifera	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> pine wood nematode	
200. Fruit	Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	
201. Glasshouse, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.
Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 10.

Overview of interceptions per pest of harmful organisms in EU 2007-09

Sorted after number of interceptions

Crop sector	Crop	Organism group	Pest	2007	2008	2009
Conglomerated data for selected groups of organisms						
Glasshouse	Ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	White flies, <i>Bemisia</i>	202	302	243
Fruit	Fruit	Insect	Fruit flies, <i>Tephritidae</i> , non-European	389	292	286
Glasshouse, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	Thrips, <i>Thrips palmi</i>	289	307	306
Glasshouse, agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Leafminers, <i>Liriomyza</i>	139	271	318
Agriculture, glasshouse	Vegetables, tomato, grass, maize, rice, potato, ornamental flower/ ornamental flower	Insect/insect	Spodoptera/Helicoverpa	417	334	104
Other organisms						
Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	66	149	74
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	<i>Sinoxylon</i> sp. (not on the q-list)	36	22	56
Agriculture	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	Leucinodes orbonalis (on EP-PO's Alert list)	18	37	26
Fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Xanthomonas axonopodis pv. citri (EPPO quarantine pest)	28	25	25
Agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Agromyzidae (<i>Liriomyza</i> spp. a.o. leaf miners)	51	7	12
Glasshouse	Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	Aleyrodidae (<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> a.o. hemipteras)	60	3	5
Forestry	Larch tree	Fungi	<i>Guignardia</i> sp.	42	4	3
Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	36	9	-
Plants for planting	Box tree	Insect	<i>Diaphania indica</i> (box tree)	12	23	9

ing			moth)			
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	Bostrichidae (wood borer)	15	19	8
Fruit	Macadamia nuts	Insect	Chryptophlebia leucotreta	13	3	22
Forestry	Conifers	Insect	Scolytidae (<i>Gnathotrichus sulcatus</i>)	12	19	4
Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	Meloidogyne sp.	3	17	14
Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Virus	Pepino mosaic virus	11	14	6
Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	Cerambycidae (<i>Anoplophora</i> spp.)	13	11	6
Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	Hirschmanniella sp.	11	10	6

Sorted after crop sector

Crop sector	Crop	Organism group	Pest	2007	2008	2009
Conglomerated data for selected groups of organisms						
Glasshouse	Ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	White flies, <i>Bemisia</i>	202	302	243
Fruit	Fruit	Insect	Fruit flies, <i>Tephritidae</i> , non-European	389	292	286
Glasshouse, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	Thrips, <i>Thrips palmi</i>	289	307	306
Glasshouse, agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Leafminers, <i>Liriomyza</i>	139	271	318
Glasshouse, agriculture	Vegetables, tomato, grass, maize, rice, potato, ornamental flower/ ornamental flower	Insect/insect	Spodoptera/Helicoverpa	417	334	104
Other organisms						
Agriculture	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	Leucinodes orbonalis (on EP-PO's Alert list)	18	37	26
Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	Meloidogyne sp.	3	17	14
Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	Hirschmanniella sp.	11	10	6
Agriculture, glasshouse	Vegetables	Insect	Agromyzidae (<i>Liriomyza</i> spp. a.o. leaf miners)	51	7	12
Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Virus	Pepino mosaic virus	11	14	6
Glasshouse	Glasshouse or-	Insect	Aleyrodidae (hemipteras other	60	3	5

	namentals and vegetables		than <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>)			
Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	66	149	74
Fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas axonopodis</i> pv. <i>citri</i> (EPPO quarantine pest)	28	25	25
Fruit	Macadamia nuts	Insect	<i>Chryptophlebia leucotreta</i>	13	3	22
Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	36	9	-
Plants for planting	Box tree	Insect	<i>Diaphania indica</i> (box tree moth)	12	23	9
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	<i>Sinoxylon</i> sp. (not on the q-list)	36	22	56
Forestry	Larch tree	Fungi	<i>Guignardia</i> sp.	42	4	3
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	Bostrichidae (wood borer)	15	19	8
Forestry	Conifers	Insect	Scolytidae (<i>Gnathotrichus sulcatus</i>)	12	19	4
Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	Cerambycidae (Anoplophora spp.)	13	11	6

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of the Baltic Sea and Nordic countries.

Tallin 1st – 2nd December 2011

Annex 11.

Examples on different factors influencing on why certain q-pests have higher priority than other.

Many factors influence on how people working with phytosanitary problems regard the threat and importance of a specific q-pest. Some of the factors are: the status of the pest: is it absent, introduced, under spreading or established. The migration biology of the pest: naturally spreading by short or long distance migration; airborne, soilborne, waterborne; the influence of human transport. The number of host plants (one, few or many host plants) and the economical importance of each host plants. The habitat of the host plants: intensively cultivated field or glasshouse crops, landscape and park plants, forestry etc.

All these and more factors influence why certain pests and associated crops are more in focus than other and initiation of research projects have different priority.

Examples:

1. The pest is strongly regulated and no interception or registration has been obtained the last many years: f. ex. *Atropellis* spp. (Atropellis cancer in pine). Very low priority.
2. No interception or registration of the pest has been obtained the last many years: f. ex. Oak wilt (*Ceratocystis fagacearum*). Very low priority, but research might still be relevant because of the risk to introduce the pest with import with wood chip from North America.
3. No interception or registration of the pest has been obtained the last many years: f. ex. Andean potato viruses. Very low priority, but research might still be relevant because a lot of efforts are put into preventive testing.
4. The pest has changed pathogenisity and spreads naturally by long distance transport, f. ex. Ash die-back (*Chalara fraxinea*). Eradication impossible, only isolated regions (islands) can maybe resist infection. Low priority.
5. The pest has changed pathogenisity and increases host spectrum and spreads naturally only by short distance transport, f. ex. Sudden Oak Death (*Phytophthora ramorum*). Eradication possible. High priority
6. The pest has invaded Europe and spreads naturally by the pests' migration, f.ex. horse-chestnut leaf-miner (*Cameraria ohridella*). Prevention of migration not possible, but impediment is. Low priority.
7. The pest has invaded Europe and spreads naturally by the pests' migration, f.ex. Western Corn Rootworm (*Diabrotica virgifera*) Eradication not possible any more, but impediment is. The pest connected to an agricultural crop. Regulation has a high priority.
8. The pest has recently been established in one member country, where it is under eradication measures, f. ex. Pine wood nematode (*Bursaphelenchus xylophilis*). High priority.

9. The pest has recently been introduced repeatedly in some member states and eradication initiated f. ex. citrus long - horned beetle. High priority.
10. The pest is repeatedly intercepted and sometimes introduced and subsequently eradicated, f.ex. the whitefly *Bemisia tabaci*. Low priority, because the biology and eradication methods are well known.
11. The pest is established in small areas in many member states and repeatedly under eradication, f. ex. fireblight (*Erwinia amylovora*). Potato ring rot (*Corynebacterium sepedonicum* subsp. *sepedonicus*), potato cyst nematode (*Globodera* spp.) Priority? Depends on many factors.

The main conclusion from this workshop was that there was some limited under-representation of some plant sectors or crops (e.g. strawberry and vaccinum species) but otherwise no other crops were under-represented in the EUPHRESCO initiated projects to date.

Concerning specific plant health problems the conclusion was that the unique Nordic-Baltic regional problems have been covered in a more satisfactory way under EUPHRESCO-2 than under EUPHRESCO-1. The recommendation is to include much more general plant health topics as for example the influence of climatic changes and import of plant products for energy production on plant health in the future call rounds.

- **A workshop exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe was held in Sofia 28–29 February 2012.**

The Report, with conclusions and recommendations, from the workshop is provided here:

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.

Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Participants

All EUPHRESCO partners and observers in the Balkan-Eastern European region were invited to the workshop. Ten partners contributed to the background materials and concerning the most important crops in the region information were drawn from EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT for the missing information.

Participants and excuses:

List of participants:

Jana Erjavec, Slovenia
Erika Oresek, Slovenia
Biljana Korunoska, Machedonia
Krstes Tashev, Machedonia
Natalia Sherokolava, Russia
Irene Vloutoglou, Greece
Steen Lykke Nielsen, Denmark
Olia Karadjova, Bulgaria
Zhenya Ilieva, Bulgaria
Elena Petrova, Bulgaria
Ventsislav Ventsislavov, Bulgaria
Nikolay Petrov, Bulgaria
Maria Stoyanova, Bulgaria
Miroslava Valkova, Bulgaria
Daniela Georgieva, Bulgaria
Tzenko Vatchev, Bulgaria
Vladimir Krumov, Bulgaria
Ganka Baeva, Bulgaria
Stoyka Masheva, Bulgaria
Boiko Likov, Bulgaria
Violeta Koloma, Bulgaria

List of apologies:

Czech Republic
Turkey
Romania
Serbia
Cyprus
Ukraine

Annexes

Programme.

Annex 0-1. Introduction and overview of background materials. The present Annex.

Annex 0-2. Short analyse of the background material. Most of the Annexes are analysed and the main results are highlighted.

Annex 1. A list of the harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community. The listing follows the order of the Annexes and the order of pests in the Annexes. A column titled “crop sector” classified into Agriculture, Fruit, Citrus fruit, Viticulture, Glasshouse, Tomato, Plants for planting and Forestry is added. The list includes 189 pests.

Annex 2. The pests from Annex 1 classified to crop sectors and split into crops. The crop sectors are agriculture with 59 pests, fruits with 89 pests, viticulture with 7 pests, protected ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato) and field ornamentals with 27 pests, tomato with 13 pests, plants for planting with 22 pests and forestry with 27 pests.

Annex 3. Topic calls from EUPHRESCO-1 and EUPHRESCO-2 (2011) split on crops. The list shows the 20 projects initiated by EUPHRESCO until now. Split on crops/crop sectors the topics spread as follows: 8 on potato, 1 on maize, 1 on field vegetables, 2 on tomato, 2 on glasshouse ornamentals, 5 on fruit, 2 on vine, 4 on plants for planting, 3 on forestry and 3 on other more general aspects.

Annex 4. EPPO’s Alert List split on crops: The September 2011 version includes 37 pests with 10 pests on tomato, 3 on potato, 4 on maize, 4 on other agricultural crops (cotton, sunflower, lettuce), 1 on glasshouse ornamentals, 5 on fruit and citrus fruit, 6 on plants for planting and 8 on forestry.

Annex 5. Lists of most important crops (other than forestry) in countries in the Balkan and Eastern European Region. The list comprises input from Balkan and Eastern European countries.

Annex 6a. The lists of Appendix 5 sorted after how many countries have included the specific crop in their list.

Annex 6b. Power point presentation of Annex 5 & 6.

Annex 7. Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary threats (other than forestry) according to NPPO’s in countries in the Balkan and Eastern European Region sorted after importance by each NPPO. However not much weight should be laid on the sorting after importance, because the NPPOs used different criteria for making the lists. Some NPPOs made a list of what they consider as the most important phytosanitary threats present, while other NPPOs made a list of the quarantine pests they carry out official monitoring for and one NPPO made a list of topic proposals for future transnational EUPHRESCO projects. The list of forestry pests is not complete, because this topic has been covered by a separate workshop, so not all NPPOs have included forestry pests in their lists.

Annex 8. The list of Annex 7 split on crop sectors and crops and listed in descending order of numbers of countries listing the pest. The crop sectors comprise agriculture, protected crops (glasshouse, screen-house, plastic coverage etc.), viticulture, fruits (split on citrus, pome, stone fruit and berries), plants for planting and forestry besides more general phytosanitary problems as for example diagnostics, climatic changes and invasive weeds.

Annex 8 B. Shortlist of Annex 8 only including pests stated by two or more partners.

Annex 9. List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests. The list comprises 11 pests. The crop sectors comprise agriculture, protected crops, fruit, plants for planting and forestry.

Annex 10. Interceptions per pest of harmful organisms in EU 2007-09. The list comprises 21 pests or pest groups. Above the pests listed after number of interceptions and below list sorted after crop sectors.

Annex 11. Examples on different factors influencing on why certain q-pests have higher priority than other. Many factors influence on how people working with phytosanitary problems regard the threat and importance of a specific q-pest. Eleven examples of different q-pests with different priorities in phytosanitary importance are given.

Annex 12. EU Framework Programme (FP) 6 and FP7 plant health projects (excluding forestry related projects). The list gives an overview of the plant health research projects initiated under FP6 and FP7 and projects related to plant health.

Notes from the workshop's day 1, the 28th February 2012.

Olia Karadjova welcomed the participants and read the formal welcome on behalf of Prof. Georgi Kostov, who unfortunately had to send apologies.

The background materials were presented to the participants and the usefulness for the final discussions and conclusions were discussed.

From the presentation of the Annex 5 & 6, the lists of most important crops (other than forestry) in countries in the Balkan and Eastern European Region it appeared that the Balkan-Eastern European region is very inhomogeneous in climate and plant sectors/crops. Especially Greece and Cyprus deviate from the Balkan region in having a Mediterranean climate and much higher degree of the two permanent crops: citrus and olives.

The Directive 2000/29/EC will soon be revised. It was discussed if this fact would influence the conclusions from the workshop. It was concluded that this fact will not influence the EUPHRESCO activities, because EUPHRESCO already includes upcoming pests and the background materials, besides Directive 2000/29/EC, also includes EPPO's Alert List, a list of EU's emergency measures and an actual list of what the NPPOs in the region consider as the present most important plant health threats.

The future for EUPHRESCO, when the Commission's grant to EUPHRESCO-2 runs out by the end of 2013 was briefly mentioned, but it was agreed that it was not a real topic for the workshop.

Notes from the workshop's 2nd day the 29th February 2012 and conclusions and recommendations

The following conclusions were drawn:

Concerning regionalisation, to the question: “Are there specific regional plant health problems in the Balkan-Eastern European region which makes a regional approach relevant for EUPHRESCO?” the workshop participants concluded NO. On this background no further recommendations were worked out.

Concerning underrepresented plant sectors:

To the question: “Are there some specific plant sectors/crops in the Balkan-Eastern Europe region, which have been underrepresented in the EUPH-1 and the EUPH-2 (2011) topic identification and project initiation activities and in the FP6 and FP7 projects on plant health?” the workshop participants concluded NO in general. However, the following topics were highlighted and the workshop participants recommend these topics to be presented in the coming topic round in April, 2012 and in future rounds if relevant.

Upcoming plant health problems in maize comprising fungal (*Stenocarpella macrocarpa* and *S. maydis*) and nematode (*Heterodera zea*) problems.

Protected ornamentals and vegetables is an important crop sector, threatened by many tropical q-pests and serious pests with the potential to establish in field conditions in some countries. Special attention was paid to thrips- and whitefly-transmitted viruses.

A new Nepovirus in vine was mentioned by the Slovenian partner.

Tuta absoluta in tomato production was mentioned by several participants as an important problem.

The workshop participants all agreed that PRA is an important tool in plant health. However, several participants pointed out problems in the region to build up expertise in PRA and problems in funding participation in PRA activities in topic rounds and in EUPHRESCO mediated projects. The workshop participants forward this to EUPHRESCO for consideration and further initiative.

EUPHRESCO-2 WP5-Workshop Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern European countries.

Sofia, February 28 – 29, 2012

List of participants

No	Name	Institution
1	Olia Karadjova	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
2	Erika Oresek	MAE-PARS
3	Jana Erjavec	MAE
4	Ventsislav Ventsislavov	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
5	Nikolay Petrov	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
6	Maria Stoyanova	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
7	Miroslava Valkova	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
8	Daniela Georgieva	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
9	Vladimir Krumov	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
10	Tzenko Vatchev	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
11	Krste Tashev	SPL-MAFWE, Macedonia
12	Biljana Korunoska	SPL-MAFWE, Macedonia
13	Ganka Baeva	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
14	Stoyka Masheva	Vegetable Crops Institute, Bulgaria
15	Natalia Sherokolava	FGU All-Russian Plant Quarantine Center, Russia
16	Zhenya Ilieva	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
17	Irene Vloutoglou	Benaki Phytopathological Institute, Greece
18	Elena Petrova	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
19	Rositsa Dimitrova	Agricultural Academy, Plant Protection Institute, Bulgaria
20	Georgi Baldjiev	Bulgarian Food Safety Agency, Risk Assessment Centre
21	Steen Lykke Nielsen	Aarhus University, Denmark
22	Boiko Likov	Bulgarian Food Safety Agency, Risk Assessment Centre
23	Violeta Koloma	Bulgarian Food Safety Agency, Phytosanitary Control

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.
Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 0-2

Short analyse of the background material.

The aims of the exploration is to analyse whether a regionalised approach to specific plant health topics is relevant for EUPHRESCO with the Baltic/Nordic-region and highlighting underrepresented plant sectors (except forestry, which is dealt with in another working group)

The Council Directive 2000/29/EC (see Annex 1-2)

The Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community comprises totally 189 pests, which are distributed in the following way:

1. Agricultural crops: total 59 pests
 - a. Potato: 19 pests
 - b. Vegetables (field grown): 15,
 - c. Maize: 8
 - d. Cereals including rice: 4
 - e. Grasses, clover and alfalfa: 4
 - f. Beets: 2
 - g. Sunflower, soybean, tobacco, Brassica (cabbage, rape etc.) and cotton: 4
2. Fruit with 89 pests
3. Viticulture: 7 pests.
4. Glasshouse (ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato)) and field ornamentals: 27.
5. Tomato: 13 pests.
6. Plants for planting: 22 pests.
7. Forestry: 27 pests.

The main crop sectors/crops calculated into % of the total list:

1. Agricultural crops: 31%
2. Potato: 10%
3. Vegetables (field grown): 8%
4. Maize: 4%
5. Citrus: 19%
6. Fruit (other than citrus): 28%
7. Viticulture: 4%
8. Glasshouse (ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato)) and field ornamentals: 14%
9. Tomato: 7%
10. Plants for planting: 12%
11. Forestry: 14%

The EUPHRESCO initiated projects (see Annex 3) split on crop sectors/crops and compared with the distribution of pests in the same crop sectors/crops listed in directive 2000/29/EC, the EPPO's Alert List and the NPPO's phytosanitary threats list (Balkan-Eastern European Region)

Table 1.

Crop sector/crop	No. of projects initiated by EUPHRESCO	No. of projects initiated by EU-PHRESCO in % of sector / crop	The sector / crop in % in directive 2000/29/EC	The sector / crop in % in EPPO's Alert List	The sector/ crop in % in the NPPO's Alert list	Shortlist of the NPPO's Alert list in % (only pests stated by 2 or more partners)
Potato	8	27	10	8	18	26
Maize	1	3	4	11	4	6
Tomato	2	7	7	27	11	14
Vegetables fields	1	3	8	3	6	3
Ornamentals glasshouse	2	7	14	3	10	12
Fruit: Citrus	0	0	19	6	9	6
Fruit: other	5	17	28	8	14	17
Vine	2	7	4	0	4	3
Plants for planting	4	13	12	16	9	9
Forestry	3	10	14	22	(8)*	6
Other broader topics	3	10	0	0	9	0

*Not all NPPOs have reported forestry pests.

From the table it appears that compared to the directive 2000/29/EC list there is an overweight of EUPHRESCO initiated projects in potato and clear shortage of projects in field vegetables, protected (glasshouse) ornamentals and fruit including citrus. Compared to EPPO's Alert List there is an overweight of potato, ornamental and vine projects and a shortage in projects in maize, tomato and forestry. Compared to the NPPO's Alert list there is an overweight of EUPHRESCO initiated projects in potato and a shortage in tomato, field vegetables and especially in citrus and other fruits and also in other broader topics, however compared with the NPPO's, short list (only including pests and topics stated by two or more partners) the number of potato and fruit (other than citrus) projects are adequate, but there is a shortage of EUPHRESCO initiated projects in tomato, ornamentals, citrus and plant for planting and an overweight of projects in vine and other broader topics.

EPPO's Alert List (see Annex 4)

The distribution of pests/broader topics split on crop sectors/crops is shown in Appendix 4 and is calculated into % and included in Table 1 (shown above). From Table 1 it appears that there, compared to the directive 200/29/EC list, is a strong overweight on tomato, maize and forestry on the EPPO Alert List.

The list of the economically most important crops in the Balkan-Eastern European region (see Annex 5 & 6).

The lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary threats (other than forestry) according to NPPO's in countries in the Balkan-Eastern European region (see Annex 7, 8 & 8B)

From Annex 7 with the pests and topics sorted after importance by each NPPO not much weight should be laid on the sorting after importance, because the NPPOs used different criteria for making the lists. Some NPPOs made a list of what they consider as the most important phytosanitary threats present, while other NPPOs made a list of the quarantine pests they carry out official monitoring for and one NPPO made a list of topic proposals for future transnational EUPHRESCO projects. The list of forestry pests is not complete, because this topic has been covered by a separate workshop, so not all NPPOs have included forestry pests in their lists.

The distribution of pests/broader topics split on crop sectors/crops is shown in Appendix 8 and is calculated into % and included in Table 1 above. Further more a short list of Annex 8, only including pests stated by two or more partners (Annex 8B) is included in Table 1 as the last column. The short list gives a more realistic picture of the most important q-pests and topic in the Balkan-Eastern European region, because pests, only of importance for a single country and not for the region in general, have been removed.

The list of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests (Annex 9) will be discussed during the workshop.

The list of interceptions per pest of harmful organisms in EU 2007-09 (Annex 10) shows that five insects constitute a majority of the interceptions.

Examples on different factors influencing why certain q-pests have higher priority than other (Annex 11)

In Annex 11 is given eleven examples illustrating why different q-pests are regarded as having different importance, actuality and priority.

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.
Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 1

Overview of harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Protected crops are glasshouse, screenhouse, plastic coverage etc.

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Classification
1. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Forestry	Conifers	Insect	<i>Acleris</i> spp.	Annex I part A I
5. Ornamentals, cut flowers	Asters	Insect	<i>Amauromyza maculosa</i>	Annex I part A I
6. Agriculture	Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Protected crops	Protected ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Viticulture, fruit	Vine, fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
9. Forestry	Conifers	Insect	<i>Choristoneura</i> spp	Annex I part A I
10. Plants for planting	Rosea family	Insect	<i>Conotrachelus</i> spp	Annex I part A I

11. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica barberi</i>	Annex I part A I
12. Agriculture	Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
13. Agriculture	Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
14. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	Annex I part A I
15. Agriculture	Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I
16. Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	<i>Hirschmaniella</i> spp	Annex I part A I
17. Agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I
18. Fruit, Viticulture	Peach, vine	Nematode	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
19. Forestry	Conifers (vector of pine wood nematode)	Insect	<i>Monochamus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
20. Plant for planting	Palm (vector of palm lethal yellowing phytoplasma)	Insect	<i>Myndus crudus</i>	Annex I part A I
21. Agriculture	Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
22. Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
24. Forestry	Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus</i>	Annex I part A I

25. Forestry	Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus pruinosis</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Forestry, plants for planting	Elm (vector of elm phloem necrosis phytoplasma)	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus luteolus</i>	Annex I part A I
27. Agriculture, protected crops	Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
28. Agriculture	Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
29. Protected crops, agriculture	Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I
30. Protected crops, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
31. Fruit	Fruit	Insect	<i>Tephritidae</i> (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
32. Agriculture, fruit	Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematode	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
33. Agriculture, fruit	Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematode	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
34. Viticulture	Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	Annex I part A I
35. Forestry	Oak	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	Annex I part A I

36. Forestry	Picea	Fungi	<i>Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli</i>	Annex I part A I
37. Forestry	Conifers	Fungi	<i>Cronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
38. Forestry	Conifers	Fungi	<i>Endocronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
39. Forestry	Larix	Fungi	<i>Guignardia laricina</i>	Annex I part A I
40. Fruit	Fruit, Juniperus	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
41. Forestry	Conifera	Fungi	<i>Inonotus weirii</i>	Annex I part A I
42. Forestry	Tsuga	Fungi	<i>Melampsora farlowii</i>	Annex I part A I
43. Fruit	Stonefruit	Fungi	<i>Monilinia fructicola</i>	Annex I part A I
44. Forestry	Larix	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella larici-leptolepsis</i>	Annex I part A I
45. Plants for planting	Populus	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella populorum</i>	Annex I part A I
46. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Phoma andina</i>	Annex I part A I
47. Fruit	Apple	Fungi	<i>Phyllosticta solitaria</i>	Annex I part A I
48. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex I part A I
49. Protected crops, agriculture	Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
50. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	Annex I

				part A I
51. Agriculture	Cereals	Fungi	<i>Tilletia indica</i>	Annex I part A I
52. Agriculture	Cotton	Fungi	<i>Trechispora brinkmannii</i> (Phymato-trichopsis omnivora)	Annex I part A I
53. Forestry	Elms	Virus etc	Elm phlœm necrosis mycoplasm	Annex I part A I
54. Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato viruses non European	Annex I part A I
55. Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato spindle tuber viroid	Annex I part A I
56. Agriculture, protected crops, plants for planting, fruit	Soybean, tobacco, curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
57. Fruit, viticulture	Stonefruit, apple, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
58. Fruit	Fruit and berries	Virus etc	Virus and phytoplasmas infecting <i>Cydonia</i> Mill., <i>Fragaria</i> L., <i>Malus</i> Mill., <i>Prunus</i> L., <i>Pyrus</i> L., <i>Ribes</i> L., <i>Rubus</i> L. or <i>Vitis</i> L.	Annex I part A I
59. Protected crops, agriculture	Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
60. Agriculture	Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
61. Agriculture	Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
62. Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
63. Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i>	Annex I

				part A II
64. Protected crops	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Opogona sacchari</i>	Annex I part A II
65. Agriculture, fruit, forestry, plants for planting	Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
66. Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	Annex I part A II
67. Protected crops	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Rhizoecus hibisci</i>	Annex I part A II
68. Protected crops	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	Annex I part A II
69. Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i>	Annex I part A II
70. Agriculture, protected crops	Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
71. Forestry, plants for planting	Populus, conifera	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
72. Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	Annex I part A II
73. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	Annex I part A II
74. Fruit	Apple	Mycoplasma	Apple proliferation mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
75. Fruit	Stone fruit	Mycoplasma	Apricot chlorotic leafroll mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
76. Fruit	Pear	Mycoplasma	Pear decline mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
77. Protected crops	Ornamental	Insect	<i>Aculops fuchsiae</i>	Annex II

				part A I
78. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Aleurocanthus</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
79. Fruit	Strawberry	Insect	<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i> and <i>A. signatus</i>	Annex II part A I
80. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Aonidiella citrina</i>	Annex II part A I
81. Agriculture	Rice	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A I
82. Plants for planting	Juniper	Insect	<i>Aschistonyx eppo</i>	Annex II part A I
83. Forestry	Conifera	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
84. Fruit	Pear	Insect	<i>Carposina niponensis</i>	Annex II part A I
85. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	Annex II part A I
86. Fruit	Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	Annex II part A I
87. Fruit, plants for planting	Pome, stonefruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I
88. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	Annex II part A I
89. Fruit	Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Grapholita inopinata</i>	Annex II part A I
90. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Hishomonus phycitis</i>	Annex II part A I
91. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Leucaspis japonica</i>	Annex II

				part A I
92. Agriculture	Brassicas, clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I
93. Viticulture	Vine	Insect	<i>Margarodes</i> spp	Annex II part A I
94. Fruit	Pear	Insect	<i>Numonia pyrivorella</i>	Annex II part A I
95. Plants for planting	Juniper	Insect	<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	Annex II part A I
96. Forestry	Conifera	Insect	<i>Pissodes</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
97. Citrus fruit, protected crops	Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
98. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Saissetia nigra</i>	Annex II part A I
99. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Scirtothrips</i> 3 species	Annex II part A I
100. Forestry	Conifera	Insect	<i>Scolytidae</i> spp	Annex II part A I
101. Fruit	Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Tachypterellus quadrigibbus</i>	Annex II part A I
102. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>	Annex II part A I
103. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Trioza erytraeae</i>	Annex II part A I
104. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Unaspis citri</i>	Annex II part A I
105. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus greening bacterium	Annex II part A I

106.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus variegated chlorosis	Annex II part A I
107.	Agriculture	Maize	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia stewartii</i>	Annex II part A I
108.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i>	Annex II part A I
109.	Agriculture	Rice	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>Oryzae</i> & <i>orizicola</i>	Annex II part A I
110.	Fruit	Pome	Fungi	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Annex II part A I
111.	Fruit, plants for planting	Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I
112.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Apiosporina morbosa</i>	Annex II part A I
113.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Atropellis</i>	Annex II part A I
114.	Forestry, plants for planting	Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
115.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Cercoseptoria pini-densiflorae</i>	Annex II part A I
116.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Cercospora angolensis</i>	Annex II part A I
117.	Protected crops	Camelia	Fungi	<i>Ciborinia camelliae</i>	Annex II part A I
118.	Fruit	Blueberry	Fungi	<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	Annex II part A I
119.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Elsinoe</i> spp	Annex II

				part A I	
120.	Fruit, plants for planting	Date palm	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. albedines</i>	Annex II part A I
121.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	Annex II part A I
122.	Fruit	Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
123.	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	Annex II part A I
124.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia acicola</i>	Annex II part A I
125.	Fruit	Pear	Fungi	<i>Venturia nashicola</i>	Annex II part A I
126.	Agriculture	Beet	Virus etc.	Beet curly top virus	Annex II part A I
127.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Black raspberry latent virus	Annex II part A I
128.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Blight and blight-like	Annex II part A I
129.	Fruit	Coconut	Virus etc.	Cadang-cadang viroid	Annex II part A I
130.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Cherry leaf roll virus	Annex II part A I
131.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus mosaic virus	Annex II part A I
132.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A I
133.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Leprosis	Annex II

				part A I	
134.	Fruit	Stonefruit	Virus etc.	Little cherry pathogen	Annex II part A I
135.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Naturally spreading psorosis	Annex II part A I
136.	Fruit	Coconut	Virus etc.	Palm lethal yellowing mycoplasma	Annex II part A I
137.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Prunus necrotic ringspot virus	Annex II part A I
138.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Satsuma dwarf virus	Annex II part A I
139.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Tatter leaf virus	Annex II part A I
140.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Witches' broom	Annex II part A I
141.	Fruit	Strawberry	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A II
142.	Viticulture	Vine	Insect	<i>Daktulosphaira vitifoliae</i>	Annex II part A II
143.	Field, Protected crops	Ornamental bulbs	Insect	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>	Annex II part A II
144.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer haematoceps</i>	Annex II part A II
145.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer tenellus</i>	Annex II part A II
146.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus orientalis</i>	Annex II part A II

147.	Protected crops	Ornamental cut flowers	Insect	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Annex II part A II
148.	Protected crops	Pot plants	Insect	<i>Radopholus similis</i>	Annex II part A II
149.	Protected crops, field	Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>	Annex II part A II
150.	Protected crops, field	Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Lirimyza trifolii</i>	Annex II part A II
151.	Agriculture	Alfalfa	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> spp. <i>insidiosus</i>	Annex II part A II
152.	Protected crops, field	Tomato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>michiganensis</i>	Annex II part A II
153.	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
154.	Protected crops	Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia chrysanthemi</i> pv. <i>Dianthicola</i> (<i>Pectobacterium dianthicola</i>)	Annex II part A II
155.	Protected crops	Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas caryophylli</i>	Annex II part A II
156.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>persicae</i>	Annex II part A II
157.	Vegetables	Beans	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>phaseoli</i>	Annex II part A II
158.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>	Annex II part A II
159.	Protected	Tomato, chili	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesica-</i>	Annex II

	crops, field			<i>toria</i>	part A II
160.	Fruit	Strawberry	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
161.	Viticulture	Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylophilus ampelinus</i>	Annex II part A II
162.	Plants for planting	Platanus	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i> f. sp. <i>platani</i>	Annex II part A II
163.	Plant for planting, fruit	Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
164.	Protected crops, field	Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Didymella ligulicola</i>	Annex II part A II
165.	Protected crops	Cut flowers (carnation)	Fungi	<i>Phialophora cinerescens</i>	Annex II part A II
166.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Phoma tracheiphila</i>	Annex II part A II
167.	Fruit	Strawberry	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
168.	Plants for planting	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex II part A II
169.	Agriculture	Sunflower	Fungi	<i>Plasmopara halstedii</i>	Annex II part A II
170.	Protected crops, field	Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>	Annex II part A II
171.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia pini</i>	Annex II part A II

172.	Vegetable	Hop	Fungi	<i>Verticillium albo-atrum</i>	Annex II part A II
173.	Vegetable	Hop	Fungi	<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>	Annex II part A II
174.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Arabis mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
175.	Agriculture	Beet	Virus etc.	Beet leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II
176.	Protected crops	Chrysanthemum	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid	Annex II part A II
177.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A II
178.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus vein enation woody gall	Annex II part A II
179.	Viticulture	Vine	Phyto- plasma	Grapevine flavescence dorée MLO	Annex II part A II
180.	Protected crops, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
181.	Fruit	Stonefruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus	Annex II part A II
182.	Agriculture	Potato	Phyto- plasma	Potato stolbur mycoplasm	Annex II part A II
183.	Fruit	Strawberry, Rubus	Virus etc.	Raspberry ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
184.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	<i>Spiroplasma citri</i>	Annex II part A II
185.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry crinkle virus	Annex II part A II

186.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry latent ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
187.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry mild yellow edge virus	Annex II part A II
188.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Tomato black ring virus	Annex II part A II
189.	Protected crops, vegetables, agriculture	Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
190.	Protected crops, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.

Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 2

Overview of harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Protected is glasshouse, screenhouse, plastic coverage etc.

Sorted after the crop sector and split on crops.

Agriculture

Potato

1. Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
4. Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
6. Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
7. Potato	Fungi	<i>Phoma andina</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Potato	Fungi	<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	Annex I part A I
9. Potato	Virus etc	Potato viruses non European	Annex I part A I
10. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
11. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
12. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
13. Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i>	Annex I part A II
15. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
16. Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	Annex I part A II
17. Potato	Fungi	<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	Annex II part A I
18. Potato	Phytoplasma	Potato stolbur mycoplasma	Annex II part A II
19. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II

Vegetables (field grown)

20. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
21. Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
22. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I
24. Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I
25. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
27. Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I

28. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
29. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
30. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
31. Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
32. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
33. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
34. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
35. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
Maize			
36. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
37. Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica barberi</i>	Annex I part A I
38. Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
39. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
40. Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	Annex I part A I
41. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I
42. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
43. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
Cereals including rice			
44. Rice	Nematod	<i>Hirschmaniella</i> spp	Annex I part A I
45. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
46. Cereals	Fungi	<i>Tilletia indica</i>	Annex I part A I
47. Rice	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A I
Grasses, clover and alfalfa			
48. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
49. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
50. Brassicas, clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I
51. Alfalfa	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> spp. <i>insidiosus</i>	Annex II part A II
Beets			
52. Beet	Virus etc.	Beet curly top virus	Annex II part A I
53. Beet	Virus etc.	Beet leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II
Sunflower, soybean, Tobacco, Brassica, Cotton			
54. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I

tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus			
55. Tomato, tobacco , strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
56. Cotton	Fungi	<i>Trechispora brinkmannii</i> (Phymatotri-chopsis omnivora)	Annex I part A I
57. Soybean, tobacco , curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
58. Brassicas , clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I
59. Sunflower	Fungi	<i>Plasmopara halstedii</i>	Annex II part A II
Fruit			
1. Peach, Vine	Nematod	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Fruit	Insect	<i>Tephritidae</i> (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
3. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
4. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Fruit, Juniperus	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Soybean, tobacco, curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
7. Stonefruit, pome, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
8. Fruit and berries	Virus etc	Virus and phytoplasmas infecting <i>Cydonia</i> Mill., <i>Fragaria</i> L., <i>Malus</i> Mill., <i>Prunus</i> L., <i>Pyrus</i> L., <i>Ribes</i> L., <i>Rubus</i> L. og <i>Vitis</i> L.,	Annex I part A I
9. Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
10. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
11. Blueberry	Fungi	<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	Annex II part A I
12. Coconut	Virus etc.	Cadang-cadang viroid	Annex II part A I
13. Coconut	Virus etc.	Palm lethal yellowing mycoplasm	Annex II part A I
14. Date palm	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>albedines</i>	Annex II part A I
15. Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I

16. Rubus	Virus etc.	Black raspberry latent virus	Annex II part A I
17. Rubus	Virus etc.	Cherry leaf roll virus	Annex II part A I
18. Rubus	Virus etc.	Prunus necrotic ringspot virus	Annex II part A I
19. Pear	Mycoplasma	Pear decline mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
20. Pear	Insect	<i>Carposina niponensis</i>	Annex II part A I
21. Pear	Insect	<i>Numonia pyrivorella</i>	Annex II part A I
22. Pome	Fungi	<i>Phyllosticta solitaria</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Pome	Mycoplasma	Apple proliferation mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
24. Pome	Fungi	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Annex II part A I
25. Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
26. Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
27. Pome, stone fruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I
28. Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Grapholita inopinata</i>	Annex II part A I
29. Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Tachypterellus quadrigibbus</i>	Annex II part A I
30. Vine, stone fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
31. Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Monilinia fructicola</i>	Annex I part A I
32. Stone fruit	Mycoplasma	Apricot chlorotic leafroll mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
33. Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Apiosporina morbosa</i>	Annex II part A I
34. Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Little cherry pathogen	Annex II part A I
35. Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>persicae</i>	Annex II part A II
36. Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>	Annex II part A II
37. Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus	Annex II part A II
38. Strawberry	Insect	<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i> and <i>A. signatus</i>	Annex II part A I
39. Strawberry	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A II
40. Strawberry	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
41. Strawberry	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
42. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Arabis mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
43. Strawberry, Rubus	Virus etc.	Raspberry ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
44. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry crinkle virus	Annex II part A II
45. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry latent ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
46. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry mild yellow edge virus	Annex II part A II
47. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Tomato black ring virus	Annex II part A II
48. Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	Annex II part A I
49. Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
50. Citrus	Insect	<i>Aonidiella citrina</i>	Annex II part A I
51. Citrus	Insect	<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	Annex II part A I
52. Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	Annex II part A I
53. Citrus	Insect	<i>Hishomonus phycitis</i>	Annex II part A I
54. Citrus	Insect	<i>Leucaspis japonica</i>	Annex II part A I
55. Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
56. Citrus	Insect	<i>Saissetia nigra</i>	Annex II part A I
57. Citrus	Insect	<i>Scirtothrips</i> 3 species	Annex II part A I
58. Citrus	Insect	<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>	Annex II part A I
59. Citrus	Insect	<i>Trioza erytreae</i>	Annex II part A I
60. Citrus	Insect	<i>Unaspis citri</i>	Annex II part A I

61. Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus greening bacterium	Annex II part A I
62. Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus variegated chlorosis	Annex II part A I
63. Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i>	Annex II part A I
64. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Cercospora angolensis</i>	Annex II part A I
65. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Elsinoe</i> spp	Annex II part A I
66. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	Annex II part A I
67. Citrus	Virus etc.	Blight and blight-like	Annex II part A I
68. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus mosaic virus	Annex II part A I
69. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A I
70. Citrus	Virus etc.	Leprosis	Annex II part A I
71. Citrus	Virus etc.	Naturally spreading psorosis	Annex II part A I
72. Citrus	Virus etc.	Satsuma dwarf virus	Annex II part A I
73. Citrus	Virus etc.	Tatter leaf virus	Annex II part A I
74. Citrus	Virus etc.	Witches' broom	Annex II part A I
75. Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer haematoceps</i>	Annex II part A II
76. Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer tenellus</i>	Annex II part A II
77. Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus orientalis</i>	Annex II part A II
78. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Phoma tracheiphila</i>	Annex II part A II
79. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A II
80. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus vein enation woody gall	Annex II part A II
81. Citrus	Virus etc.	<i>Spiroplasma citri</i>	Annex II part A II
Viticulture			
1. Vine, fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
2. Peach, vine	Nematod	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Stonefruit, apple, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
5. Vine	Insect	<i>Margarodes</i> spp	Annex II part A I
6. Vine	Insect	<i>Daktulosphaira vitifoliae</i>	Annex II part A II
7. Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylophilus ampelinus</i>	Annex II part A II
Protected ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato) and field ornamentals			
1. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Opogona sacchari</i>	Annex I part A II
2. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Rhizoecus hibisci</i>	Annex I part A II
3. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	Annex I part A II
4. Ornamental	Insect	<i>Aculops fuchsiae</i>	Annex II part A I
5. Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
6. Protected ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Soybean, tobacco, cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
9. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I

10. Protected ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
11. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
12. Soybean, tobacco, cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
13. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
14. Ornamental bulbs	Insect	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>	Annex II part A II
15. Ornamental cut flowers	Insect	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Annex II part A II
16. Pot plants	Insect	<i>Radopholus similis</i>	Annex II part A II
17. Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>	Annex II part A II
18. Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Liriomyza trifolii</i>	Annex II part A II
19. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus	Annex II part A II
20. Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia chrysanthemi</i> pv. <i>Dianthicola</i> (<i>Pectobacterium dianthicola</i>)	Annex II part A II
21. Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas caryophylli</i>	Annex II part A II
22. Cut flowers (carnation)	Fungi	<i>Phialophora cinerescens</i>	Annex II part A II
23. Asters	Insect	<i>Amauromyza maculosa</i>	Annex I part A I
24. Camelia	Fungi	<i>Ciborinia camelliae</i>	Annex II part A I
25. Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Didymella ligulicola</i>	Annex II part A II
26. Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>	Annex II part A II
27. Chrysanthemum	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid	Annex II part A II
Tomato			
1. Protected ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
6. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
9. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
10. Tomato, chili	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesicatoria</i>	Annex II part A II
11. Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
12. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato,	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II

etc.			
13. Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II
Plants for planting			
1. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Rosea family	Insect	<i>Conotrachelus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
5. Fruit, Juniper	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Populus	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella populorum</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Soybean, tobacco, cucurbitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
9. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
10. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
11. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
12. Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	Annex I part A II
13. Populus, conifera	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Juniper	Insect	<i>Aschistonyx eppo</i>	Annex II part A I
15. Pome, stonefruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I
16. Juniper	Insect	<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	Annex II part A I
17. Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I
18. Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
19. Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
20. Platanus	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i> f. sp. <i>platani</i>	Annex II part A II
21. Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
22. Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex II part A II
Forestry			
1. Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
2. Conifers	Insect	<i>Acleris</i> spp.	Annex I part A I
3. Conifers	Insect	<i>Choristoneura</i> spp	Annex I part A I
4. Conifers (vector of pine wood nematode)	Insect	<i>Monochamus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
5. Conifers	Fungi	<i>Cronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Conifers	Fungi	<i>Endocronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
7. Conifera	Fungi	<i>Inonotus weirii</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Conifera	Insect	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
9. Conifera	Insect	<i>Pissodes</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
10. Conifera	Insect	<i>Scolytidae</i> spp	Annex II part A I
11. Elms	Virus etc	Elm phloem necrosis mycoplasma	Annex I part A I
12. Elm (vector of elm phlo-)	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus luteolus</i>	Annex I part A I

			em necrosis phytoplasma)
13. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Larch	Fungi	<i>Guignardia laricina</i>	Annex I part A I
15. Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus minutissimus</i>	Annex I part A I
16. Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus pruinosis</i>	Annex I part A I
17. Oak	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	Annex I part A I
18. Spruce	Fungi	<i>Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli</i>	Annex I part A I
19. Pine	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	Annex I part A II
20. Pine	Fungi	<i>Atropellis</i>	Annex II part A I
21. Pine	Fungi	<i>Cercoseptoria pini-densiflorae</i>	Annex II part A I
22. Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia acicola</i>	Annex II part A I
23. Poplar, conifer	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
24. Tsuga	Fungi	<i>Melampsora farlowii</i>	Annex I part A I
25. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
27. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.
Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 3

Topic calls from EUPHRESCO-1 and EUPHRESCO-2 (2011) split on crops

Call title	Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
Potato brown rot and potato ring rot. Validation of methods that can be approved for use via control directives.	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> , <i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>
Potato cyst nematodes. Ringtesting methods for identification and resistance testing.	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	Potato cyst nematodes
<i>Dickeya</i> species in potato and management strategies.	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Dickeya dianthicola</i> , <i>D. solani</i>
Use of novel molecular methods to understand population diversity and its implication on disease management through use of resistant potato varieties	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	Potato cyst nematodes
Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for detection and identification of <i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i> in support of integrated plant protection strategies	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i>
Diagnostic methods for <i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i> , especially for pathotype identification	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>
Epidemiology and diagnosis of potato phytoplasmas and Candidatus <i>Liberibacter solanacearum</i> and their contribution to risk management	Agriculture	Potato	Mycoplasma	Potato phytoplasmas
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals, tomato, potato Various agricultural	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids

<i>Erwinia stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i> , maize bacterial blight. Validation and ring testing of diagnostic methods.	Agriculture	crops Maize	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i>
Validation of diagnostic methods for the detection and identification of whitefly transmitted viruses of regulatory or quarantine concern to EU.	Field crops, glasshouse	Ornamentals, vegetables	Viruses	Bean golden mosaic, Lettuce infectious yellows, Pepper mild tigré, Euphorbia mosaic a.o. viruses
Assessment of the risk posed by ornamentals and tomato seeds infected by Pospiviroids to tomato crops and evaluation of Pospiviroid detection protocols for seed testing in tomato	Glasshouse, field crop	Tomato Tomato	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals, tomato, potato Ornamentals	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals, tomato, potato	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids
Validation of diagnostic methods for the detection and identification of whitefly transmitted viruses of regulatory or quarantine concern to EU.	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals, vegetables	Viruses	Bean golden mosaic, Lettuce infectious yellows, Pepper mild tigré, Euphorbia mosaic a.o. viruses
Interlaboratory comparison and validation of detection methods for phytoplasmas of phytosanitary concern in European orchards.	Fruit	Fruit Fruit trees	Phytoplasma	Phytoplasmas
Evaluation of factors determining distribution, impact, detection and characterization of apple proliferation and other fruit tree phytoplasmoses in the European Community	Fruit	Fruit trees	Mycoplasmas	Apple proliferation and other fruit tree phytoplasmoses
Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for the detection of fire blight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>).	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, ornamental	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>

Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight	Fruit and plants for planting	trees Fruit trees, hawthorn etc	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
Damage potential of <i>Drosophila suzukii</i> and development of phytosanitary measures	Fruit	Fruit trees, grapevine	Insect	<i>Drosophila suzukii</i>
Evaluation of the risk of spread of <i>Scaphoideus titanus</i> , the vector of grapevine flavescence dorée, with commercial grapevine propagation material.	Viticulture	Vine Vine	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus titanus</i>
Epidemiological studies on reservoir hosts and potential vectors of Grapevine flavescence dorée (GFD) and validation of different diagnostic procedures for GFD	Viticulture	Vine	Mycoplasma	Grapevine flavescence dorée
Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for the detection of fire blight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>).	Fruit, plants for planting	Plants for planting Fruit trees, ornamental trees	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight	Fruit and plants for planting	Fruit trees, hawthorn etc	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
Risk management for the EC listed <i>Anoplophora</i> species, <i>A. chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>
Current and emerging <i>Phytophthora</i> : research supporting risk assessment and risk management	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Fungi	<i>P. ramorum</i> , <i>kernoviae</i> , <i>lateralis</i>
Phytosanitary Efficacy of Kiln Drying.	Forestry	Forestry Various trees	Various	Various
Risk management for the EC listed <i>Anoplophora</i> species, <i>A. chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>
Current and emerging <i>Phytophthora</i> : research supporting risk assessment and risk management	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Fungi	<i>P. ramorum</i> , <i>kernoviae</i> , <i>lateralis</i>
Strategies for <i>Ambrosia</i> control.	Agriculture	Other topics Various	Weed plant	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>

Whole genomic amplification methods	All	All	Various	Various
Management of invasive alien aquatic/riparian weeds.	None	None	Plant	Various

Annex 4

Overview of harmful organisms listed in EPPO's Alert List (last updated February 2012).

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
Tomato	Tomato		
1. Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Insect	<i>Keiferia lycopersicella</i>
2. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<i>Pepino mosaic virus</i>
3. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<i>Tomato apical stunt pospiviroid</i>
4. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato torrado virus
5. Potato, agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	<i>Leucinodes orbonalis</i>
6. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato, chilli, sweet pepper	Bacteria	' <i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i> '
Potato	Potato		
7. Potato, agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	<i>Leucinodes orbonalis</i>
8. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato, chilli, sweet pepper	Bacteria	' <i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i> '
9. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>
Maize	Maize		
10. Agriculture	Maize	Bacteria	<i>Spiroplasma kunkelii</i>
11. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>
12. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>
13. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>
14. Agriculture	Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>) and other cereals (<i>Triticum</i> , <i>Hordeum</i>)	Nematode	<i>Hederodera zeae</i>
15. Agriculture	Maize (<i>Zea mays</i>)	Nematode	<i>Punctodera chalconensis</i>
Other agriculture	Other agriculture		

crops	crops		
16. Agriculture	Sunflower	Insect	<i>Strauzia longipennis</i>
17. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>
18. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>
19. Agriculture, glasshouse	Lettuce	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>lactucae</i>
Glasshouse	Glasshouse		
20. Glasshouse	Ornamental pot plant	Fungi	<i>Melampsora euphorbiae</i>
Fruit	Fruit		
21. Citrus fruit, agriculture	Citrus, melon	Bacteria	<i>Acidovorax citrulli</i>
22. Fruit	Ficus, morus	Insect	<i>Psacotheta hilaris</i>
23. Fruit	Kiwi	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>actinidiae</i>
24. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>
25. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i>
Plants for planting	Plants for planting		
26. Plants for planting	Horse chestnut	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>aesculi</i>
27. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>
28. Forestry, plants for planting	Beech, rhododendron	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora kernoviae</i>
29. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum, oak	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>
30. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>
31. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i>
Forestry	Forestry		

32. Forestry	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	Insect	<i>Chrysophtharta bimaculata</i>
33. Forestry	Oak species	Insect	<i>Enaphalodes rufulus</i>
34. Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora pinifolia</i>
35. Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i>
36. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>
37. Forestry, plants for planting	Beech, rhododendron	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora kernoviae</i>
38. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum, oak	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>
39. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oeomona hirta</i>
40. Forestry	<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	Insect	<i>Aproceros leucopoda</i>
41. Forestry	<i>Abies</i> sp.	Insect	<i>Polygraphus proximus</i>

Annex 5

Lists of most important crops (other than forestry) in countries in the Balkan and Eastern European Region. The list comprises input from Balkan and Eastern European countries.

Type of the crop	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Bulgaria	Croatia*	Cyprus*	Czech Republic*	Greece	Hungary*	Macedonia, F.Y.R.	Romania*	Russia	Serbia*	Slovenia	Turkey	Ukraine
Grain and small grain	Maize Wheat Barley Oats Triticale Rye	Wheat Maize Barley Coriander Oats Rye Triticale Rice, paddy Millet Sorghum	Maize Wheat Barley Oats Mixed grain Rye Sorghum Buckwheat Millet	Barley Wheat Oats	Wheat Barley Maize Oats Triticale Rye Cereals, nes Mixed grain Millet Anise, badian, fennel Canary seed	Wheat Maize Barley Oats Rye Cereals, nes Millet Anise, badian, fennel Sorghum Mixed grain Canary seed	Maize Wheat Barley Triticale Rye Oats Millet Sorghum Canary seed Cereals, nes	Wheat Barley Maize Rye Oats Sorghum Millet Anise, badian, fennel Mixed grain	Maize Wheat Barley Oats Triticale Rice, paddy Anise, badian, fennel Sorghum Millet Cereals, nes	Wheat Barley Oats Maize Buckwheat Millet Rice, paddy Sorghum Anise, badian, fennel, corian.	Maize Wheat Barley Oats Triticale Mixed grain Buckwheat Rye Cereals, nes Millet	Maize Wheat Barley Oats Triticale Mixed grain Buckwheat Rye Cereals, nes Millet	Wheat Barley Maize Rye Oats Triticale Rice, paddy Cereals, nes Millet Mixed grain	Wheat Barley Maize Oats Triticale Rye Cereals, nes Millet Anise, badian, fennel, corian.
Oil bearing crops	Soybeans Rapeseed Sunflower seed Olives	Sunflower seed Rapeseed Mustard seed Cotton seed Soyabean	Soyabean Sunflower seed Rapeseed Olives Poppy seed	Olives Sesame seed	Rapeseed Poppy seed Sunflower seed Mustard seed Soyabean Linseed	Olives Cotton seed Sunflower seed Rapeseed Soyabean Sesame seed Melonseed	Sunflower seed Rapeseed Soyabean Mustard seed Poppy seed Hempseed Linseed Safflower seed	Olives Sunflower seed Rapeseed Soyabean Mustard seed Poppy seed Hempseed Linseed	Sunflower seed Rapeseed Soyabean Mustard seed Poppy seed Hempseed Linseed Safflower seed	Sunflower seed Soyabean Rapeseed Poppy seed	Sunflower seed Soyabean Rapeseed Poppy seed		Olives Sunflower seed Cotton seed Poppy seed Sesame seed Rapeseed Soyabean Safflower seed	Sunflower seed Rapeseed Mustard seed Linseed Hempseed
Root and tuber crops	Potato	Potato	Potato Sugar beet	Potato	Potato	Potato Sugar beet	Potato Sugar beet	Potato Sugar beet	Potato Sugar beet	Potato Sugar beet	Potato Sugar beet	Potato	Potato Sugar beet	Potato Sugar beet
Vegetables	Cabbages and other brassicas Onions, dry Chillies and peppers, green Tomatoes Cucumbers and gherkins Watermelons Carrots and turnips Garlic Beans, green Maize, green	Tomatoes Cucumbers and gherkins Chillies and peppers, green Cabbages and other brassicas Onions, dry Watermelons Asparagus Peas, green Vegetables fresh nes Garlic Beans, green Onions (inc. shallots), green Carrots and turnips Eggplants (aubergines) Pumpkins, squash and gourds Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Spinach	Chillies and peppers, green Cabbages and other brassicas Tomatoes Onions, dry Watermelons Beans, green Peas, green Vegetables fresh nes Artichokes Pumpkins, squash and gourds Spinach Asparagus Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Peas, green Carrots and turnips Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Spinach	Vegetables fresh nes Watermelons Tomatoes Leguminous vegetables Cucumbers and gherkins Onions, dry Carrots and turnips Cauliflowers and broccoli Garlic Other melons (inc. cantaloupes) Spinach Asparagus Cauliflowers and broccoli Cabbages and other brassicas Peas, green Carrots and turnips Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Spinach Eggplants (aubergines) Garlic Onions (inc. shallots), green Leeks, other alliaaceous veg	Onions, dry Cucumbers and gherkins Peas, green Cabbages and other brassicas Tomatoes Onions, dry Carrots and turnips Cauliflowers and broccoli Garlic Chillies and peppers, green Pumpkins, squash and gourds Spinach Lettuce and chicory Asparagus Cauliflowers and broccoli Vegetables fresh nes Eggplants (aubergines) Cucumbers and gherkins Onions (inc. shallots), green Leeks, other alliaaceous veg Carrots and turnips Leguminous vegetables Onions (inc. shallots), green Leeks, other alliaaceous veg	Tomatoes Watermelons Cabbages and other brassicas Other melons (inc. cantaloupes) Onions, dry Chillies and peppers, green Pumpkins, squash and gourds Tomatoes Vegetables fresh nes Cauliflowers and broccoli Spinach Asparagus Cauliflowers and broccoli Cucumbers and gherkins Other melons (inc. cantaloupes) Other melons (inc. cantaloupes) Vegetables fresh nes Cauliflowers and broccoli Eggplants (aubergines) Lettuce and chicory Maize, green Leeks, other alliaaceous veg Lettuce and chicory Spinach Eggplants (aubergines)	Maize, green Beans, green Chillies and peppers, green Cabbages and other brassicas Watermelons Tomatoes Onions, dry Carrots and turnips Cucumbers and gherkins Peas, green Garlic Beans, green Vegetables fresh nes Cauliflowers and broccoli Asparagus Carrots and turnips Peas, green Leguminous vegetables Eggplants (aubergines) Pumpkins, squash and gourds Vegetables fresh nes Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Spinach Artichokes	Beans, green Chillies and peppers, green Cabbages and other brassicas Watermelons Onions, dry Carrots and turnips Cucumbers and gherkins Peas, green Garlic Beans, green Vegetables fresh nes Eggplants (aubergines) Pumpkins, squash and gourds Vegetables fresh nes Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Maize, green Leeks, other alliaaceous veg Artichokes	Tomatoes Cabbages and other brassicas Watermelons Onions, dry Vegetables fresh nes Beans, green Onions, dry Carrots and turnips Cucumbers and gherkins Tomatoes Carrots and turnips Cucumbers and gherkins Pumpkins, squash and gourds Cucumbers and gherkins Tomatoes Cauliflowers and broccoli Peas, green Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Spinach Eggplants (aubergines)	Cabbages and other brassicas Lettuce and chicory Vegetables fresh nes Beans, green Onions, dry French beans Tomatoes Carrots and turnips Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Cauliflowers and broccoli Peas, green Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Spinach Leeks, other alliaaceous veg	White cabbage Tomatoes Cucumbers Sweet peppers Onion French beans Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Cauliflowers and broccoli Peas, green Cauliflowers and broccoli Lettuce and chicory Spinach Leeks, other alliaaceous veg	Tomatoes Watermelons Other melons (inc. cantaloupes) Chillies and peppers, green Beans, green Onions, dry Cucumbers and gherkins Cucumbers and gherkins Pumpkins, squash and gourds Eggplants (aubergines) Garlic Carrots and turnips Other melons (inc. cantaloupes) Spinach Chillies and peppers, green Onions (inc. shallots), green Pumpkins, squash and gourds Eggplants (aubergines) Lettuce and chicory Onions (inc. shallots), green Cauliflowers and broccoli Peas, green Lettuce and chicory Garlic Maize, green Beans, green String beans Cauliflowers and broccoli Okra Leguminous vegetables, nes Artichokes		

Annex 6a

The lists of Appendix 5 sorted after how many countries have included the specific crop in their list.

	Bosnia	Bulgaria	Croatia	Cyprus	Czech Republic	Greece	Hungary	Romania	Russian Federation	Serbia	Slovenia	F.Y.R. Macedonia	Turkey	Ukraine	
Vegetable crops															
Artichokes				x		x		x					x		4
Asparagus		x			x	x	x					x			5
Beans, green	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	13
Cabbages and other brassicas	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Carrots and turnips	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Cauliflowers and broccoli		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	12
Chillies and peppers, green	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	13
Cucumbers and gherkins	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Eggplants (aubergines)		x		x		x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	10
Garlic	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Leeks, other alliaceous veg			x	x		x	x	x			x	x	x		8
Leguminous vegetables, nes		x		x	x	x			x				x		6
Lettuce and chicory		x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x	11
Maize, green	x						x			x		x		x	5
Okra				x									x		2
Onions (inc. shallots), green		x		x		x	x					x	x	x	7
Onions, dry	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Other melons (inc.cantaloupes)				x		x	x	x				x	x	x	7
Peas, green		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	13
Pumpkins, squash and gourds		x		x		x	x	x	x				x	x	8
Spinach		x		x	x	x	x	x			x		x		8
String beans													x		1
Tomatoes	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Watermelons	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	12
Cereals andsmall grain field crops															
Anise, badian, fennel, corian.		x				x	x	x	x	x			x	x	9
Barley	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Buckw heat			x		x		x		x		x			x	6
Canary seed					x		x								2
Cereals, nes		x			x	x	x	x	x		x			x	8
Maize	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	13

Millet		x	x		x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	11
Mixed grain			x		x	x				x	x	x	x		7
Oats	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Rice, paddy		x				x	x	x	x			x	x	x	8
Rye	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	13
Sorghum		x	x				x	x	x	x		x		x	8
Triticale	x	x			x		x	x	x	x	x		x		9
Wheat	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Oil bearing crops															
Castor oil seed									x						1
Groundnuts, with shell		x		x		x							x		4
Hempseed							x	x	x					x	4
Linseed		x			x		x	x	x					x	6
Melonseed						x									1
Mustard seed		x			x		x	x	x					x	6
Oilseeds, Nes		x			x		x		x					x	5
Olives	x		x	x		x						x	x		6
Poppy seed			x		x		x	x		x		x	x		7
Rapeseed	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	12
Safflower seed							x		x					x	3
Seed cotton		x				x								x	3
Sesame seed				x		x						x	x		4
Soybeans	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	12
Sunflower seed	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	12
Root and tuber crops															
Potato	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Sugar beet		x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	10

Beans and lentils - dry															
Beans - dry	x	x	x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	12
Lentils - dry		x						x	x	x	x	x	x		7
Fruit, berries and nuts															
Apple	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Apricots	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Avocados	x			x		x							x		4
Bananas				x		x							x		3
Berries Nes	x	x	x		x	x		x	x	x	x		x	x	11
Blueberries								x	x					x	3
Carobs				x	x		x						x	x	5
Cherries	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Cranberries													x		3
Currants					x		x	x	x				x		6
Dates														x	1
Figs	x			x	x		x					x	x	x	7
Gooseberries					x		x			x					4
Grapefruit (inc. pomelos)				x		x								x	3
Grapes	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Kiw i fruit				x		x						x		x	5
Lemons and limes				x		x								x	4
Oranges	x			x		x			x					x	7
Peaches and nectarines	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Pears	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Persimmons													x		2
Plums and sloes	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Pome fruit, nes														x	2

Quinces	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	12
Raspberries	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	x		x		x	10
Sour cherries	x	x	x		x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	12
Straw berries	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Tangerines, mandarins, clem.	x	x	x	x		x								x	5
Viticulture	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	14
Protected cultivation	?	x	?	?	?	x	?	?	?	?	?	x	x	?	
Essential-oil crops															
Rose		x												x	2
Mint		x													1
Lavender		x													1
Technical crops															
Hops		x									x				2
Tobacco		x				x						x	x		4

Annex 6b

Power point presentation of Annex 5 & 6.

Euphresco
Phytosanitary ERA-NET

A list of the economical most important crops in the Balkan/Eastern Europe region

28-29 February 2012, Sofia

Agricultural Academy Plant Protection Institute

Euphresco
Phytosanitary ERA-NET

Data sources:

- ❑ NPPO's
- ❑ FAOSTAT – 5 year period (2006-2010) – area, production and value
- ❑ Eurostat

All data are represented as relative part to the total agricultural or/arable area of each country

Euphresco
Phytosanitary ERA-NET

Economically important cereal and small grain crops

	1st place	2nd place	3rd place
Wheat	8	6	
Maize	5	1	4
Barley	1	5	7

Oats			
Rye			
Millet			
Buckwheat	5 countries		
Millet			
Sorghum			
Rice, paddy	8 countries - important for 4 countries		
Canary seed	2 countries - Hungary and Czech Republic - there are only 6 producing countries		
Anise, badian, fennel, coriander	9 countries - 6 of them are in the first 20 as quantity and price in the world		

Economically important cereal and small grain crops

No countries	Crops
13	Barley
13	Oats
13	Wheat
12	Maize
12	Rye
10	Millet
9	Anise, badian, fennel, coriander
8	Triticale
7	Rice, paddy
7	Sorghum
6	Mixed grain
5	Buckwheat
2	Canary seed

Vegetables

Crop	No countries	Crop	No countries
Tomatoes	13	Pumpkins, squash and gourds	8
Watermelons	11	Lettuce and chicory	11
Cabbages and other brassicas	13	Cauliflowers and broccoli	12
Onions, dry	13	Eggplants (aubergines)	10
Chillies and peppers, green	12	Asparagus	5
Cucumbers and gherkins	12	Spinach	8
Peas, green	13		
Beans, green	12	Onions (inc. shallots), green	7
Carrots and turnips	13	Artichokes	4
Maize, green	4	Leeks, other alliaceous veg	8
Garlic	13	Okra	4
Other melons (inc. cantaloupes)	7	String beans	1

* No reliable data about the part of protected cultivation production of vegetables

Other specific crops:

Tobacco – 5 countries

Essential oil crops – Rose, Mint, Lavender

Ornamentals – outside and protected cultivation – lack of structured and system data; very dynamic trade

Summary		
Spread and outlined from the NPPD	Specific and outlined	Specific not mentioned
Wheat, Maize, Barley	Buckwheat Rice, paddy Coriander	Carary seed
Potato, Sugar beet		
Sunflower, Rapeseed, Soybeans	Olives Poppy seed	Safflower seed Melon seed oil
Flax	Cotton	
Tomatoes Watermelons Chilies and peppers, green Cucumbers and gherkins Eggplants Leaf vegetables	Asparagus	Okra String beans
Apricots Cherries Plums and sloes Sour cherries Strawberries	Citruses Figs Raspberries Cumin	Quinces Pomegranate Dates Carobs Persimmons
Ornamentals? Protected cultivation?	Tobacco Hops Rose	Essential oil crops

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.
Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 7

Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary threats (other than forestry) according to NPPO's in countries in the Balkan and Eastern European Region

Bulgaria	Cyprus	Czech R.	Greece	Hungary	Macedonia	Russia	Slovenia	Turkey	Ukraine
Few pests prioritized and most official monitored	Prioritized list	Prioritized list	Prioritized list	Prioritized list	Prioritized list	Prioritized list	Prioritized list and supplemented with many non-q-pests	Few pests prioritized and most official monitored	Prioritized list, but more like project ideas
<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i> , Western Corn Rootworm	<i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i>	<i>Quadraspidiotus perniciosus</i> , San José scale	Citrus tristeza virus (CTV)	<i>Dickeya solani</i> , blackleg of potato	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>	<i>Agrilus planipennis</i>	<i>Epitrix</i>	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i> , White tip disease agent	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>
<i>Tuta absoluta</i>	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. actinidiae	apple proliferation	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i> , Potato wart	<i>Epitrix similis</i> , <i>E. cucumeris</i> and <i>E. tuberis</i> , potato flea beetles	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> ssp. <i>sepedonicus</i>	<i>Polygraphus proximus</i>	<i>Tuta absoluta</i>	<i>Tuta absoluta</i>	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i> , bacterial fire blight
Pests below official monitored	<i>Liberibacter africanum</i> and <i>L. asiaticum</i> , Citrus huanglong-bing (citrus greening)	pear decline phtoplasma	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i> , Western Corn Rootworm	<i>Potato spindle tuber viroid</i>	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	<i>Ramularia collo-cygni</i> , <i>Ramularia</i> leaf spot	<i>Phythoraimeae operculella</i> , Potato tuber-moth	Potato cyst nematodes
<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>									
<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	European stone fruit phytoplasma	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i> , Red palm weevil	Potato stolbur phytoplasma	<i>Globodera rostchiensis</i>	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	<i>Meloidogyne</i> spp., Root knot nematodes	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	
<i>Liriomyza trifolii</i>	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>sepedonicus</i>	Potential effects of climate change on the spread and the risks of the	<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i> , Canker stain of plane	<i>Potato virus Y PVY^{NTN}</i> (N-Tuber Necrosis)	Plum pox virus	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> and <i>B. mucronatus</i>	<i>Globodera pallida</i> and <i>Globodera rostchiensis</i> , Potato cyst nematode	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	

EU regulated
organisms

<i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>	Ralstonia solanacearum	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> , Pinewood nematode	<i>Plasmopara halstedii</i>	Quadrascidiotus perniciosus	<i>Dickeya solani</i> и <i>D. dianthicola</i>	Plum pox virus,	<i>Ditylenchus destructor</i>
<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Xanthomonas axonopodis pv. Citri	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i> , Citrus long-horn beetle	Grapevine Flavescence dorée phytoplasma	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> sp. <i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Cold tolerance in tropical pests at high latitudes	Prunus necrotic ringspot virus	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>
<i>Frankliniella occidentalis</i>	Erwinia sp.	<i>Guignardia citricarpa</i> , Citrus black spot	<i>Scaphoideus titanus</i> , the vector of Flavescence Dorée phytoplasma		Phytosanitary control of seeds for presence of viruses	Monilinia fructicola	<i>Globodera pallida</i>
<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> spp. <i>michiganensis</i>	Xanthomonas fragariae	<i>Xanthomonas citri</i> subsp. <i>citri</i> , Citrus canker	<i>Plum pox virus</i>	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesicatoria</i> pepper & tomato	Testing of alternative fumigants for methyl bromide	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>persicae</i>	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>
<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesicatoria</i>	Seiridium cardinale	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>actinidiae</i> , Bacterial canker of kiwifruit	Candidatus Phytoplasma prunorum	Tomato spotted wilt virus	Requirements for quarantine pests reference collections	<i>Xanthomonas arboricola</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>	<i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.
<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> ssp. <i>Sepedonicus</i>	Guignardia citricarpa		<i>Rhagoletis cingulata</i>	Tobacco ringspot virus	Development and test of pheromone monitoring products to provide agro- and biosafety.	<i>Drosophila suzukii</i>	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>
<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>	Fusarium oxysporum albendenis		Tomato spotted wilt virus		Study of virulence of quarantine weed plants, <i>Cuscuta</i> spp., and relevance as vectors of pests	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>actinidiae</i>	<i>Liriomyza trifolii</i>
<i>Synchytrium</i>	Synchytrium		Tomato		Development	<i>Dryocosmus</i>	<i>Spodoptera</i>

<i>endobioticum</i>	endobioticum	<i>torrado virus</i>	of phytosanitary demarcation methods	<i>kuriphilus</i>	<i>littoralis</i>
<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Elsinoe spp	<i>Tomato yellow leaf curl virus</i>	Development of molecular methods for identification of <i>Bidens</i> spp	Grapevine flavescence dorée phytoplasma	
<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Tomato apical stunt viroid	<i>Tuta absoluta</i>	Development of diagnostic for <i>Dendrolimus sibiricus</i> , <i>Bemisia argentifolii</i> , <i>Potato Andean mottle virus</i> , <i>Potato Andean latent virus</i> , <i>Tomato and Tobacco Ringspot viruses</i> and <i>Beet Necrotic yellow vein virus</i> , <i>Erwinia amylovora</i> , <i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> race 3, <i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i> , <i>Dickeya solani</i> n <i>D. dianthicola</i> , <i>Phytophthora fragariae</i> , <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> , <i>Stenocarpella macrospora</i> and <i>S. maydis</i>	Low prioritized list	
<i>Ditylenchus destructor</i>	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid			Elateridae (Agriotes)	<i>Rotylenchus reniformis</i>

Meloidogyne chitwoodi Potato spindle tuber viroid

Fusarium section Sporotrichiella

Officially monitored species comprise 50 more pests not listed here

Meloidogyne fallax

Magnaporthe grisea (anamorph: *Pyricularia*) *Macrophomin a phaseolina* Diseases on Cucurbitaceae : *Acidovorax avenae* subsp. *citrulli*, *E. tracheiphilla*, Cucumber vein yellowing virus, Watermelon mosaic virus, Moroccan watermelon mosaic virus, Eggplant mottled dwarf virus and Cucurbit aphid borne yellows virus, *Macrophomin a phaseolina* *Ostrinia nubilalis*

Tomato spotted wilt virus
Potato Stolbur
Tomato torrado virus
Chrysanthemum stem necrosis virus

Meloidogyne chitwoodi
Meloidogyne fallax

Potato Spindle Tuber Viroid
Erwinia amylovora
Pseudomonas syringae pv. *Persicae*
Watermelon silver mottle virus
Pepino mosaic virus
Rhagoletis cerasi

Agrilus planipennis

Popillia japonica
Mycosphaerella pini

Aleyrodes proletella
European stone fruit yellows phytoplasma

<i>Xanthomonas arboricola</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>	Dactylospira vitifoliae	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>	Prune dwarf virus, Appel mosaic virus
<i>Monilinia fructicola</i>	Toxoptera citricida	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	<i>Fusicoccum amygdali</i>
<i>Plum pox potyvirus</i>	Leptinotarsa decemlineata	<i>Anaphlophora chinensis</i>	<i>Valsaria inisitiva</i>
<i>Tomato ring-spot virus</i>	Anoplophora chinensis, A. glabripennis, A. malasiaca	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	<i>Leucostoma persoonii</i>
<i>Tobacco ring-spot virus</i>	Toxoptera citricapra	<i>Rhagoletis completa</i>	<i>Dasineura pyri</i> , <i>D. mali</i>
Pear Decline phytoplasma	Monochamus sp.	Risks imposed by importing goods: Changes in the mixed populations of bark beetles (e.g. <i>Platypus</i>) emerging from wood and the associated fungal species	<i>Monilinia laxa</i> f. sp. <i>mali</i>
Apple Proliferation phytoplasma	Dacus (Bactrocera) sp.	Non-quarantine pests	<i>Botryosphaeria obtusa</i>
Apricot chlorotic leaf roll phytoplasma	Anastrepha sp.	<i>Fusarium foetens</i>	<i>Monilinia vaccinii-corymbosi</i>
Tomato ringspot nepovirus	Diaphorina citri	Pepper mild mottle virus	<i>Colletotrichum acutatum</i>
Tobacco ringspot nepovirus	Tuta absoluta	<i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i>	<i>Rhagoletis completa</i> , mulberry scale
<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	Thrips palmi	<i>Aproceros leucopoda</i>	<i>Scaphoideus titanus</i>
<i>Xylophilus ampelinus</i>	Drosophila suzukii		grapevine ESCA disease
Grapevine	Grapevine		<i>Pulvinaria</i> sp

Flavescence
doree

flavescence
doree
Meloidogyne
ethiopica
Bursaphelenc
hus
xylophilus
Tetranychus
evansi

Neopulvinaria
sp
Planococcus
sp

Pseudococcus
sp
Parthenolecan
ium sp.
Hop stunt
viroid
Invasive alien
plants: *Fallo-
pia japonica*,
Increasing
diagnostic
capacity of
laboratories in
the wider
Balkan and
Pannonian
region

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.
Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 8

NPPO's in countries in the Balkan and Eastern European Region split on crop sectors and crops in descending order of numbers of countries (10) listing the pest.

*Protected is glasshouse, screenhouse, plastic coverage etc.

No. of countries listing the pest	Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
5	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> , <i>G. pallida</i> a.o. potato nematodes
5	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Syncytrium endobioticum</i>
4	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>
4	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp, i.e <i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>
3	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>sepedonicus</i>
2	Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Epitrix</i> spp.
2	Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato stulbur phytoplasma
2	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Dickeya</i> sp.
1	Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato Virus Y ^{NTN}
1	Agriculture	Potato	Insect	Colorado beetle
1	Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Phythorimeae operculella</i> , potato tuber moth
2	Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Ditylenchus destructor</i>
1	Agriculture	Potato, vegetables	Bacteria	<i>Ca. Liberibacter solanacearum</i>
1	Agriculture	Potato, tomato,	Mite	<i>Tetranychus evansi</i>

		aubergine, tobacco		
3	Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>
1	Agriculture	Rice, strawberry	Fungi	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>
1	Agriculture	Sunflower	Fungi	<i>Plasmopara halstedii</i>
1	Agriculture	Cotton	Nematode	<i>Rotylenchus reniformis</i>
1	Agriculture, *protected, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>
1	Agriculture	Cotton	Insect	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>
4	Protected	Tomato	Insect	<i>Tuta absoluta</i>
3	*Protected	Tomato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>michiganensis</i>
3	Protected	Tomato, ornamentals	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid
2	Protected	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato torrado virus
2	Protected	Tomato, ornamentals	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus
1	Protected	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus
1	Protected	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato apical stunt viroid
1	Protected	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic potexvirus
1	Protected	Tomato	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesicatoria</i>
1	Protected	Vegetables, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Liriomyza</i> sp.
1	Protected	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>
1	Protected	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>
1	Protected	Ornamentals	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stem necrosis virus
2	Protected	Ornamentals	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid
	Protected	Ornamentals	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>
4	Viticulture	Grapevine	Virus etc.	Flavescence dorée phytoplasma

1	Viticulture	Grapevine	Bacteria	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>
1	Viticulture	Grapevine	Insect	<i>Dactulosphaira vitifolia</i>
2	Fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas axonopodis</i> pv. <i>citri</i>
2	Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarpa</i>
1	Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Elsinoe</i> spp
1	Fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus
1	Fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus huanglogbing
1	Fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>
1	Fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Diaphorina citri</i>
4	Fruit	Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus
3	Fruit	Stone fruit kiwi	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>actinidia</i>
2	Fruit	Apple and pear	Virus etc.	Phytoplasma in fruit trees, <i>Apple proliferation</i> and <i>pear decline phytoplasma</i>
2	Fruit	Pome, stone fruit, berries	Insect	<i>Drosophila suzukii</i>
2	Fruit	Stone fruit	Insect	<i>Rhagoletis cingulata</i> & <i>R. cerasi</i>
1	Fruit	Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Prunus necrotic ringspot virus
1	Fruit	Pome, stone fruit, berries	Insect	<i>Quadraspidiotus perniciosus</i> , San Jose scale
1	Fruit	Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Monilia fructicola</i>
1	Fruit	Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv <i>persicae</i>
1	Fruit	Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas arboricola</i> pv <i>pruni</i>
1	Fruit	Strawberry	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>
4	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
3	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>
2	Plants for planting	Chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>
1	Plants for planting,	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>

1	forestry Plants for planting	Palm	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>
1	Plants for planting	Platanus	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i>
1	Plants for planting	Myrtle	Insect	<i>Anastrepha</i> sp
4	Forestry	Conifers	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>
2	Forestry	Ash	Insect	<i>Agrilus planipennis</i> (emerald ash borer)
1	Forestry	Deciduous trees	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>
1	Forestry	Abies	Insect	<i>Polygraphus proximus</i>
1	Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella pini</i>
1	Forestry	Cypress tree	Fungi	<i>Seiridium cardinale</i>
	General problem	General topic		Specific description
1	The ecosys- tem	Climatic chang- es		Cold tolerance in tropical pests at high latitudes.
1	Pests	Diagnostics		Phytosanitary control of seeds for pres- ence of viruses. Diagnostic methods for a long list of pests (insects, bacteria, virus and fungi).
1	Control	Pesticide treat- ment		Testing of alternative fumigants for meth- yl bromide.
1	Pests	Reference col- lections		Requirements for quarantine pests ref- erence collections.
1	Pests	Detec- tion/monitoring		Pheromone monitoring products to pro- vide agro-and biosafety.
1	Invasive weed	Study		Study of virulence of quarantine weed, <i>Cuscuta</i> spp., and relevance as vectors of pests. Molecular method for identification of <i>Bidens</i> sp.
1	Control	Management		Development of phytosanitary demarca-

tion methods

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.

Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 8 B

Shortlist of Annex 8 only including pests stated **by two ore more partners.**

*Protected is glasshouse, screenhouse, plastic coverage etc.

No. of countries listing the pest	Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
5	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> , <i>G. pallida</i> a.o. potato cyst nematodes
5	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Syncytrium endobioticum</i>
4	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>
4	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp, i.e <i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>
3	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>sepedonicus</i>
2	Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Epitrix</i> spp.
2	Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato stulbur phytoplasma
2	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Dickeya</i> sp.
2	Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Ditylenchus destructor</i>
3	Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>
4	Protected	Tomato	Insect	<i>Tuta absoluta</i>
3	*Protected	Tomato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>michiganensis</i>
3	Protected	Tomato, ornamentals	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid
2	Protected	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato torrado virus
2	Protected	Tomato, ornamentals	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus
2	Protected	Ornamentals	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid
	Protected	Ornamentals	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>
4	Viticulture	Grapevine	Virus etc.	Flavescence dorée phytoplasma
2	Fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas axonopodis</i> pv. <i>citri</i>
2	Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarpa</i>
4	Fruit	Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus
3	Fruit	Stone fruit kiwi	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>actinidia</i>
2	Fruit	Apple and pear	Virus etc.	Phytoplasma in fruit trees, <i>Apple proliferation</i> and <i>pear decline phytoplasma</i>

2	Fruit	Pome, stone fruit, berries	Insect	<i>Drosophila suzukii</i>
2	Fruit	Stone fruit	Insect	<i>Rhagoletis cingulata & R. cerasi</i>
4	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
3	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>
2	Plants for planting	Chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>
4	Forestry	Conifers	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>
2	Forestry	Ash	Insect	<i>Agrilus planipennis</i> (emerald ash borer)
	General problem	General topic		Specific description

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.
Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 9

List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests.

Protected crops are glasshouse, screenhouse, plastic coverage etc.

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Comments
1. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	
2. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	
3. Protected crops, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	As regards Thailand
4. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	
5. Agriculture	Potato, ornamentals	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid	
6. Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	
7. Agriculture, protected crops	Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Import from Egypt
8. Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	
9. Forestry	Conifera	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> pine wood nematode	
10. Fruit	Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	
11. Protected crops, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.

Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 10

Overview of interceptions per pest of harmful organisms in EU 2007-09

Protected crops are glasshouse, screenhouse, plastic coverage etc.

Sorted after number of interceptions

Crop sector	Crop	Organism group	Pest	2007	2008	2009
Conglomerated data for selected groups of organisms						
Protected crops	Ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	White flies, <i>Bemisia</i>	202	302	243
Fruit	Fruit	Insect	Fruit flies, <i>Tephritidae</i> , non-European	389	292	286
Protected crops, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	Thrips, <i>Thrips palmi</i>	289	307	306
Protected crops, agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Leafminers, <i>Liriomyza</i>	139	271	318
Agriculture, Protected crops	Vegetables, tomato, grass, maize, rice, potato, ornamental flower/ ornamental flower	Insect/insect	Spodoptera/Helicoverpa	417	334	104
Other organisms						
Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	66	149	74
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	<i>Sinoxylon</i> sp. (not on the q-list)	36	22	56
Agriculture	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	Leucinodes orbonalis (on EPPO's Alert list)	18	37	26
Fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Xanthomonas axonopodis pv. citri (EPPO quarantine pest)	28	25	25
Agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Agromyzidae (<i>Liriomyza</i> spp. a.o. leaf miners)	51	7	12
Protected crops	Protected ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	Aleyrodidae (<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> a.o. hemipteras)	60	3	5
Forestry	Larch tree	Fungi	<i>Guignardia</i> sp.	42	4	3
Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	36	9	-
Plants for planting	Box tree	Insect	<i>Diaphania indica</i> (box tree moth)	12	23	9

Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	Bostrichidae (wood borer)	15	19	8
Fruit	Macadamia nuts	Insect	Chryptophlebia leucotreta	13	3	22
Forestry	Conifers	Insect	Scolytidae (<i>Gnathotrichus sulcatus</i>)	12	19	4
Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	Meloidogyne sp.	3	17	14
Protected crops, agriculture	Tomato	Virus	Pepino mosaic virus	11	14	6
Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	Cerambycidae (<i>Anoplophora</i> spp.)	13	11	6
Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	Hirschmanniella sp.	11	10	6

Sorted after crop sector

Crop sector	Crop	Organism group	Pest	2007	2008	2009
Conglomerated data for selected groups of organisms						
Protected crops	Ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	White flies, <i>Bemisia</i>	202	302	243
Fruit	Fruit	Insect	Fruit flies, <i>Tephritidae</i> , non-European	389	292	286
Protected crops, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	Thrips, <i>Thrips palmi</i>	289	307	306
Protected crops, agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Leafminers, <i>Liriomyza</i>	139	271	318
Protected crops, agriculture	Vegetables, tomato, grass, maize, rice, potato, ornamental flower/ ornamental flower	Insect/insect	Spodoptera/Helicoverpa	417	334	104
Other organisms						
Agriculture	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	Leucinodes orbonalis (on EP-PO's Alert list)	18	37	26
Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	Meloidogyne sp.	3	17	14
Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	Hirschmanniella sp.	11	10	6
Agriculture, Protected crops	Vegetables	Insect	Agromyzidae (<i>Liriomyza</i> spp. a.o. leaf miners)	51	7	12
Protected crops, agriculture	Tomato	Virus	Pepino mosaic virus	11	14	6
Protected crops	Protected ornamentals and veg-	Insect	Aleyrodidae (hemipteras other than <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>)	60	3	5

	etables					
Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	66	149	74
Fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas axonopodis</i> pv. <i>citri</i> (EPPO quarantine pest)	28	25	25
Fruit	Macadamia nuts	Insect	<i>Chryptophlebia leucotreta</i>	13	3	22
Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	36	9	-
Plants for planting	Box tree	Insect	<i>Diaphania indica</i> (box tree moth)	12	23	9
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	<i>Sinoxylon</i> sp. (not on the q-list)	36	22	56
Forestry	Larch tree	Fungi	<i>Guignardia</i> sp.	42	4	3
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	Bostrichidae (wood borer)	15	19	8
Forestry	Conifers	Insect	Scolytidae (<i>Gnathotrichus sulcatus</i>)	12	19	4
Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	Cerambycidae (Anoplophora spp.)	13	11	6

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.

Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 11

Examples on different factors influencing on why certain q-pests have higher priority than other.

Many factors influence on how people working with phytosanitary problems regard the threat and importance of a specific q-pest. Some of the factors are: the status of the pest: is it absent, introduced, under spreading or established. The migration biology of the pest: naturally spreading by short or long distance migration; airborne, soilborne, waterborne; the influence of human transport. The number of host plants (one, few or many host plants) and the economical importance of each host plants. The habitat of the host plants: intensively cultivated field or glasshouse crops, landscape and park plants, forestry etc.

All these and more factors influence why certain pests and associated crops are more in focus than other and initiation of research projects have different priority.

Examples:

1. The pest is strongly regulated and no interception or registration has been obtained the last many years: f. ex. *Atropellis* spp. (Atropellis cancer in pine). Very low priority.
2. No interception or registration of the pest has been obtained the last many years: f. ex. Oak wilt (*Ceratocystis fagacearum*). Very low priority, but research might still be relevant because of the risk to introduce the pest with import with wood chip from North America.
3. No interception or registration of the pest has been obtained the last many years: f. ex. Andean potato viruses. Very low priority, but research might still be relevant because a lot of efforts are put into preventive testing.
4. The pest has changed pathogenicity and spreads naturally by long distance transport, f. ex. Ash die-back (*Chalara fraxinea*). Eradication impossible, only isolated regions (islands) can maybe resist infection. Low priority.
5. The pest has changed pathogenicity and increases host spectrum and spreads naturally only by short distance transport, f. ex. Sudden Oak Death (*Phytophthora ramorum*). Eradication possible. High priority
6. The pest has invaded Europe and spreads naturally by the pest's migration, f.ex. horse-chestnut leaf-miner (*Cameraria ohridella*). Prevention of migration not possible, but impediment is. Low priority.
7. The pest has invaded Europe and spreads naturally by the pests' migration, f.ex. Western Corn Rootworm (*Diabrotica virgifera*) Eradication not possible any more, but impediment is. The pest connected to an important agricultural crop. Regulation has a high priority.
8. The pest has recently been established in one member country, where it is under eradication measures, but risk of further spreading, f. ex. Pine wood nematode (*Bursaphelenchus xylophilis*). High priority.
9. The pest has recently been introduced repeatedly in some member states and eradication initiated f. ex. citrus long - horned beetle. High priority.

10. The pest is repeatedly intercepted and sometimes introduced and subsequently eradicated, f.ex. the whitefly *Bemisia tabaci*. Low priority, because the biology and eradication methods are well known.
11. The pest is established in small areas in many member states and repeatedly under eradication, f. ex. fireblight (*Erwinia amylovora*). Potato ring rot (*Corynebacterium sepedonicum* subsp. *sepedonicus*), potato cyst nematode (*Globodera* spp.) Priority? Depends on many factors.

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop. Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems in the region of Balkan and Eastern Europe.
Sofia 28th – 29th February 2012

Annex 12

FP6 and FP7 PLANT HEALTH RESEARCH PROJECTS (excluding forestry projects)

	Description	Sector	Pathogen
FP6			
PEPEIRA	Pepino mosaic virus: epidemiology, economic impact and pest risk analysis. PRA + diagnostic	Horticulture/ Tomato	<i>Pepino mosaic virus</i>
BACTOFRUCT	Development of biological pesticide against fire blight	Horticulture/ Rosaceae	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
PORT CHECK	DEVELOPMENT OF GENERIC ON SITE MOLECULAR DIAGNOSTICS FOR EU QUARANTINE PESTS AND PATHOGENS. Development and evaluation of real-time PCR assays for a number of key harmful organisms, including <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> and pinewood nematode; and transfer these assays to field portable real-time PCR platforms which were originally developed for bio-warfare and bio-terrorism applications.	All	All/prioritized?
DIABR-ACT	Harmonization of the strategies for fighting <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> .	Agriculture/ Maize	<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>
EUPHRESCO	Coordination of European Phytosanitary (Statutory Plant Health) Research	All	All
RAPRA	Risk analysis for <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> , a newly recognized pathogen threat to Europe and the cause of Sudden Oak Death in the USA	Horticulture	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>
FP7			
PRATIQUE	Enhancements of pest risk analysis techniques: targeted research to improve existing procedures and develop new methods for the assessment of economic, environmental and social impacts, summarizing risk in effective, harmonized ways that take account of uncertainty, mapping endangered areas pathway risk analysis and systems approaches and guiding actions during emergencies caused by outbreaks of harmful pests.	All	All

QDETECT	Developing quarantine pest detection methods for use by national plant protection organizations (NPPO) and inspection services. Development of detection methods based on biochemical (detecting volatile organic compounds [VOC] and nucleic acid), acoustic (including resonance), remote imaging (incorporating spectral and automated data analysis) and pest trapping (insect pests and pathogen vectors) techniques.		High priority targets for the EU such as the pine wood nematode (<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>), potato brown rot (<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>) and potato ring rot (<i>Clavibacter michiganensis ssp. Sepedonicus</i>), Asian longhorn beetle (<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>) and a range of whitefly transmitted viruses.
EUPHRESKO II	EUROPEAN PHYTOSANITARY RESEARCH COORDINATION II	All	All
SHARCO	Sharka containment. Tools such as marker-assisted selection, PPV resistant plant materials, guidelines, warning systems, decision-support system. Identification of driving factors of PPV spread and diversification and develop novel and highthrough-put detection systems warning sharka outbreaks.	Horticulture (Stonefruits)	<i>Plum pox virus</i>
QBOL	Development of a new diagnostic tool using DNA barcoding to identify quarantine organisms in support of plant health. Making DNA barcoding available for plant health diagnostics and focusing on strengthening the link between traditional and molecular taxonomy as a sustainable diagnostic resource. Within QBOL collections harboring plant pathogenic Q-organisms will be made available. Informative genes from selected species on the EU Directive and EPPO lists will be DNA barcoded from vouchered specimens. The sequences, together with taxonomic features, will be included in a new internet-based database system. A validation procedure on developed protocols and the database will be undertaken across worldwide partners to ensure robustness of procedures for use in a distributed network of laboratories across Europe.	All	All/prioritized?
Palm protect	Eradication and containment strategies and tools for the implementation of EU legislation against the red palm weevil <i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i> Olivier and <i>Paysandisia archon</i> Burmeister. The PALM PROTECT consortium aims to develop reliable methods, for use by national plant protection organisations (NPPO),	Palm trees	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i> + <i>Paysandisia archon</i>

inspection services, growers and other end-users, for early detection, eradication, control and containment of the red palm weevil, *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* and the moth *Paysandisia archon*. The methods will be developed for use at origin, point of entry, in transit and on-site to combat these invasive pests of palm trees.

RESEARCH PROJECTS RELATED TO PLANT HEALTH

		Description
2E-BCAS IN CROPS	FP6	Enhancement and exploitation of soil biocontrol agents for bio-constraint management in crops. The main aim of the project is to study some of the already available or the most promising biocontrol microorganisms (such as <i>Fusarium</i> , <i>Trichoderma</i> or <i>Coniothyrium</i> sp.), using a combination of strategies.
CROPBIOERROR		FOOD AND CROP BIOSECURITY ALSO AS A MEAN TO PREVENT AND TO BE PREPARED FOR BIOTERRORISM. Addresses the threat of plant pathogens as weapons against crops.
RESISTVIR		Co-ordination of research on genetic resistance to control plant pathogenic viruses and their vectors in European crops
ENDURE		Development and implementation of durable pest control strategies. Reducing pesticide inputs as well as on mitigating inherent risks through alternative technologies, and/or basing control strategies on a more cohesive knowledge of the ecology, behavior and genetics of pest organisms.
BIOEXPLOIT		Exploitation of natural plant biodiversity for the pesticide-free production of food (resistance breeding).
PURE	FP7	Pesticide use and risk reduction in European farming systems with integrated pest management
TEAMPEST		Theoretical developments and empirical measurements of the external costs of pesticides
LEGUME-FUTURE		Legume supported cropping systems for Europe
EU-BERRY		The sustainable improvement of European berry production, quality and nutritional value in a changing environment: Strawberries, Currants, Blackberries, Blueberries and Raspberries
FRUITBREEDOMICS		Integrated approach for increasing breeding efficiency in fruit tree crops
BACCARA		Biodiversity and climate change, a risk analysis
MULTISWARD		Multi-species swards and multi scale strategies for multifunctional grassland-based ruminant production systems
EUPHOROS		Efficient use of inputs in protected horticulture
VALORAM		Valorizing Andean microbial diversity through sustainable intensification of potato-based farming systems

The main conclusion from the Balkan-Eastern European workshop was that there are no specific regional plant health problems in the Balkan-Eastern European region making a regional approach irrelevant (unnecessary) for EUPHRESKO. Based in this conclusion, no further recommendations were worked out.

- **A workshops exploring EUPHRESKO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important Forestry Plant Health threats was held in Vienna 17–18 January 2012.**

The report from the workshop, including Annexes is provided here:

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Notes from the workshop

The workshop was held at The Austrian Agency of Health and Food Safety (AGES), Spargelfeldstraße 191, A-1220 Vienna/AUSTRIA. AGES kindly provided facilities for the workshop.

Participants

All EUPHRESCO partners and observers were invited, and EUPHRESCO partners who have expressed specific interest in forestry received a special invitation. The last mentioned countries include Finland, Portugal, Norway, United Kingdom, Poland, Bulgaria, Ukraine and Austria. Denmark participated as work package leader. However several apologies were obtained and at last the following partners participated:

Tuula Maki-Valkama	Finland
Halvor Solheim	Norway
Joan Webber	UK
Alois Egartner	Austria
Sylvia Blümel	Austria
Steen Lykke Nielsen	Denmark

Annexes

Programme

Annex F0 EUPH Forestry WP5. Introduction and overview of background materials

Annex F1 EUPH Forestry WP5. Forestry Competences Mapping. EUPHRESCO 2 - Partners and additional Institutions with funding mandate for plant health forestry research

Annex F2 EUPH Forestry WP5. NPPOs forestry phytosanitary threats. Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary forestry threats according to NPPO's in EUPHRESCO partner sorted after importance by each NPPO

Annex F3 EUPH Forestry WP5. Importance forestry phytosanitary threats. Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary forestry threats according to NPPO's in EUPHRESCO partner sorted after importance by each NPPO

Annex F4. EUPH Forestry WP5. List of Council Directive 2000/29/EC sorted after pest.

Overview of harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Annex F5 EUPH Forestry WP5. List of Council Directive 2000/29/EC sorted after crop.

Overview of harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Annex F6 EUPH Forestry WP5. Topic calls from EUPHRESCO-1 and EUPHRESCO-2 (2011).

EUPHRESCO topic calls split on crops

Annex F7 EUPH Forestry WP5. EPPO Alert List. Overview of harmful organisms listed in EPPO's Alert List (last updated September 2011).

Annex F8 EUPH Forestry WP5. EU Emergency measures. List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests

Annex F9 EUPH Forestry WP5. Interceptions. Overview of interceptions per pest of harmful organisms in EU 2007-09

Annex 10 EUPH Forestry WP5. FP6 and FP7 plant health Forestry projects

List of EU Frame Work Programme (FP) 6 and FP7 forestry plant health projects and forestry plant health related projects

Annex F11 EUPH Forestry WP5. Factors influencing priorities. Examples of different factors influencing on why certain quarantine pests have higher priority than other

Annex F12 EUPH Forestry WP5. Forestry plant health topics proposed to the first call round in 2011 in EUPHRESCO-2. List of the topic ideas from the 1st call round of EUPHRESCO-2 from 2011. Of the 10 topics one has been realised as a transnational project.

Annex F13 EUPH Forestry WP5. Short analyse of some of the background material.

Notes from the workshop's day 1, the 17th January 2012

Concerning definition of what is included under forestry plant health and what is not (for example public greens (parks, street plantings, commons, nurseries and orchards).

Comments by the workshop participants: seen from the point of view of plant health pests, those pests infesting and infecting trees are included under forestry plant health. Seen from the point of view of the plant hosts, forestry plant health includes trees and hereunder forests (public and private) and forestry nurseries, but not nurseries producing garden plants and not orchard crops. There exists a grey zone about public greens and nature areas.

Concerning mapping of funders with mandate to fund forestry plant health research, Annex F1

The annex shows that out of the 24 responding partners/observers, 15 of those are mandated to fund forestry. Furthermore 11 institutions were additionally named as having mandate for forestry funding. Comments by the workshop participants: These Institutions/organisations should be invited/involved in EUPHRESCO [the official partner of the country that has the mandate for forestry funding should be invited]. The mapping result might change if/when more responses are obtained and included.

Concerning results of Questionnaire to NPPO's on actual forest threats, Annex F2 & F3

NPPOs from 14 countries have replied; only one Mediterranean country is included, giving an overweight of Nordic and Central European countries; there is also big differences in how many pests each contributing partner/observer has listed. Many of the named pests in annex 2 & 3 are not listed in the EU Directive 2000/29/EC – or mentioned in EPPO's alert list. Annex 2 & 3 also include pests, where EUPHRESCO or EU FP7 projects already have been initiated. However from the list it is possible to identify some pests on which 6-10 NPPOs have expressed concern.

The replies from the NPPO's also include many topics of more general character as for example climatic changes, use of integrated pest management systems and problems with plant products for energy production (for example wood chip). The workshop participants recommend EUPHRESCO to consider to include more general topics in future topic call rounds.

The participants in the workshop furthermore discussed that new use of forestry products, as for example untreated conifer stems inside artificial (plastic) Christmas trees from the Far East and re-naming of a plant product as for example wood chip import (from North America) to a bio-energy-source.

Concerning the overview of FP6 and FP7 projects on forestry plant health and related forestry project, annex F10

Further projects could be included in the annex 10. An EFSA project generally on PRA's, including forestry and a new concerted action on ash dieback. [The EFSA project has subsequently been included. The COST action on ash dieback]

Concerning the number of EUPHRESCO initiated projects and pests in forestry compared with other crops

In the table below is forestry compared with other crop sectors/crops

The EUPHRESCO initiated projects (see Annex F6) split on crop sectors/crops and compared with the distribution of pests in the same crop sectors/crops listed in directive 2000/29/EC and the EPPO's Alert List

Crop sector/crop	No. of EUPHRESCO initiated projects	No. of EUPH. projects in % of sector / crop in column 1	The sector / crop in % in directive 2000/29/EC	The sector / crop in % in EPPO's Alert List
Potato	8	27	10	8
Maize	1	3	4	11
Tomato	2	7	7	27
Vegetables fields	1	3	8	3
Ornamentals glasshouse	2	7	14	3
Fruit	5	17	47	14
Vine	2	7	4	0
Plants for planting	4	13	12	16
Forestry	3	10	14	22
Other broader topics	3	10	0	0

From the table it appears that compared to the directive 2000/29/EC list there is a small underweight of EUPHRESCO initiated projects in forestry. Compared to EPPO's Alert List there is a clear underweight of forestry.

Notes from the 18th January 2012, the 2nd day of the workshop

Concerning reasons for the very low participation (12 announced participation out of 31 EUPHRESCO-partners and finally only 5 partners attended the workshop):

A reason might be problems to identify and reach the proper plant health forestry funders for the workshop invitation. (Some EUPHRESCO partners appointed forestry scientist, because they thought

the workshop was a scientific workshop. When informed that it was a workshop for funders in forestry plant health they were not able to appoint a representative). The mapping of which ministry/agency has mandate to finance plant health forestry research (annex F1) shows that 10 new institutions were identified. The workshop invitation might not have been forwarded from the present EUPHRESCO representative to the forestry funder institution, even though it is the responsibility of national EUPHRESCO representative. In some countries more than one institution is mandated to fund forestry and maybe the one mandated specifically to plant health topics might not have been identified. Competences/responsibilities for funding are unclear in some countries due to reorganisation. The invitation to the workshop was sent out in November and followed up in December 2011, a time of the year where many employees are busy with reporting, so general time constraints might explain part of the low participation.

Concerning the limited response to request to NPOs on main forestry phytosanitary threats, annex F2.

The participants discussed the validity of the background material in annex F2, which as mentioned in the notes from the 1st day missed input from Mediterranean countries except Portugal and has an overweight of input from Nordic- Baltic and Central European Countries. It was concluded, that even though the background material obtained from the partners did not cover all EUPHRESCO countries it is still valid information to be used.

Aims of the workshop

- To analyse the degree of underrepresentation of forestry topics and EUPHRESCO-initiated projects in forestry.
- To explore the reasons for the underrepresentation.
- To propose solution/solutions to EUPHRESCO-2 (PMG, assembly) to increase the representation of forestry topics and EUPHRESCO-initiated projects.

Concerning the hypotheses set up in the introduction to the workshop, annex F0.

Hypothesis 1. Many of the EUPHRESCO partners and observers (both from EUPHRESCO-1 and EUPHRESCO-2) do not have mandate to fund forestry research. (Probably because forestry belongs under another ministry or agency).

The workshop participants agree that H1 is partly correct. The results from the analysis of funders with mandate to fund forestry plant health research, Annex F1 showed that not all funders of forestry plant health research have been reached. Only 15 out of the 24, which had responded, have mandate to fund forestry plant health research and 10 more forestry funders were additionally mentioned. The workshop participants suggest to invite national forestry research funders, who at present are non-EUPHRESCO-2-partner, to join EUPHRESCO-2.

Hypothesis 2. There are not as many problems with plant health in forestry than in other crops/cultures.

The workshop participants agreed that there are not as many plant health problems in forestry compared to agri-/horticultural crops with regard to numbers of pests. However, there has been an increase in forestry plant health threats both in number and impact over the last decade.

To the rhetorical question: "would it be relevant to run specific forestry topic identification round under EUPH-2 or will it be sufficient to include forestry related topics under the regular EUPH-2 topic

identification rounds?" the workshop participants agreed to reject the idea of separate forestry call rounds. The preference is to have all topic proposals in one for all funders to avoid that funders might miss topics and to avoid overlapping topics.

Hypothesis 3. In the last few years many plant health forestry research projects (national and transnational) have been initiated, so there has been/is a lesser demand to initiate new projects in forestry than in other crops/cultures and this has been/is the background for the underrepresentation of forestry in EUPHRESKO-1.

The workshop participants discussed whether there has been an underrepresentation of forestry plant health topics in FP6 /FP7. The workshop participants concluded that there have been notable projects in forestry plant health topics in FP6 /FP7 especially on specific pests (e.g. pine wood nematode, *Phytophthora ramorum*), diagnostics, detection and PRAs.

To the rhetorical question: "would it be relevant to settle a permanent forestry working group under EUPHRESKO to secure forestry is not neglected?" the workshop participants answered no. But suggested to consider to arrange a European stakeholder/funder workshop on forestry plant health, taking into consideration the outcome of a future ISEFOR workshop.

To the overall question: "has the forestry crop sector been or not been underrepresented in EUPHRESKO up to now?" the workshop participants concluded: 10% of the EUPHRESKO initiated projects have been forestry projects vs. 14% of the EU 2000/29/EEC listed pest organisms are forestry pests. However > 20% of the pest organisms listed in the EPPO alert list are forestry pests, which demonstrates that for emerging pests there is a underrepresentation of forestry topics in EUPHRESKO (remark: out of 60 topics in 1st call EUPHRESKO-2, 10 topic proposals dealt with forestry plant health, but only 1 has been realised. One of the reasons for that may be that EUPHRESKO could NOT identify and contact all relevant forestry plant health funders. However, the workshop participants recognized that it is unclear how to compare figures of statistics of the different crop sectors and which figures to take into account for a comparison (e.g. trade value, area of production, annual contra perennial crops).

Conclusions and recommendations

Definition of forestry plant health: those quarantine and serious regulated pest and upcoming pests infecting trees grown in forests and in nurseries growing forestry tree production.

The workshop participants concluded that there are not as many plant health problems in forestry compared to agri-/horticultural crops with regard to numbers of pests, but there has been an increase in forestry plant health threats both in number and impact over the last decade, which hopefully will result in more EUPHRESKO initiated projects in forestry in the future.

The workshop participants recommend EUPHRESKO

- to consider to arrange a European stakeholder/funder workshop on forestry plant health in cooperation with ISEFOR
- to invite national forestry research funders, who at present are non-EUPHRESKO-2-partner, to join or be associated to EUPHRESKO.
- EUPHRESKO to consider to include more general topics in future topic call rounds.

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F0 EUPH Forestry WP5. Introduction and overview of background materials

Background:

In the application for EUPHRESCO2 the work package 5 (WP5) includes activities on underrepresented plant sectors and forestry is specifically selected for a closer analysis.

Extract from the WP5 application text:

5.2 Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems and increased inclusion of plant-producing sectors under-represented in EUPHRESCO-I

This sub-workpackage will analyse and explore the potential and relevance of a regionalised approach to specific plant health topics and for certain plant-production sectors that have been under-represented in EUPHRESCO-I transnational projects.

During EUPHRESCO-I it was clear that forestry plant health was insufficiently included in research topics selected for transnational funding cooperation, despite forestry-related pests being of current and high concern to the EU. Therefore, this sub-workpackage will include:

- Production of a plan for improving the financing and initiation of forestry-based research related to plant health.

Aims of the exploration

- To analyse the degree of underrepresentation of forestry topics and EUPHRESCO-initiated projects in forestry.
- To explore the reasons for the underrepresentation.
- To propose a solution/solutions to EUPHRESCO-2 (PMG, assembly) to increase the representation of forestry topics and EUPHRESCO-initiated projects.

Hypotheses

- Hypothesis 1. Many of the EUPHRESCO partners and observers (both from EUPH-1 and EUPH-2) do not have mandate to fund forestry research. (Probably because forestry belongs under another ministry or agency).
- Hypothesis 2. There are not as many problems with plant health in forestry than in other crops/cultures.
- Hypothesis 3. In the last few years many plant health forestry research projects (national and transnational) have been initiated, so there has been/is a lesser demand to initiate new projects in forestry than in other crops/cultures and this has been/is the background for the underrepresentation of forestry in EUPH-1.
- Others?

Aims of the Vienna forestry workshop

The overall aim is to discuss the analyses worked out as background material to the workshop, to agree on the conclusions for the reasons for the underrepresentation of forestry and to propose solutions to increase the representation of forestry topics and EUPHRESCO-initiated projects.

Sub-aims:

- Define what is included under forestry and what is not (for example parks, street plantings, nurseries, commons, orchards?).
- Approve and reject hypotheses.
- Propose solutions, hereunder
 - o If hypothesis 1 is correct,
 - Should national forestry research funders, who at present are non-EUPHRESCO-2-partner, be invited to join EUPH-2?
 - Would it be relevant to run specific forestry topic identification round under EUPH-2 or will it be sufficient to include forestry related topics under the regular EUPH-2 topic identification rounds?
 - Would it be relevant to settle a permanent forestry working group under EUPH to secure forestry is not neglected?
 - o If hypotheses 2 or 3 are correct, there will be no need for special initiative.

Background materials worked out to the workshop

Annex F0 EUPH Forestry WP5. Introduction and overview of background materials

Annex F1 EUPH Forestry WP5. Forestry Competences Mapping. EUPHRESCO 2 - Partners and additional Institutions with funding mandate for plant health forestry research

Annex F2 EUPH Forestry WP5. NPPOs forestry phytosanitary threats. Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary forestry threats according to NPPO's in EUPHRESCO partner sorted after importance by each NPPO

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EUPHRESCO topic calls split on crops

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Annex F11 EUPH Forestry WP5. Factors influencing priorities. Examples of different factors influencing on why certain quarantine pests have higher priority than other

EUPHRESCO_2_WP5_Forestry_Compences_Mapping

EUPHRESCO 2 - Partners and additional Institutions with fundeing mandate for plant health forestry research (updated for Norway and Portugal)

No. Partner	Name Partner	Country	Y: Yes; N: No Reply (Y/N)	0: means NO mandate (competence) funder mandate research PLH Agr(hort)-culture (1 or 0)	1: means mandate (competence) funder mandate research PLH Agr(hort)-culture & forestry (1 or 0)	Funder mandate research PLH Forestry only (0 or 1)	additional inclusion of institution with FMRPLH forestry in EUPHRESCO 2 recommended (Y/N/n.r.)	contact person	e-mail	
2	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Environment & Waste Management (BMLFUW)	Austria	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Elfriede Fuhrmann	elfriede.fuhrmann@lebensministerium.at	Stubenring 1, Vienna A-1012, Austria
3	Austrian Agency for Health & Food Safety (AGES)	Austria	YES	1	0	0	n.r.	Sylvia Bluemel	sylvia.bluemel@ages.at	Spargelfeldstr. 191, A-1220 Wien, AUSTRIA, Phone: +43-(0)-10555-33300; Fax: +43-(0)-10555 95 33300
4	The Federal Public Service for Public Health, Food Chain Security & Environment (FPS)	Belgium	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Ris Nouwen	ris.nouwen@health.fgov.be	4 Rue de l'Autonomie Brussels 1070 Belgium
5	Walloon Agricultural Research Centre (CRA-W)	Belgium	YES	0	0	0	n.r.	Thibaut Olivier, Anne Chandelier	t.olivier@cra.walloon.be	CRA-W, Life Sciences Department, F. Marchal Building, Rue de Lioux, 4, B-5030 Gembloux. Phone: (+32) 081/620.339; Fax: (+32) 081/620.349
6	Ministry of the Flemish Community, Institute for Agricultural & Fisheries Research (ILVO)	Belgium	NO					Martine Maes	martine.maes@ilvo.vlaanderen.be	Burg. Van Gansberghelaan 96 Mellebeke 9820 Belgium
7	Ministry of Agriculture & Forestry, National Service for Plant Protection (NSPP)	Bulgaria	YES	1	0	0	YES	Olia Karsajova	oliasarsajova@bv.bg	Plant Protection Institute; 2230, Kostinbrod; Bulgaria Tel: +359 72168801
	Ministry of Agriculture and Food / Executive Forest Agency	Bulgaria		0	0	1	n.r.	Elena Petrova	angeloreli@bv.bg	Plant Protection Institute; 2230, Kostinbrod; Bulgaria Tel: +359 72168802
	Ministry of Education, Youth and Science/ Bulgarian Academy of Sciences/ Institute of Forestry	Bulgaria		0	0	1	n.r.	**	**	
8	Ministry of Agriculture, National Agency for Agricultural Research (MZe)	Czech Rep	NO					Ladislav Jerabek	ladislav.jerabek@mze.cz	Ladislav Jerabek Dipl. Eng. Ministry of Agriculture CR, 17010 - Dpt. Research, Education and Extension phone: +420 221 812 252 e-mail: ladislav.jerabek@mze.cz
9	The Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation – DASTI	Denmark	YES	1	1	0	YES	Per Mogensen	permi@f.dk	The Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation – DASTI
	Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries, Danish Food Industry Agency (DFIA)	Denmark		1	0	0	n.r.	Bjarne Thomsen		Dept. of Integrated Pest Management; Faculty of Agricultural Sciences; Aarhus University Forsøgsvej 1; DK-4200 Slagelse; Tel.: +45 8999 3671
10	Ministry of Agriculture, Research and Development Department (MARDOD)	Estonia	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Kylli Kaare	kylli.kaare@agri.ee	Head of Research and Development Department, Ministry of Agriculture Republic of Estonia Telefon 625 6554
11	Ministry of Agriculture & Forestry (MMM-F)	Finland	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Tuula Mäki-Valkama	Tuula.Maki-Valkama@mmm.fi	Unit of Plant Production and Animal Nutrition, Department of Food and Health, Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Finland; tel. +358-9-16052692, GSM +358-40-5222651
12	Ministry of Agriculture, Food, Fisheries & Rural Policy, General Food Directorate (MAAP-DGAL)	France	NO					David Caffer	david.caffer@agriculture.gouv.fr	7 rue Jean Dumérès 49044 Angers Cedex 01, France
13	National Institute of Agronomic Research (INRA)	France	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Thierry Candresse	thierry.candresse@bordeaux.inra.fr	UMR GDZP, IBVM, BP81, INRA, 33883 Villenave d'Ornon Cedex France
	Julius Kühn Institute (JKI)	Germany	YES	1	1	0	NO	Silke Steinmoeller	silke.steinmoeller@jki.bund.de	Stahnsdorfer Damm 51; D-14532 Kleinmachnow; Tel: 033203 / 48-259
14	The Federal Agency for Agriculture and Food (BLE)	Germany		1	1	0	n.r.	Elke Seegau	ELKE.SAIGAU@ble.de	Deichmanns Aue 29, Bonn 53179, Germany
16	Benaki Phytosanitological Institute (BPI)	Greece	YES	???	0	0	YES	Irene Vlioutoglou	ivlioutoglou@bpi.gr	Stefanou Delta street, 8, 14561 Athens, Greece
	Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Directorate of Forest Protection			0	0	1	n.r.			
17	Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (DAFF) Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (DAFF)	Ireland	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	James Choiseul Dale Crammond	James.Choiseul@agriculture.gov.ie ???	Maynooth Business Campus Maynooth Co. Kildare Ireland
18	Ministry of Agricultural & Forestry Policy (MPAFAF)	Italy	NO					Alberto Masci Maria Montedoro	a.masci@politicheagricole.gov.it m.montedoro@politicheagricole.gov.it	Via XX Settembre 20 Roma 00187 Italy Via XX Settembre 20 Roma 00187 Italy
19	Agricultural Research Council (CRA)	Italy	NO					Fidalma Dandrea	fidalma.dandrea@entecra.it	CRA-PAV; Consiglio per la Ricerca e la Sperimentazione in Agricoltura; Centro di Ricerca per la Patologia Vegetale; Via C.G. Bertero 22/J-00156 Rome Italy; Tel.: +390682070329
		Italy						Luca Riccioni	luca.riccioni@entecra.it	CRA-PAV; Consiglio per la Ricerca e la Sperimentazione in Agricoltura; Centro di Ricerca per la Patologia Vegetale; Via C.G. Bertero 22/J-00156 Rome Italy; Tel.: +390682070329
		Italy						Sauro Simoni	sauro.simoni@entecra.it	C.R.A. - Istituto Sperimentale per la Zoologia Agraria via di Lanciola 12/a 50125 Firenze Italy
20	Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)	Lithuania	NO					Zita Duchovskiene Dalia Abraityte	ZitaD@zum.lt abraita@zum.lt	Dr. Zita Duchovskiene and Dalia Abraityte are replacing Jurgita Liaugminė [jurgita@zum.lt] while she is on maternity leave. 19 Gediminas av. 01103 Vilnius, Lithuania
	Plant Health Directorate (PHD), Ministry for Resources and Rural Affairs, Malta	Malta	YES	1	1	0	YES	Marica Gatt	marica.gatt@gov.mt	
	Malta Centre for Science and Technology (MCST)	Malta		0	0	1	n.r.			

21	Ministry of Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Innovation, Department of Knowledge and Innovation.	Netherlands	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Eric Regouin	e.j.m.regouin@minlnv.nl	Department of Knowledge Policy, Ministry of Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Innovation; postal address: Postbus 20401, 2500 EK Den Haag, Nederland; street address: Prins Clauslaan 8, 2595 AJ Den Haag, Nederland; phone: +31 (0)70 - 757 3151 and (mobile)
21	Ministry of Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Innovation, Department of Agrochains and Fisheries.							Hans Smolders	j.w.j.smolders@minlnv.nl	Department of Knowledge Policy, Ministry of Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Innovation; postal address: Postbus 20401, 2500 EK Den Haag, Nederland; street address: Prins Clauslaan 8, 2595 AJ Den Haag, Nederland; phone: +31 (0)70 - 757 3151 and (mobile)
22	Food & Consumer Product Safety authority, nVWA	Netherlands	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Paul van den Boogert	p.h.j.f.van.den.boogert@minlnv.nl	Prinses Beatrixlaan 2, 'S-Gravenhage, The Netherlands; PO Box: 19506, 2500 CM, The Netherlands; Phone: + 31 (0) 70 4484087
	Food & Consumer Product Safety authority, nVWA							Marlette Edema	m.j.edema@minlnv.nl	Prinses Beatrixlaan 2, 'S-Gravenhage, The Netherlands; PO Box: 19506, 2500 CM, The Netherlands; Phone: + 31 (0) 70 4484088
	Norwegian Forest and Landscape Institute	Norway	YES	0	0	1	n.r.	Halvor Solheim	halvor.solheim@stogogardskap.no	
23	Instituto Nacional de Recursos Biológicos (INRB)	Portugal	YES	1	0	0	n.r.	Maria Leonor Cruz	leonor.cruz@inrb.pt, amelia.lopes@inrb.pt	Instituto Nacional de Recursos Biológicos, IP / L-INIA Unidade de Investigação de Protecção de Plantas (UIPP) Laboratório de Fitobacteriologia Edifício I - Tapada do Aljido 1349 - 018 Lisboa Tel.: (+351) 21 361 32 84 Fax: (+351) 21 446 40 29
	Portuguese Research Funding Agency (FCT)	Portugal	YES	?	?	1	n.r.			
24	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (MAFF)	Slovenia	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Jana Erjavec	jana.erjavec@gov.si	Dunajska 58, Ljubljana SI-1000, Slovenia
	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (MAFF)							Janez Zafrañ	???	
25	Ministry of Education and Science, National Institute of Agricultural Research (INIA)	Spain	NO					Pilar Sabuquillo	mpsc@inia.es	Ctra. de la Corona, km 7.5 Madrid 28040 Spain
		Spain						Ananbel de la Pena	ananabel.delapena@inia.es	Ctra. de la Corona, km 7.5 Madrid 28040 Spain
	The Swedish Research Council for Environment, Agricultural Sciences and Spatial Planning. (Formas).	Sweden	YES	1	1	0	n.r.	Jan Svensson	jan.svensson@formas.se	P.O. Box 1206, SE-111 82 STOCKHOLM
26	Federal Office of Agriculture, Division of Research & Extension (FOAG)	Switzerland	YES	1	0	0	YES	Gabriele Schachermeyr	gabriele.schachermeyr@blw.admin.ch	
	Federal Office for the Environment FOEN Federal Department of the Environment, Transport and Communications DETEC	Switzerland		0	0	1	n.r.	??	??	
27	Ministry of Agriculture, Food & Rural Affairs, DG of Agriculture Research (MARA-SDAR)	Turkey	YES	1	0	0	YES	Alev Burcak	sburcak@tagem.gov.tr	PO Box 78 Istanbul Yolu Uzeri, Bagciot Cad 06171 Ankara Turkey
	Ministry of Forestry and Water Affairs, General Directorate of Forestry	Turkey		0	0	1	n.r.			
1	Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, Food & Environment Research Agency (DEFRA-FERA) - COORDINATOR	UK	YES	1	0	0	YES	Alan Inman	euphresco@fera.gsi.gov.uk	Sand Hutton, York YO41 1LZ
28	Forestry Commission, Forest Research (FR)	UK	NO					Joan Webber	joan.webber@forestry.gsi.gov.uk	Alice Holt Lodge, Farnham, GU10 4LH, UK
29	Scottish Government, Science and Advice for Scottish Agriculture (SASA)	UK: Scotland	YES	0	0	0	YES	David Kenyon	David.Kenyon@sasa.gsi.gov.uk	Dr David Kenyon, Science and Advice for Scottish Agriculture (SASA), Roddinglaw road, Edinburgh, EH12 9FJ, UK T: +44(0)131 244 8878 / F: +44(0)131 244 8987
	Agri-Food & Biosciences Institute, A.F.B.I., N. Ireland.	UK-Northern Ireland	YES	1	0	0	YES	Ailstair R. McCracken	ailstair.mccracken@afbini.gov.uk	Applied Plant Science & Biometrics Division, Agri-Food & Biosciences Institute, 18A Newforge Lane, Belfast BT9 5FX, N. Ireland, UK
	Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (DARD)	UK-Northern Ireland		0	0	1	n.r.			
30	Institute of Plant Protection Ukrainian Academy of Agrarian Sciences (IPP UAAS)	Ukraine	YES	1	0	0	YES	Ul'ya Pylypenko	pylypenko@mail.ru	33, Vesikivskaya Str., Institute of Plant Protection NAAS, Kiev, 04215, Ukraine
	Ukrainian Research Institute of Forestry & Forest Melioration named after G.M.Vysotsky, Ukraine	Ukraine		0	0	0	YES	Valentyna Meshkova	valentynameshkova@gmail.com, vsm@wiffm.org.ua	Ukrainian Research Institute of Forestry & Forest Melioration, Laboratory of Forest Protection 61024, Pushkinska, 86, Kharkov, Ukraine
	State Forest Resources Agency, Kyiv	Ukraine		0	0	1	n.r.	??	??	State Forest Resources Agency, Kyiv, Shota Rustaveli str. 9a
31	All-Russian Plant Quarantine Centre (FGU VNIKR)	Russian Federation	YES	1	1	0	YES	Nataliya Sherokolova	natalia_sh@mail.ru	140150, Russia, Moscow oblast, Luberetsky region, Bykovo, Pogranichnaya str. 32 ; Phone: +79039619068 Fax: +7 (495)2257904
	All-Russian Plant Quarantine Centre (FGU VNIKR)							Oleg Kulich	vnikr@mail.ru	
	All-Russian Institute of Forestry and Forestry Mechanization	Russian Federation		0	0	1	n.r.	Yuri Ivanovich Gninenko	vnilm@mail.ru	ВНИИЛМ.рф
	N replies	27 countries (UK: Scotland and Northern Ireland separately counted)	23 countries (85% replied) / 23 funders replied (is not necessarily congruent)	24 funders with mandate to fund Plant Health Research in AGRICULTURE	15 funders with mandate to fund Plant Health Research BOTH in AGRICULTURE & FORESTRY	11 funders with mandate to fund Plant Health Research ONLY in FORESTRY	YES (additional inclusion of institution with FundMandRes PUH forestry in EUPHRESKO 2 recommended)			

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F2 EUPH Forestry WP5 NPPOs forestry phytosanitary threats

Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary forestry threats according to NPPO's in EUPHRESCO partner sorted after importance by each NPPO

	Austria	Belgium	Den mark	Fin land	Ger many	Lithu ania	Latvia	Norway	Poland	Portu gal	Russia	Slove nia	Sweden	Switzerl .
INSECTS														
<i>Agrilus planipennis</i>	xxx	xxx	xx			xxx		xxx			xxx		xxx	xx
<i>Agrilus sinuatus</i>	x		xxx											
<i>Agrilus anxius</i>	x	xxx	xx	xxx				xxx					xxx	
<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	xxx	xxx	xxx		xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx		xxx			xxx	xx
<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	xxx	xxx	xxx		xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx		xx			xxx	xxx
<i>Aprocerus leucopoda</i>	xx				xxx				xxx			xx		xx
<i>Dendrolimus sibiricus</i>	x	xxx									xxx			
<i>Dendroctonus frontalis</i>	x													xx
<i>Dendroctonus ponderosae</i>	x			xxx										xx
<i>Dendroctonus rufipennis</i>	x													xx
<i>Diaphania (Glyphodes perspectalis)</i>	xxx													xx
<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	xxx	xxx			xxx					xxx		xxx		xxx
<i>Gonipterus scutellatus</i>										xxx				
<i>Hylobius spp</i>	x								xxx					
<i>Ips duplicatus</i>	xx													xx
<i>Ips typographus</i>	x								xxx					
<i>Leptoglossus occidentalis</i>	xx									xx		xx		
<i>Lymantria monacha</i>	x								xxx					

	Austria	Belgium	Den mark	Fin land	Ger many	Lithu ania	Latvia	Norway	Poland	Portu gal	Russia	Slove nia	Sweden	Switzerl .
<i>Monochamus</i> spp. (non European)	XX	xxx				xxx						xxx		
<i>Monochamus galloprovincialis</i>										xxx				
<i>Myzocallis walshii</i>	X											XX		
<i>Phyllonorycter issikii</i>	XX											XX		
<i>Physokermes inopinatus</i>	XX			xxx										
<i>Platypus cylindrus</i>										xxx				
<i>Thaumetopoea processionea</i>	XX			xxx	xxx					xxx				
<i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i>	XX	xxx										xx		
NEMATODES														
<i>Bursaphelenchus mucronatus</i>	xxx										xxx			
<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	xxx	xxx			xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx		xxx		xxx	xxx	xxx
FUNGI														
<i>Biscogniauxia mediterranea</i>										xxx				
Botryosphaeriaceae <i>Botryosphaeria dothidea</i>	X													xxx
<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	X	xxx				xxx								
<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata f.sp. platani</i>	XX												xxx	
<i>Cronartium flaccidum/ Peridermium pini</i>	X											xxx		
<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	XX				xxx			X					xxx	
<i>Cryptostroma corticale</i>	X				xxx									
<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	xxx						xx							
<i>Diplodia pinea</i>	xxx							X		xx		Xxx		

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F3 EUPH Forestry WP5 importance forestry phytosanitary threats

Lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary forestry threats according to NPPO's in EUPHRESCO partner sorted after importance by each NPPO

	No. countries listed the pest	Crop sector	Forestry crops
<i>INSECTS</i>			Grey coloured: not listed in Annexes 2000/29/EC
			Yellow coloured: not listed in Annex 2000/29/EC, but listed in the EPPO Alert List of September 2011
<i>Agilus planipennis</i> (emerald ash borer)	8	Forestry, landscape and nurseries	Ash
<i>Agilus sinuatus</i> (hawthorn jewel beetle)	2	Plants for planting (Nurseries)	Hawthorn
<i>Agilus anxius</i> (bronze birch borer)	6	Forestry, landscape and nurseries	Birch
<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	10	Plants for planting (nurseries), forestry, landscape, public green	Various deciduous
<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	10	Plants for planting (nurseries), forestry, landscape, public green	Various deciduous
<i>Aprocerus leucopoda</i>	5	Forestry, landscape	Ulmus
<i>Dendrolimus sibiricus</i>	3		
<i>Dendroctonus frontalis</i>	2		
<i>Dendroctonus ponderosae</i>	3		
<i>Dendroctonus rufipennis</i>	2		
<i>Diaphania (Glyphodes perspectalis)</i>	2		

	No. countries	Crop sector	Forestry crops
<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	6	Forestry, landscape and nurseries	Castanea sativa, Various deciduous
<i>Hylobius spp</i>	2		
<i>Ips duplicatus</i>	2		B (Protected zones)
<i>Ips typographus</i>	2		B (Protected zones)
<i>Leptoglossus occidentalis</i>	3		
<i>Lymantria monacha</i>	2	Forestry	Pinus
<i>Monochamus</i> spp. (non European)	4		
<i>Monochamus galloprovincialis</i>	1	Forestry	Pinus
<i>Myzocallis walshii</i>	2		
<i>Phyllonorycter issikii</i>	2		
<i>Physokermes inopinatus</i>	2		
<i>Thaumetopoea processionea</i>	4		High allergic potential – problem for public health
<i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i>	3		
NEMATODES			
<i>Bursaphelenchus mucronatus</i>	2		
<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	10	Forestry	Conifers, Pinus
FUNGI			
<i>Biscogniauxia mediterranea</i>	1		
Botryosphaeriaceae <i>Botryosphaeria dothidea</i>	2		
<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	3		IV / A1
<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i> f.sp. <i>platani</i>	2		IV / A1

	No. countries	Crop sector	Forestry crops
<i>Cronartium flaccidum/ Peridermium pini</i>	2		
<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	4		IV / A1
<i>Cryptostroma corticale</i>	2	Public green, Acer pseudoplatanus	Spores with allergic potential
<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	2		
<i>Diplodia pinea</i>	4		
<i>Eutypella parasitica</i>	2		
<i>Gibberella circinata (Fusarium circinatum)</i>	7	Forestry	Pinus
<i>Heterobasidion annosum</i>	2		
<i>Hymenoscyphus pseudoalbidus (Chalara fraxinea)</i>	7	Forestry	Ash (methods to reduce impact)
<i>Lophodermium spp</i>	2		
<i>Macrodiplodiopsis desmazieresii</i>	2	Public green, Platanus	
<i>Mycosphaerella dearnessii (Scirrhia/Lecanosticta acicola)</i>	7	Forestry and nurseries	Pinus
<i>Mycosphaerella pini / Dothistroma pini</i>	9	Forestry and nurseries	Pinus
<i>Phytophthora lateralis</i>	8	Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc
<i>Phytoph. kernoviae</i>	8	Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc
<i>Phytoph. ramorum</i>	9	Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, Larix Kaempferi, etc
<i>Phytophthora hybrids (any other)</i>	3	Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc
<i>Sphaeropsis sapinea</i>	2	Pinus sylvestris	

BACTERIA			
	No. countries	Crop sector	Forestry crops
<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> <i>pv aesculus</i>	4	Public green, Aesculus	Way of infestation not known so far, but rapid spread; No coordinated control measures in NL, DE and UK
NEOPHYTA			
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>	2		
<i>Fallopia japonica</i>	2		
<i>Pueraria lobata</i>	2		
General problem		General topic	Specific description
the ecosystem	3	Climatic changes	Increased immigration of <i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> and its vectors; Increased occurrence of insect pests in northern regions e.g. <i>Thaumetopoea processionea</i> Increased occurrence or change of damaging potential of Phytophthora species e.g. <i>P. cinnamon</i> ; <i>Sphaeropsis sapinea</i> ; changes in host specialisation: <i>Diplodia pinea</i> , <i>Fusarium circinatum</i> ; <i>Peridermium harknessii</i>
Pests	3	Diagnostics	Rapid molecular diagnostic methods for quarantine pests; New developments in diagnostics; Applications of image analysis and computer vision in plant health inspections.
Pests	4	Complex studies: occurrence, epidemiology, morphology, early & rapid detection, damage estimation, control methods	Complex studies on quarantine diseases and pests; new insects harmful to forests in Balkan region/eastern part of Europe & their influence on forests; Risk to natural environment caused by increased import of <i>Vaccinium</i> species (<i>Dasineura oxycoccana</i> , <i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i> and <i>Blueberry scorch virus</i>); introduction of butterflies & sawflies; Early detection methods (rapid and targeted search of invasive alien harmful organisms) & control methods (integrated) for pests and for disease vectors

Forestry, landscape, gardening	3	Bio fuel/ bioenergy, wood packaging, bark	Wood chips imported from other continents. Wood packaging. Bark as component in growing media and for groundcover. Risk to natural environment through introduction of buprestid beetles, bark beetles, weevils, longhorn beetles
Forestry, landscape, gardening	2	Bonsai imports	Risk to natural environment through introduction of pests

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F4. EUPH Forestry WP5. List of Council Directive 2000/29/EC sorted after pest

Overview of harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Classification
1. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Forestry	Conifers	Insect	<i>Acleris</i> spp.	Annex I part A I
5. Ornamentals, cut flowers	Asters	Insect	<i>Amauromyza maculosa</i>	Annex I part A I
6. Agriculture	Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Glasshouse	Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Viticulture, fruit	Vine, fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
9. Forestry	Conifers	Insect	<i>Choristoneura</i> spp	Annex I part A I
10. Plants for planting	Rosea family	Insect	<i>Conotrachelus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
11. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica barberi</i>	Annex I part A I
12. Agriculture	Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
13. Agriculture	Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
14. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	Annex I part A I
15. Agriculture	Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I
16. Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	<i>Hirschmaniella</i> spp	Annex I part A I
17. Agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I

18. Fruit, Viticulture	Peach, vine	Nematode	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
19. Forestry	Conifers (vector of pine wood nematode)	Insect	<i>Monochamus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
20. Plant for planting	Palm (vector of palm lethal yellowing phytoplasma)	Insect	<i>Myndus crudus</i>	Annex I part A I
21. Agriculture	Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
22. Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Agriculture	Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
24. Forestry	Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus minutissimus</i>	Annex I part A I
25. Forestry	Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopithyophthorus pruinosis</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Forestry, plants for planting	Elm (vector of elm phloem necrosis phytoplasma)	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus luteolus</i>	Annex I part A I
27. Agriculture, glasshouse	Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
28. Agriculture	Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
29. Glasshouse, agriculture	Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I
30. Glasshouse, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
31. Fruit	Fruit	Insect	<i>Tephritidae</i> (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
32. Agriculture, fruit	Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematode	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
33. Agriculture, fruit	Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematode	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I

34. Viticulture	Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	Annex I part A I
35. Forestry	Oak	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	Annex I part A I
36. Forestry	Picea	Fungi	<i>Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli</i>	Annex I part A I
37. Forestry	Conifers	Fungi	<i>Cronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
38. Forestry	Conifers	Fungi	<i>Endocronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
39. Forestry	Larix	Fungi	<i>Guignardia laricina</i>	Annex I part A I
40. Fruit	Fruit, Juniperus	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
41. Forestry	Conifera	Fungi	<i>Inonotus weirii</i>	Annex I part A I
42. Forestry	Tsuga	Fungi	<i>Melampsora farlowii</i>	Annex I part A I
43. Fruit	Stonefruit	Fungi	<i>Monilinia fructicola</i>	Annex I part A I
44. Forestry	Larix	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella larici-leptolepsis</i>	Annex I part A I
45. Plants for planting	Populus	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella populorum</i>	Annex I part A I
46. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Phoma andina</i>	Annex I part A I
47. Fruit	Apple	Fungi	<i>Phyllosticta solitaria</i>	Annex I part A I
48. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex I part A I
49. Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
50. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	Annex I part A I
51. Agriculture	Cereals	Fungi	<i>Tilletia indica</i>	Annex I part A I
52. Agriculture	Cotton	Fungi	<i>Trechispora brinkmannii</i> (Phymatotrichopsis omnivora)	Annex I part A I
53. Forestry	Elms	Virus etc	Elm phloem necrosis mycoplasma	Annex I part A I
54. Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato viruses non European	Annex I part A I
55. Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc	Potato spindle tuber viroid	Annex I part A I
56. Agriculture, glasshouse, plants for	Soybean, tobacco, curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I

planting, fruit				
57. Fruit, viticulture	Stonefruit, apple, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
58. Fruit	Fruit and berries	Virus etc	Virus and phytoplasmas infecting <i>Cydonia</i> Mill., <i>Fragaria</i> L., <i>Malus</i> Mill., <i>Prunus</i> L., <i>Pyrus</i> L., <i>Ribes</i> L., <i>Rubus</i> L. og <i>Vitis</i> L.,	Annex I part A I
59. Glasshouse, agriculture	Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
60. Agriculture	Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
61. Agriculture	Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
62. Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
63. Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i>	Annex I part A II
64. Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Opogona sacchari</i>	Annex I part A II
65. Agriculture, fruit, forestry, plants for planting	Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
66. Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	Annex I part A II
67. Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Rhizoecus hibisci</i>	Annex I part A II
68. Glasshouse	Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	Annex I part A II
69. Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i>	Annex I part A II
70. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
71. Forestry, plants for planting	Populus, conifera	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
72. Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	Annex I part A II
73. Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	Annex I part A II
74. Fruit	Apple	Mycoplasma	Apple proliferation mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
75. Fruit	Stone fruit	Mycoplasma	Apricot chlorotic leafroll mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
76. Fruit	Pear	Mycoplasma	Pear decline mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
77. Glasshouse	Ornamental	Insect	<i>Aculops fuchsiae</i>	Annex II

				part A I
78. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Aleurocanthus</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
79. Fruit	Strawberry	Insect	<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i> and <i>A. signatus</i>	Annex II part A I
80. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Aonidiella citrina</i>	Annex II part A I
81. Agriculture	Rice	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A I
82. Plants for planting	Juniper	Insect	<i>Aschistonyx eppo</i>	Annex II part A I
83. Forestry	Conifera	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
84. Fruit	Pear	Insect	<i>Carposina niponensis</i>	Annex II part A I
85. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	Annex II part A I
86. Fruit	Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	Annex II part A I
87. Fruit, plants for planting	Pome, stonefruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I
88. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	Annex II part A I
89. Fruit	Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Grapholita inopinata</i>	Annex II part A I
90. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Hishomonus phycitis</i>	Annex II part A I
91. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Leucaspis japonica</i>	Annex II part A I
92. Agriculture	Brassicacae, clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I
93. Viticulture	Vine	Insect	<i>Margarodes</i> spp	Annex II part A I
94. Fruit	Pear	Insect	<i>Numonia pyrivorella</i>	Annex II part A I
95. Plants for planting	Juniper	Insect	<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	Annex II part A I
96. Forestry	Conifera	Insect	<i>Pissodes</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
97. Citrus fruit, glasshouse	Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
98. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Saissetia nigra</i>	Annex II part A I
99. Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Scirtothrips</i> 3 species	Annex II part A I
100. Forestry	Conifera	Insect	<i>Scolytidae</i> spp	Annex II

					part A I
101.	Fruit	Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Tachypterellus quadrigibbus</i>	Annex II part A I
102.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>	Annex II part A I
103.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Trioza erytrae</i>	Annex II part A I
104.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Unaspis citri</i>	Annex II part A I
105.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus greening bacterium	Annex II part A I
106.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus variegated chlorosis	Annex II part A I
107.	Agriculture	Maize	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia stewartii</i>	Annex II part A I
108.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i>	Annex II part A I
109.	Agriculture	Rice	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>Oryzae</i> & <i>orizicola</i>	Annex II part A I
110.	Fruit	Pome	Fungi	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Annex II part A I
111.	Fruit, plants for planting	Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I
112.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Apiosporina morbosa</i>	Annex II part A I
113.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Atropellis</i>	Annex II part A I
114.	Forestry, plants for planting	Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
115.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Cercoseptoria pini-densiflorae</i>	Annex II part A I
116.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Cercospora angolensis</i>	Annex II part A I
117.	Glasshouse	Camelia	Fungi	<i>Ciborinia camelliae</i>	Annex II part A I
118.	Fruit	Blueberry	Fungi	<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	Annex II part A I
119.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Elsinoe</i> spp	Annex II part A I
120.	Fruit, plants for planting	Date palm	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>albedines</i>	Annex II part A I
121.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	Annex II part A I
122.	Fruit	Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
123.	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	Annex II

					part A I
124.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia acicola</i>	Annex II part A I
125.	Fruit	Pear	Fungi	<i>Venturia nashicola</i>	Annex II part A I
126.	Agriculture	Beet	Virus etc.	Beet curly top virus	Annex II part A I
127.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Black raspberry latent virus	Annex II part A I
128.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Blight and blight-like	Annex II part A I
129.	Fruit	Coconut	Virus etc.	Cadang-cadang viroid	Annex II part A I
130.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Cherry leaf roll virus	Annex II part A I
131.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus mosaic virus	Annex II part A I
132.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A I
133.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Leprosis	Annex II part A I
134.	Fruit	Stonefruit	Virus etc.	Little cherry pathogen	Annex II part A I
135.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Naturally spreading psorosis	Annex II part A I
136.	Fruit	Coconut	Virus etc.	Palm lethal yellowing mycoplasm	Annex II part A I
137.	Fruit	Rubus	Virus etc.	Prunus necrotic ringspot virus	Annex II part A I
138.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Satsuma dwarf virus	Annex II part A I
139.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Tatter leaf virus	Annex II part A I
140.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Witches' broom	Annex II part A I
141.	Fruit	Strawberry	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A II
142.	Viticulture	Vine	Insect	<i>Daktulosphaira vitifoliae</i>	Annex II part A II
143.	Field, glasshouse	Ornamental bulbs	Insect	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>	Annex II part A II
144.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer haematoceps</i>	Annex II part A II
145.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer tenellus</i>	Annex II part A II
146.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus orientalis</i>	Annex II part A II

147.	Glasshouse	Ornamental cut flowers	Insect	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Annex II part A II
148.	Glasshouse	Pot plants	Insect	<i>Radopholus similis</i>	Annex II part A II
149.	Glasshouse, field	Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>	Annex II part A II
150.	Glasshouse, field	Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Lirimyza trifolii</i>	Annex II part A II
151.	Agriculture	Alfalfa	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> spp. <i>insidiosus</i>	Annex II part A II
152.	Glasshouse, field	Tomato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>michiganensis</i>	Annex II part A II
153.	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
154.	Glasshouse	Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia chrysanthemi</i> pv. <i>Dianthicola</i> (<i>Pectobacterium dianthicola</i>)	Annex II part A II
155.	Glasshouse	Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas caryophylli</i>	Annex II part A II
156.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>persicae</i>	Annex II part A II
157.	Vegetables	Beans	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>phaseoli</i>	Annex II part A II
158.	Fruit	Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>	Annex II part A II
159.	Glasshouse, filed	Tomato, chili	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesicatoria</i>	Annex II part A II
160.	Fruit	Strawberry	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
161.	Viticulture	Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylophilus ampelinus</i>	Annex II part A II
162.	Plants for planting	Platanus	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i> f. sp. <i>platani</i>	Annex II part A II
163.	Plant for planting, fruit	Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
164.	Glasshouse, field	Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Didymella ligulicola</i>	Annex II part A II
165.	Glasshouse	Cut flowers (carnation)	Fungi	<i>Phialophora cinerescens</i>	Annex II part A II
166.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Phoma tracheiphila</i>	Annex II part A II
167.	Fruit	Strawberry	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
168.	Plants for planting	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex II part A II

169.	Agriculture	Sunflower	Fungi	<i>Plasmopara halstedii</i>	Annex II part A II
170.	Glasshouse, field	Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>	Annex II part A II
171.	Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia pini</i>	Annex II part A II
172.	Vegetable	Hop	Fungi	<i>Verticillium albo-atrum</i>	Annex II part A II
173.	Vegetable	Hop	Fungi	<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>	Annex II part A II
174.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Arabidopsis mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
175.	Agriculture	Beet	Virus etc.	Beet leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II
176.	Glasshouse	Chrysanthemum	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid	Annex II part A II
177.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A II
178.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus vein enation woody gall	Annex II part A II
179.	Viticulture	Vine	Phytoplasma	Grapevine flavescence dorée MLO	Annex II part A II
180.	Glasshouse, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
181.	Fruit	Stonefruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus	Annex II part A II
182.	Agriculture	Potato	Phytoplasma	Potato stolbur mycoplasma	Annex II part A II
183.	Fruit	Strawberry, Rubus	Virus etc.	Raspberry ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
184.	Citrus fruit	Citrus	Virus etc.	<i>Spiroplasma citri</i>	Annex II part A II
185.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry crinkle virus	Annex II part A II
186.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry latent ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
187.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry mild yellow edge virus	Annex II part A II
188.	Fruit	Strawberry	Virus etc.	Tomato black ring virus	Annex II part A II
189.	Glasshouse, vegetables, agriculture	Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
190.	Glasshouse, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F5 EUPH Forestry WP5. List of Council Directive 2000/29/EC sorted after crop

Overview of harmful organisms listed in Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

Sorted after the crop sector and split on crops.

Agriculture

Potato			
1. Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
4. Potato	Nematod	<i>Nacobbus aberrans</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Potato	Insect	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	Annex I part A I
6. Potato	Insect	<i>Premnotrypes</i> spp. (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
7. Potato	Fungi	<i>Phoma andina</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Potato	Fungi	<i>Thecaphora solani</i>	Annex I part A I
9. Potato	Virus etc	Potato viruses non European	Annex I part A I
10. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
11. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
12. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
13. Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i>	Annex I part A II
15. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
16. Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>	Annex I part A II
17. Potato	Fungi	<i>Puccinia pittieriana</i>	Annex II part A I
18. Potato	Phytoplasma	Potato stolbur mycoplasma	Annex II part A II
19. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
Vegetables (field grown)			
20. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
21. Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
22. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I
24. Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I
25. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I

27. Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I
28. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
29. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
30. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
31. Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
32. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
33. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
34. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
35. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus,	Annex II part A II
Maize			
36. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
37. Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica barberi</i>	Annex I part A I
38. Vegetables, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	Annex I part A I
39. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata undecimpunctata</i>	Annex I part A I
40. Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	Annex I part A I
41. Vegetable, maize	Insect	<i>Heliothis zea</i>	Annex I part A I
42. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
43. Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	Annex I part A II
Cereals including rice			
44. Rice	Nematod	<i>Hirschmaniella</i> spp	Annex I part A I
45. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
46. Cereals	Fungi	<i>Tilletia indica</i>	Annex I part A I
47. Rice	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A I
Grasses, clover and alfalfa			
48. Grass, vegetables maize	Insect	<i>Anomala orientalis</i>	Annex I part A I
49. Grass, maize, rice	Insect	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Annex I part A I
50. Brassicas, clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I
51. Alfalfa	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> spp. <i>insidiosus</i>	Annex II part A II
Beets			
52. Beet	Virus etc.	Beet curly top virus	Annex II part A I
53. Beet	Virus etc.	Beet leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II

Sunflower, soybean, Tobacco, Brassica, Cotton			
54. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
55. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
56. Cotton	Fungi	<i>Trechispora brinkmannii</i> (Phymatotrichopsis omnivora)	Annex I part A I
57. Soybean, tobacco, curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
58. Brassicas, clover, grasses	Insect	<i>Listronotus bonariensis</i>	Annex II part A I
59. Sunflower	Fungi	<i>Plasmopara halstedii</i>	Annex II part A II
Fruit			
1. Peach, Vine	Nematod	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Fruit	Insect	<i>Tephritidae</i> (non-Europien)	Annex I part A I
3. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema americanum</i> (non European)	Annex I part A I
4. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Fruit, Juniperus	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Soybean, tobacco, curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
7. Stonefruit, pome, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
8. Fruit and berries	Virus etc	Virus and phytoplasmas infecting <i>Cydonia</i> Mill., <i>Fragaria</i> L., <i>Malus</i> Mill., <i>Prunus</i> L., <i>Pyrus</i> L., <i>Ribes</i> L., <i>Rubus</i> L. og <i>Vitis</i> L.,	Annex I part A I
9. Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
10. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II

11. Blueberry	Fungi	<i>Diaporthe vaccinii</i>	Annex II part A I
12. Coconut	Virus etc.	Cadang-cadang viroid	Annex II part A I
13. Coconut	Virus etc.	Palm lethal yellowing mycoplasma	Annex II part A I
14. Date palm	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>albedines</i>	Annex II part A I
15. Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I
16. Rubus	Virus etc.	Black raspberry latent virus	Annex II part A I
17. Rubus	Virus etc.	Cherry leaf roll virus	Annex II part A I
18. Rubus	Virus etc.	Prunus necrotic ringspot virus	Annex II part A I
19. Pear	Mycoplasma	Pear decline mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
20. Pear	Insect	<i>Carposina niponensis</i>	Annex II part A I
21. Pear	Insect	<i>Numonia pyrivorella</i>	Annex II part A I
22. Pome	Fungi	<i>Phyllosticta solitaria</i>	Annex I part A I
23. Pome	Mycoplasma	Apple proliferation mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
24. Pome	Fungi	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Annex II part A I
25. Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
26. Pome	Fungi	<i>Guignardia piricola</i>	Annex II part A I
27. Pome, stone fruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I
28. Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Grapholita inopinata</i>	Annex II part A I
29. Pome, stonefruit	Insect	<i>Tachypterellus quadrigibbus</i>	Annex II part A I
30. Vine, stone fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
31. Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Monilinia fruticicola</i>	Annex I part A I
32. Stone fruit	Mycoplasma	Apricot chlorotic leafroll mycoplasma	Annex I part A II
33. Stone fruit	Fungi	<i>Apiosporina morbosa</i>	Annex II part A I
34. Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Little cherry pathogen	Annex II part A I
35. Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv <i>persicae</i>	Annex II part A II
36. Stone fruit	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>pruni</i>	Annex II part A II
37. Stone fruit	Virus etc.	Plum pox virus	Annex II part A II
38. Strawberry	Insect	<i>Anthonomus bisignifer</i> and <i>A. signatus</i>	Annex II part A I
39. Strawberry	Insect	<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	Annex II part A II
40. Strawberry	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
41. Strawberry	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i>	Annex II part A II
42. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Arabis mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
43. Strawberry, Rubus	Virus etc.	Raspberry ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
44. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry crinkle virus	Annex II part A II
45. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry latent ringspot virus	Annex II part A II
46. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Strawberry mild yellow edge virus	Annex II part A II
47. Strawberry	Virus etc.	Tomato black ring virus	Annex II part A II
48. Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	Annex II part A I
49. Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
50. Citrus	Insect	<i>Aonidiella citrina</i>	Annex II part A I
51. Citrus	Insect	<i>Diaphorina citri</i>	Annex II part A I
52. Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus lewisi</i>	Annex II part A I

53. Citrus	Insect	<i>Hishomonus phycitis</i>	Annex II part A I
54. Citrus	Insect	<i>Leucaspis japonica</i>	Annex II part A I
55. Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
56. Citrus	Insect	<i>Saissetia nigra</i>	Annex II part A I
57. Citrus	Insect	<i>Scirtothrips</i> 3 species	Annex II part A I
58. Citrus	Insect	<i>Toxoptera citricida</i>	Annex II part A I
59. Citrus	Insect	<i>Trioza erytrae</i>	Annex II part A I
60. Citrus	Insect	<i>Unaspis citri</i>	Annex II part A I
61. Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus greening bacterium	Annex II part A I
62. Citrus	Bacteria	Citrus variegated chlorosis	Annex II part A I
63. Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i>	Annex II part A I
64. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Cercospora angolensis</i>	Annex II part A I
65. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Elsinoe</i> spp	Annex II part A I
66. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	Annex II part A I
67. Citrus	Virus etc.	Blight and blight-like	Annex II part A I
68. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus mosaic virus	Annex II part A I
69. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A I
70. Citrus	Virus etc.	Leprosis	Annex II part A I
71. Citrus	Virus etc.	Naturally spreading psorosis	Annex II part A I
72. Citrus	Virus etc.	Satsuma dwarf virus	Annex II part A I
73. Citrus	Virus etc.	Tatter leaf virus	Annex II part A I
74. Citrus	Virus etc.	Witches' broom	Annex II part A I
75. Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer haematoceps</i>	Annex II part A II
76. Citrus	Insect	<i>Circulifer tenellus</i>	Annex II part A II
77. Citrus	Insect	<i>Eotetranychus orientalis</i>	Annex II part A II
78. Citrus	Fungi	<i>Phoma tracheiphila</i>	Annex II part A II
79. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus tristeza virus	Annex II part A II
80. Citrus	Virus etc.	Citrus vein enation woody gall	Annex II part A II
81. Citrus	Virus etc.	<i>Spiroplasma citri</i>	Annex II part A II
Viticulture			
1. Vine, fruit (almond, prunes, apricot)	Insect	Cicadellidae (non European species), vector of <i>Pierce's disease</i> (caused by <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>)	Annex I part A I
2. Peach, vine	Nematod	<i>Longidorus diadecturus</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Stonefruit, apple, raspberry, grapevine	Virus etc	Tomato ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
5. Vine	Insect	<i>Margarodes</i> spp	Annex II part A I
6. Vine	Insect	<i>Daktulosphaira vitifoliae</i>	Annex II part A II
7. Vine	Bacteria	<i>Xylophilus ampelinus</i>	Annex II part A II
Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato) and field ornamentals			
1. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Opogona sacchari</i>	Annex I part A II
2. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Rhizoecus hibisci</i>	Annex I part A II

3. Ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera littoralis</i>	Annex I part A II
4. Ornamental	Insect	<i>Aculops fuchsiae</i>	Annex II part A I
5. Citrus, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Radopholus citrophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
6. Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Soybean, tobacco, curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
9. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
10. Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
11. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
12. Soybean, tobacco, curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
13. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
14. Ornamental bulbs	Insect	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>	Annex II part A II
15. Ornamental cut flowers	Insect	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Annex II part A II
16. Pot plants	Insect	<i>Radopholus similis</i>	Annex II part A II
17. Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>	Annex II part A II
18. Pot plants, cut flowers, leaf celery	Insect	<i>Lirimyza trifolii</i>	Annex II part A II
19. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus	Annex II part A II
20. Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia chrysanthemi</i> pv. <i>Dianthicola</i> (<i>Pectobacterium dianthicola</i>)	Annex II part A II
21. Cut flowers (carnation)	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas caryophylli</i>	Annex II part A II
22. Cut flowers (carnation)	Fungi	<i>Phialophora cinerescens</i>	Annex II part A II
23. Asters	Insect	<i>Amauromyza maculosa</i>	Annex I part A I
24. Camelia	Fungi	<i>Ciborinia camelliae</i>	Annex II part A I
25. Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Didymella ligulicola</i>	Annex II part A II
26. Chrysanthemum	Fungi	<i>Puccinia horiana</i>	Annex II part A II
27. Chrysanthemum	Virus etc.	Chrysanthemum stunt viroid	Annex II part A II
Tomato			
1. Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Vegetables	Insect	<i>Liriomyza sativae</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Potato, vegetables, flower ornamentals	Insect	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	Annex I part A I
5. Vegetables, ornamentals	Virus etc	Virus transmitted by <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Annex I part A I

6. Vegetables, tomato	Insect	<i>Spodoptera eridania</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Tomato, tobacco, strawberry, cherry (vector of tomato and tobacco ring spot virus and cherry rasp leaf virus)	Nematod	<i>Xiphinema californicum</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Tomato	Fungi	<i>Septoria lycopersici</i>	Annex I part A I
9. Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Annex I part A II
10. Tomato, chili	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i> pv. <i>vesicatoria</i>	Annex II part A II
11. Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	Annex II part A II
12. Pot plants, cut flowers, tomato, melon, potato, etc.	Virus etc.	Tomato spotted wilt virus	Annex II part A II
13. Tomato	Virus etc.	Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	Annex II part A II
Plants for planting			
1. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
2. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
3. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I
4. Rosea family	Insect	<i>Conotrachelus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
5. Fruit, Juniper	Fungi	<i>Gymnosporangium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Populus	Fungi	<i>Mycosphaerella populorum</i>	Annex I part A I
7. Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Soybean, tobacco, curcubitae, ornamentals, fruit	Virus etc	Tobacco ringspot virus	Annex I part A I
9. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera pallida</i>	Annex I part A II
10. Potato, plants for planting	Nematode	<i>Globodera rostochiensis</i>	Annex I part A II
11. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
12. Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	Annex I part A II
13. Populus, conifera	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Juniper	Insect	<i>Aschistonyx eppo</i>	Annex II part A I
15. Pome, stonefruit, ornamental deciduous plants	Insect	<i>Enarmonia packardi</i> and <i>E. prunivora</i>	Annex II part A I
16. Juniper	Insect	<i>Oligonychus perditus</i>	Annex II part A I
17. Hazel	Fungi	<i>Anisogramma anomala</i>	Annex II part A I
18. Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
19. Fruit trees, deciduous plants	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Annex II part A II
20. Platanus	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fimbriata</i> f. sp. <i>platani</i>	Annex II part A II
21. Sweet chestnut	Fungi	<i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>	Annex II part A II
22. Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	Annex II part A II

Forestry			
1. Acer	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis virescens</i>	Annex II part A I
2. Conifers	Insect	<i>Acleris</i> spp.	Annex I part A I
3. Conifers	Insect	<i>Choristoneura</i> spp	Annex I part A I
4. Conifers (vector of pine wood nematode)	Insect	<i>Monochamus</i> spp	Annex I part A I
5. Conifers	Fungi	<i>Cronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
6. Conifers	Fungi	<i>Endocronartium</i> spp (non European)	Annex I part A I
7. Conifera	Fungi	<i>Inonotus weirii</i>	Annex I part A I
8. Conifera	Insect	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Annex II part A I
9. Conifera	Insect	<i>Pissodes</i> spp.	Annex II part A I
10. Conifera	Insect	<i>Scolytidae</i> spp	Annex II part A I
11. Elms	Virus etc	Elm phloem necrosis mycoplasma	Annex I part A I
12. Elm (vector of elm phloem necrosis phytoplasma)	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus luteolus</i>	Annex I part A I
13. Elm, Acer, fruit, berries, grapevine, ornamentals	Insect	<i>Popillia japonica</i>	Annex I part A II
14. Larch	Fungi	<i>Guignardia laricina</i>	Annex I part A I
15. Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus</i>	Annex I part A I
16. Oak	Insect	<i>Pseudopityophthorus pruinosis</i>	Annex I part A I
17. Oak	Fungi	<i>Ceratocystis fagacearum</i>	Annex I part A I
18. Spruce	Fungi	<i>Chrysomyxa arctostaphyli</i>	Annex I part A I
19. Pine	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	Annex I part A II
20. Pine	Fungi	<i>Atropellis</i>	Annex II part A I
21. Pine	Fungi	<i>Cercoseptoria pini-densiflorae</i>	Annex II part A I
22. Pine	Fungi	<i>Scirrhia acicola</i>	Annex II part A I
23. Poplar, conifer	Fungi	<i>Melampsora medusae</i>	Annex I part A II
24. Tsuga	Fungi	<i>Melampsora farlowii</i>	Annex I part A I
25. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	Annex I part A I
26. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	Annex I part A I
27. Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora malasiaca</i>	Annex I part A I

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F6 EUPH Forestry WP5. Topic calls from EUPHRESCO-1 and EUPHRESCO-2 (2011) split on crops

Call title	Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
		Potato		
Potato brown rot and potato ring rot. Validation of methods that can be approved for use via control directives.	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> , <i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>
Potato cyst nematodes. Ringtesting methods for identification and resistance testing.	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	Potato cyst nematodes
<i>Dickeya</i> species in potato and management strategies.	Agriculture	Potato	Bacteria	<i>Dickeya dianthicola</i> , <i>D. solani</i>
Use of novel molecular methods to understand population diversity and its implication on disease management through use of resistant potato varieties	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	Potato cyst nematodes
Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for detection and identification of <i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i> in support of integrated plant protection strategies	Agriculture	Potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i>
Diagnostic methods for <i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i> , especially for pathotype identification	Agriculture	Potato	Fungi	<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>
Epidemiology and diagnosis of potato phytoplasmas and Candidatus <i>Liberibacter solanacearum</i> and their contribution to risk management	Agriculture	Potato	Mycoplasma	Potato mycoplasmas
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals , tomato, potato	Virus etc.	<i>Potato spindle tuber viroid</i> a.o. <i>pospiviroids</i>
		Various agricultural crops		
<i>Erwinia stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i> , maize bacterial blight.	Agriculture	Maize	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia stewartii</i> subsp.

Validation and ring testing of diagnostic methods.				<i>stewartii</i>
Validation of diagnostic methods for the detection and identification of whitefly transmitted viruses of regulatory or quarantine concern to EU.	Field crops, glasshouse	Ornamentals , vegetables	Viruses	Bean golden mosaic, Lettuce infectious yellows, Pepper mild tigré, Euphorbia mosaic a.o. viruses
		Tomato		
Assessment of the risk posed by ornamentals and tomato seeds infected by Pospiviroids to tomato crops and evaluation of Pospiviroid detection protocols for seed testing in tomato	Glasshouse, field crop	Tomato	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals , tomato, potato	Virus etc.	<i>Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids</i>
		Ornamentals		
Detection and Epidemiology of Pospiviroids	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals , tomato, potato	Virus etc.	<i>Potato spindle tuber viroid a.o. pospiviroids</i>
Validation of diagnostic methods for the detection and identification of whitefly transmitted viruses of regulatory or quarantine concern to EU.	Glasshouse, field crops	Ornamentals , vegetables	Viruses	Bean golden mosaic, Lettuce infectious yellows, Pepper mild tigré, Euphorbia mosaic a.o. viruses
		Fruit		
Interlaboratory comparison and validation of detection methods for phytoplasmas of phytosanitary concern in European orchards.	Fruit	Fruit trees	Phytoplasmas	Phytoplasmas
Evaluation of factors determining distribution, impact, detection and characterization of apple proliferation and other fruit tree phytoplasmoses in the European Community	Fruit	Fruit trees	Mycoplasm as	Apple proliferation and other fruit tree phytoplasmoses

Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for the detection of fire blight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>).	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, ornamental trees	Bacteria	<i>Malus, Pyrus, Crataegus, Cotoneaster a.o.</i>
Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight	Fruit and plants for planting	Fruit trees, hawthorn etc	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
Damage potential of <i>Drosophila suzukii</i> and development of phytosanitary measures	Fruit	Fruit trees, grapevine	Insect	<i>Drosophila suzukii</i>
		Vine		
Evaluation of the risk of spread of <i>Scaphoideus titanus</i> , the vector of grapevine flavescence dorée, with commercial grapevine propagation material.	Viticulture	Vine	Insect	<i>Scaphoideus titanus</i>
Epidemiological studies on reservoir hosts and potential vectors of Grapevine flavescence dorée (GFD) and validation of different diagnostic procedures for GFD	Viticulture	Vine	Mycoplasm a	Grapevine flavescence dorée
		Plants for planting		
Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for the detection of fire blight (<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>).	Fruit, plants for planting	Fruit trees, ornamental trees	Bacteria	<i>Malus, Pyrus, Crataegus, Cotoneaster a.o.</i>
Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight	Fruit and plants for planting	Fruit trees, hawthorn etc	Bacteria	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
Risk management for the EC listed <i>Anoplophora</i> species, <i>A. chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>
Current and emerging <i>Phytophthora</i> : research supporting risk assessment and risk management	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Fungi	<i>P. ramorum, kernoviae, lateralis</i>
		Forestry		
Phytosanitary Efficacy of Kiln Drying.	Forestry	Various trees	Various	Various
Risk management for the EC listed <i>Anoplophora</i> species, <i>A. chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i> and <i>A. glabripennis</i>
Current and emerging <i>Phytophthora</i> : research supporting risk assessment and risk management	Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Fungi	<i>P. ramorum, kernoviae, lateralis</i>

		Other topics		
Strategies for Ambrosia control.	Agriculture	Various	Weed plant	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>
Whole genomic amplification methods	All	All	Various	Various
Management of invasive alien aquatic/riparian weeds.	None	None	Plant	Various

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F7 EUPH Forestry WP5. EPPO Alert List

Overview of harmful organisms listed in EPPO's Alert List (last updated September 2011).

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species
Tomato	Tomato		
1. Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Insect	<u><i>Keiferia lycopersicella</i></u>
2. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<u><i>Pepino mosaic virus</i></u>
3. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<u><i>Tomato apical stunt pospiviroid</i></u>
4. Agriculture, glasshouse	Tomato	Virus etc.	<u><i>Tomato torrado virus</i></u>
5. Potato, agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	<u><i>Leucinodes orbonalis</i></u>
6. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato, chilli, sweet pepper	Bacteria	' <u><i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i></u> '
Potato	Potato		
7. Potato, agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	<u><i>Leucinodes orbonalis</i></u>
8. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato, chilli, sweet pepper	Bacteria	' <u><i>Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum</i></u> '
9. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<u><i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i></u>
Maize	Maize		
10. Agriculture	Maize	Bacteria	<u><i>Spiroplasma kunkelii</i></u>
11. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<u><i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i></u>
12. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<u><i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i></u>
13. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<u><i>Halyomorpha halys</i></u>

Other agriculture crops	Other agriculture crops		
14. Agriculture	Sunflower	Insect	<i>Strauzia longipennis</i>
15. Agriculture, fruit	Citrus, stone fruit, cotton, maize	Insect	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>
16. Agriculture, glasshouse, fruit	Cereals, vegetables, sunflower, maize, potato	Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne ethiopica</i>
17. Agriculture, glasshouse	Lettuce	Fungi	<i>Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. lactucae</i>
Glasshouse	Glasshouse		
18. Glasshouse	Ornamental pot plant	Fungi	<i>Melampsora euphorbiae</i>
Fruit	Fruit		
19. Citrus fruit, agriculture	Citrus, melon	Bacteria	<i>Acidovorax citrulli</i>
20. Fruit	Ficus, morus	Insect	<i>Psacotheta hilaris</i>
21. Fruit	Kiwi	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae pv. actinidiae</i>
22. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>
23. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i>
Plants for planting	Plants for planting		
24. Plants for planting	Horse chestnut	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas syringae pv. aesculi</i>
25. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<i>Chalara fraxinea</i>
26. Forestry, plants for planting	Beech, rhododendron	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora kernoviae</i>
27. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum, oak	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>
28. Fruit, citrus fruit, plants for planting, agriculture	Citrus, pome, stonefruit, maize, soybean, ornamental trees & shrubs etc.	Insect	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>
29. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<i>Oemona hirta</i>

Forestry	Forestry		
30. Forestry	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	Insect	<u><i>Chrysophtharta bimaculata</i></u>
31. Forestry	Oak species	Insect	<u><i>Enaphalodes rufulus</i></u>
32. Forestry	Pine	Fungi	<u><i>Phytophthora pinifolia</i></u>
33. Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<u><i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i></u>
34. Forestry, plants for planting	Ash	Fungi	<u><i>Chalara fraxinea</i></u>
35. Forestry, plants for planting	Beech, rhododendron	Fungi	<u><i>Phytophthora kernoviae</i></u>
36. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, Camellia, Viburnum, oak	Fungi	<u><i>Phytophthora ramorum</i></u>
37. Forestry, fruit, plants for planting	Citrus, many trees, stonefruit a.o. fruits	Insect	<u><i>Oemona hirta</i></u>

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F8 EUPH Forestry WP5. EU Emergency measures. List of EU's emergency measures on Q-pests

Crop sector	Crops	Organism group	Species	Comments
191. Plants for planting, forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	
192. Agriculture	Maize	Insect	<i>Diabrotica virgifera</i>	
193. Glasshouse, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	<i>Thrips palmi</i>	As regards Thailand
194. Plants for planting, forestry	Rhododendron, deciduous trees, etc	Fungi	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>	
195. Agriculture	Potato	Virus etc.	Potato spindle tuber viroid	
196. Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	
197. Agriculture, glasshouse	Potato, tomato	Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i>	Import from Egypt
198. Forestry	Pinus	Fungi	<i>Gibberella circinata</i>	
199. Forestry	Conifera	Nematode	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i> pine wood nematode	
200. Fruit	Sweet chestnut	Insect	<i>Dryocosmus kuriphilus</i>	
201. Glasshouse, field	Tomato	Virus etc.	Pepino mosaic virus	

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F9 EUPH Forestry WP5. Interceptions. Overview of interceptions per pest of harmful organisms in EU 2007-09

Sorted after number of interceptions

Crop sector	Crop	Organism group	Pest	2007	2008	2009
Conglomerated data for selected groups of organisms						
Glasshouse	Ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	White flies, <i>Bemisia</i>	202	302	243
Fruit	Fruit	Insect	Fruit flies, <i>Tephritidae</i> , non-European	389	292	286
Glasshouse, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	Thrips, <i>Thrips palmi</i>	289	307	306
Glasshouse, agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Leafminers, <i>Liriomyza</i>	139	271	318
Agriculture, glasshouse	Vegetables, tomato, grass, maize, rice, potato, ornamental flower/ ornamental flower	Insect/insect	Spodoptera/Helicoverpa	417	334	104
Other organisms						
Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	66	149	74
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	<i>Sinoxylon</i> sp. (not on the q-list)	36	22	56
Agriculture	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	Leucinodes orbonalis (on EPPO's Alert list)	18	37	26
Fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	Xanthomonas axonopodis pv. citri (EPPO quarantine pest)	28	25	25
Agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Agromyzidae (<i>Liriomyza</i> spp. a.o. leaf miners)	51	7	12
Glasshouse	Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	Aleyrodidae (<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> a.o. hemipteras)	60	3	5
Forestry	Larch tree	Fungi	Guignardia sp.	42	4	3
Plants for	Palms	Insect	Rhynchophorus ferrugineus	36	9	-

planting						
Plants for planting	Box tree	Insect	Diaphania indica (box tree moth)	12	23	9
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	Bostrichidae (wood borer)	15	19	8
Fruit	Macadamia nuts	Insect	Chryptophlebia leucotreta	13	3	22
Forestry	Conifers	Insect	Scolytidae (<i>Gnathotrichus sulcatus</i>)	12	19	4
Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	Meloidogyne sp.	3	17	14
Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Virus	Pepino mosaic virus	11	14	6
Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	Cerambycidae (<i>Anoplophora</i> spp.)	13	11	6
Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	Hirschmanniella sp.	11	10	6

Sorted after crop sector

Crop sector	Crop	Organism group	Pest	2007	2008	2009
Conglomerated data for selected groups of organisms						
Glasshouse	Ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	White flies, <i>Bemisia</i>	202	302	243
Fruit	Fruit	Insect	Fruit flies, <i>Tephritidae</i> , non-European	389	292	286
Glasshouse, agriculture	Flower ornamentals, vegetables	Insect	Thrips, <i>Thrips palmi</i>	289	307	306
Glasshouse, agriculture	Vegetables	Insect	Leafminers, <i>Liriomyza</i>	139	271	318
Glasshouse, agriculture	Vegetables, tomato, grass, maize, rice, potato, ornamental flower/ ornamental flower	Insect/insect	Spodoptera/Helicoverpa	417	334	104
Other organisms						
Agriculture	Potato, tomato a.o. solanaceous	Insect	Leucinodes orbonalis (on EPPO's Alert list)	18	37	26
Agriculture	Potato, cereals, maize, vegetables	Nematode	Meloidogyne sp.	3	17	14
Agriculture	Rice	Nematode	Hirschmanniella sp.	11	10	6

Agriculture, glasshouse	Vegetables	Insect	Agromyzidae (<i>Liriomyza</i> spp. a.o. leaf miners)	51	7	12
Glasshouse, agriculture	Tomato	Virus	Pepino mosaic virus	11	14	6
Glasshouse	Glasshouse ornamentals and vegetables	Insect	Aleyrodidae (hemipteras other than <i>Bemesia tabaci</i>)	60	3	5
Fruit	Citrus	Fungi	<i>Guignardia citricarp</i>	66	149	74
Fruit	Citrus	Bacteria	<i>Xanthomonas axonopodis</i> pv. <i>citri</i> (EPPO quarantine pest)	28	25	25
Fruit	Macadamia nuts	Insect	<i>Chryptophlebia leucotreta</i>	13	3	22
Plants for planting	Palms	Insect	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	36	9	-
Plants for planting	Box tree	Insect	<i>Diaphania indica</i> (box tree moth)	12	23	9
Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	<i>Sinoxylon</i> sp. (not on the q-list)	36	22	56
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Forestry	Wood packaging	Insect	Bostrichidae (wood borer)	15	19	8
Forestry	Conifers	Insect	Scolytidae (<i>Gnathotrichus sulcatus</i>)	12	19	4
Forestry	Various deciduous	Insect	Cerambycidae (<i>Anoplophora</i> spp.)	13	11	6

EUPHRESCO-2 WP5 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex 10 EUPH Forestry WP5 FP6 and FP7 plant health Forestry projects

List of EU Frame Work Programme (FP) 6 and FP7 forestry plant health projects and forestry plant health related projects

FP6 and FP7 FORESTRY PLANT HEALTH RESEARCH PROJECTS

	Description	Sector	Plant Health Risk
FP6			
PORT CHECK	DEVELOPMENT OF GENERIC ON SITE MOLECULAR DIAGNOSTICS FOR EU QUARANTINE PESTS AND PATHOGENS: Development and evaluation of real-time PCR assays for a number of key harmful organisms, including <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> and pinewood nematode; and transfer these assays to field portable real-time PCR platforms which were originally developed for bio-warfare and bio-terrorism applications.	Forestry, nurseries, landscape, public green	PINE WOOD NEMATODE, (<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>), <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>
EUPHRESCO	Coordination of European Phytosanitary (Statutory Plant Health) Research	All	all
RAPRA	Risk analysis for <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> , a newly recognized pathogen threat to Europe and the cause of Sudden Oak Death in the USA	Forestry, nurseries, landscape, public green	<i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>
FP7			
ISEFOR	INCREASING SUSTAINABILITY OF EUROPEAN FORESTS: MODELLING FOR SECURITY AGAINST INVASIVE PESTS AND PATHOGENS UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE: ISEFOR addresses the problems that will arise from: (1) climate change impacts on forest ecosystem vitality; (2) increasing threats from alien invasive pests and pathogens; and (3) changing threats from indigenous pests and pathogens, or alien species already established in Europe. ISEFOR research will focus on: Defining the threats to European forest ecosystems, based on current knowledge of the pest and pathogens known as potentially invasive, and the host plants attacked by these organisms; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing molecular techniques for detection and diagnosis of 	Forestry, nurseries, landscape, public green	all

	<p>potentially problematic alien organisms at ports of entry, and along pathways of dispersal in collaboration with PRATIQUÉ (https://secure.fera.defra.gov.uk/pratique/index.cfm) and QBOL (http://www.qbol.wur.nl/UK/);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critically analysing the plant nursery trade, to develop a quantified approach to pest risk assessment and determine if post-entry quarantine for commodities within this pathway provides an effective step for reducing risks linked to cryptic or dormant pest organisms; • Developing software to allow modelling of the probabilities of invasion, spread and impact of alien pathogens under climate change conditions. 		
<p>REPHRAME</p>	<p>DEVELOPMENT OF IMPROVED METHODS FOR DETECTION, CONTROL AND ERADICATION OF PINE WOOD NEMATODE IN SUPPORT OF EU PLANT HEALTH POLICY</p> <p>Europes pine forests are a valuable economic, social and environmental resource under threat from the introduction of the pine wood nematode (PWN), <i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>. Although not a pest in its native North America, PWN has devastated forests in Asia. Since the arrival of PWN in Portugal, the native maritime pine, <i>Pinus pinaster</i>, has proved to be extremely susceptible, with PWN being spread by the local longhorn beetle <i>Monochamus galloprovincialis</i>. Previous studies have shown that PWN could spread throughout the Iberian peninsula and beyond, making it a major threat to European forests.</p> <p>Effective containment and eventual eradication of PWN demands a detailed understanding of the behaviour and dynamics of PWN in infested trees, especially because delayed onset of symptoms (latency) reduces survey accuracy and can compromise containment strategies. Research will be carried out into vector dispersal capacity; improved ways to monitor and reduce populations using synthetic chemical lures will be investigated; the potential for PWN transfer between trees in the absence of the <i>Monochamus</i> spp. vectors will be evaluated, as will the introduction of resistant conifers. Crucially, the project will extend the capability of existing models to identify the risk posed by PWN to the rest of Europe and the possible impact of climate change on its spread. The REPHRAME project brings together Europes leading experts on PWN, together with colleagues from around the world, to address the key gaps in current knowledge. As well as providing a scientific basis for</p>	<p>Pine forests</p>	<p>PINE WOOD NEMATODE, (<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>)</p>

	governmental action to deal with PWN, the results of the project will be synthesised into a user-friendly toolkit so that workers on the ground can put them to immediate use. The project also includes extensive dissemination activities to ensure the uptake and application of results across the EU and world-wide.		
QBOL	Development of a new diagnostic tool using DNA barcoding to identify quarantine organisms in support of plant health. Making DNA barcoding available for plant health diagnostics and focusing on strengthening the link between traditional and molecular taxonomy as a sustainable diagnostic resource. Within QBOL collections harboring plant pathogenic Q-organisms will be made available. Informative genes from selected species on the EU Directive and EPPO lists will be DNA barcoded from vouchered specimens. The sequences, together with taxonomic features, will be included in a new internet-based database system. A validation procedure on developed protocols and the database will be undertaken across worldwide partners to ensure robustness of procedures for use in a distributed network of laboratories across Europe.	All	All
QDETECT	Developing quarantine pest detection methods for use by national plant protection organizations (NPPO) and inspection services. Development of detection methods based on biochemical (detecting volatile organic compounds [VOC] and nucleic acid), acoustic (including resonance), remote imaging (incorporating spectral and automated data analysis) and pest trapping (insect pests and pathogen vectors) techniques.	All	High priority targets for the EU such as the PWN (<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>), Asian longhorn beetle (<i>Anoplophora labripennis</i>).
EUPHRESCO II	EUROPEAN PHYTOSANITARY RESEARCH COORDINATION II	All	All
PRATIQUE	Enhancements of pest risk analysis techniques: targeted research to improve existing procedures and develop new methods for the assessment of economic, environmental and social impacts, summarizing risk in effective, harmonized ways that take account of uncertainty, mapping endangered areas pathway risk analysis and systems approaches and guiding actions during emergencies caused by outbreaks of harmful pests.	All	All
BACCARA	BIODIVERSITY AND CLIMATE CHANGE, A RISK ANALYSIS BACCARA has as its main goal to build scientific foundations for developing tools allowing forest managers and policy makers to evaluate risk of European forest biodiversity and productivity loss under climate	Forestry, landscape,	All

	<p>change. The scope of BACCARA encompasses forest composition at multiple trophic levels, i.e. assemblages of forest symbionts mycorrhiza), producers (keystone tree species), consumers (herbivores and pathogens) and their predators. The concept of the project is to construct a 3-dimensional risk assessment model linking climate change, functional diversity, and forest productivity through a three step process: 1) Effect of climate change on forest biodiversity will be evaluated through better understanding of the influence of climatic conditions on the ecological processes that shape assemblages of forest species. 2) Relationships between forest biodiversity and functioning will be deciphered through better understanding of the role of forest species richness and composition on biomass production. 3) The information will eventually be aggregated to predict the risk of forest productivity loss, considered as a function of climate change probability (hazard), susceptibility of forest to climate change according to its diversity (vulnerability), and effect of forest diversity on biomass productivity (exposure). This approach will be applied to the main European Forest Categories. As deliverables for forest managers and policy makers BACCARA will provide guidelines on "What-to-Grow" (tree species to maintain or introduce in order to sustain biomass production) and on "What-to-Combat" (pest and pathogen species to manage in order to prevent outbreaks) for the main European forest types and climate change scenarios. BACCARA will ultimately result in a multi-criteria decision analysis tool, which helps managers to choose new forest compositions according to various criteria, including risk of productivity loss under climate change.</p>		
<p>COST-ACTIONS</p>	<p>PHYTOPHTHORA: Established and emerging phytophthora: threats to woodland and forest ecosystems (FP0801); PERMIT: Pathway evaluation and pest risk management in transport (FP1002); DIAROD: Determining invasiveness and risk of Dothistroma (Red Band Needle Blight) (FP1102)</p>	<p>Forestry</p>	<p>Fungal pathogens & pest risk analysis</p>
<p>COST-ACTIONS</p>	<p>FRAXBACK. Fraxinus dieback in Europe: elaborating guidelines and strategies for sustainable management. Currently, severe dieback of <i>Fraxinus</i> spp. is observed in most European countries. This is an emerging disease, which results in massive tree mortality, threatening the existence of <i>Fraxinus</i> over the continent. It is caused by <i>Hymenoscyphus pseudoalbidus</i>, alien and invasive fungus, origin of which remains unknown. Currently, many European countries have</p>	<p>Forestry, nurseries, landscape, public green</p>	<p>Fungal pathogen</p>

	<p>national research programs on <i>Fraxinus</i> dieback, focusing on numerous aspects of the biology and ecology of the disease, but the activities are scattered. Aim of the FRAXBACK is, through sharing and synthesis of available knowledge, generate comprehensive understanding of <i>Fraxinus</i> dieback phenomenon, and to elaborate state of the art practical guidelines for sustainable management of <i>Fraxinus</i> in Europe. The <u>Action</u> will be implemented through innovative interdisciplinary approach, and will include forest pathologists, tree breeders and silviculturists. Its deliverables: i) guidelines for sustainable management of <i>Fraxinus</i> in Europe; ii) European database for dieback-resistant <i>Fraxinus</i> genotypes/families/populations and established/planned progeny trials; iii) illustrated digests/leaflets/brochures on <i>Fraxinus</i> dieback; iv) disease distribution maps; v) website; vi) book. FRAXBACK is comprised of four Working Groups: WG1 Pathogen; WG2 Host; WG3 Silviculture; WG4 Dissemination and knowledge gaps. Its duration is 4 years, including two <u>MC/WG</u> meetings and four STSMs per year, and one international conference.</p>		
LIFE+ projects	Further development and implementation of an EU-level forest monitoring system	Forestry	Tree health monitoring
EFSA	<p>EFSA project CFP/EFSA/PLH/2009/01 (Project PRIMA PHACIE): "Pest risk assessment for the European Community plant health: A comparative approach with case studies."</p> <p>EFSA project CFP/EFSA/PLH/2010/01 (Project PERSEUS): "Plant health pest surveys for the EU territory: an analysis of data quality and methodologies and the resulting uncertainties for pest risk assessment."</p>		
IUFRO	<p>IUFRO – THE GLOBAL NETWORK for Forest Science Cooperation is a non-profit, non-governmental international network of forest scientists, which promotes global cooperation in forest-related research and enhances the understanding of the ecological, economic and social aspects of forests and trees. It unites more than 15,000 scientists in almost 700 Member Organizations in over 110 countries, and is a member of ICSU. Scientists cooperate in IUFRO on a voluntary basis. With the Strategy 2010-14, IUFRO addresses Research and Institutional Goals at the same time.</p> <p>The Research Goals strongly focus on the following six thematic areas: 1 Forests for People</p>	Forestry	Forest Health

	<p>2 Forests and Climate Change 3 Forest Bioenergy 4 Forest Biodiversity Conservation 5 Forest and Water Interactions 6 Resources for the Future http://www.iufro.org/science/divisions/division-7/</p>		
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RESEARCH PROJECTS RELATED TO FORESTRY PLANT HEALTH

Description		
	FP6	
Trees4Future	FP7	<p>Designing Trees for the future TREES4FUTURE will make a significant contribution to helping the European forestry sector respond, in a sustainable manner, to increasing demands for wood products and services (among which preservation of forest biodiversity) in a context of changing climatic conditions. To do so TREES4FUTURE will integrate for the first time major, yet rarely interacting forestry communities (and their resources) from geneticists to environmentalists and from communities working at the tree/population scale to those working at forestry landscape/wood basin levels as well as industry concerns. These scientific communities will combine their complementary infrastructures, tools and knowledge and thus fill in the current gaps 1) physical environment vs genetics, 2) basic wood properties vs end-products quality and 3) individuals to forests scales of study. This collaboration will result in a holistic approach integrating abiotic and biotic environmental aspects through biological responses (eco-physiological and pest/disease risk studies), biomass production (breeding and silviculture) and industrial technology (wood quality and technology). The long-term objective of TREES4FUTURE is to provide not only the partners but the whole European forestry community, with an easy and comprehensive access to complementary but currently scattered sources of information and expertise to optimise the short and long-term exploitation of the forest resources by both the research community and the socio-economic players. Providing access to the wider research community to a wide variety of forestry research infrastructures (from state-of-the-art analytical tools to predictive models) via the project will enable TREES4FUTURE to improve, coordinate and validate its offer to the European and International researchers from both public and private sectors and thus ensure the future sustainability of the</p>

<p>MOTIVE</p>	<p>consortium as well as that of the wider European Forestry community at large.</p> <p>The project MODELS FOR ADAPTIVE FOREST MANAGEMENT (MOTIVE) is a large-scale integrated project in the 7th Framework Programme of the EU that evaluates the consequences of the intensified competition for forest resources given climate and land use change. The project focuses on a wide range of European forest types under different intensities of forest management. In particular, MOTIVE examines impacts with respect to the disturbance regimes determining forest dynamics.</p> <p>MOTIVE seeks to develop and evaluate strategies that can adapt forest management practices to balance multiple objectives under changing environmental conditions. The evaluation of different adaptive management systems will take place within a scenario analysis and a regional landscape framework. A wide range of possible scenarios will be taken into account from optimistic predictions (“no major change for forest ecosystems”) including possible opportunities offered by climate change (e.g. increased tree growth in northern areas) to worst case scenarios (“extreme deterioration of the growth conditions for trees”) on different time scales (short-, mid-, long term). The main forest types in Europe for the most important bioclimatic regions will be covered.</p>
<p>NOVELTREE</p>	<p>NOVEL TREE BREEDING STRATEGIES</p> <p>NOVELTREE will provide an improved understanding of the biology of forest tree species and enable significant genetic improvement in the composition and characteristics of forest products in order to satisfy the needs (e.g. quality, quantity, sustainability, vulnerability) of consumers and of the forest-based sector. The recent advances in the genomics of forest trees, the increasing knowledge of functional polymorphisms and the new understanding of the nature and origins of genetic variation should allow far more efficient management of breeding stock in order to exploit available genetic diversity and preserve it in the long term.</p> <p>To achieve these goals, NOVELTREE will integrate an ambitious combination of approaches, including quantitative genetics & breeding, population genetics, genomics, pathology, tree physiology, forestry and economics.</p> <p>The research of NOVELTREE will focus on model tree species of high economic importance which are representative of the four main European regions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Maritime pine - Atlantic and Mediterranean Areas •Scots pine - Northern and Central Europe •Spruce - Scandinavia and UK •Poplar - Western Europe
<p>ProCoGen</p>	<p>PROMOTING A FUNCTIONAL AND COMPARATIVE UNDERSTANDING OF THE CONIFER GENOME-IMPLEMENTING APPLIED ASPECTS FOR MORE PRODUCTIVE AND ADAPTED FORESTS.</p> <p>In the midst of a climatic change scenario, the genetics of adaptive response in conifers becomes essential to ensure a sustainable management of genetic resources and an effective breeding. Conifers</p>

	<p>are the target of major tree breeding efforts worldwide. Advances in molecular technologies, such as next-generation DNA sequencing technologies, could have an enormous impact on the rate of progress and achievements made by tree breeding programmes. These new technologies might be used not only to improve our understanding of fundamental conifer biology, but also to address practical problems for the forest industry as well as problems related to the adaptation and management of conifer forests. In this context, ProCoGen will address genome sequencing of two keystone European conifer species. Genome re-sequencing approaches will be used to obtain two reference pine genomes. Comparative genomics and genetic diversity will be closely integrated and linked to targeted functional genomics investigations to identify genes and gene networks that efficiently help to develop or enhance applications related to forest productivity, forest stewardship in response to environmental change or conservation efforts. The development of high-throughput genotyping tools will produce an array of pre-breeding tools to be implemented in forest tree breeding programmes. ProCoGen will also develop comparative studies based on orthologous sequences, genes and markers, which will allow guiding re-sequencing initiatives and exploiting the research accumulated on each of the species under consideration to accelerate the use of genomic tools in diverse species. ProCoGen will integrate fragmented activities developed by European research groups involved in several ongoing international conifer genome initiatives and contribute to strengthening international collaboration with North American initiatives (US and Canada).</p>
<p>TRANZFOR</p>	<p>TRANSFERRING RESEARCH BETWEEN EU AND AUSTRALIA-NZ ON FORESTRY AND CLIMATE CHANGE The objectives of TRANZFOR www.tranzfor.eu are to promote knowledge exchange in the general domain of Forests and Climate Change between Australia and New Zealand and the European Union through short to medium term (2– 12 months) staff exchanges. Work programmes have been developed around the following areas: Genomics and tree breeding, Forest Models, Environmental Services, Risk Assessment, Bioenergy. The purpose of the mid-term workshop was to: share experience and knowledge gained through TRANZFOR exchanges to date among participants and projects document and discuss emerging issues and forest adaptation priorities in each of the thematic areas to target future exchanges and explore more broadly common science agendas</p>
<p>FunDivEUROPE</p>	<p>FUNCTIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF FOREST BIODIVERSITY The overall scientific goal of FunDivEUROPE is to quantify the effects of forest biodiversity on ecosystem functions and services in major European forest types. A major aim is to understand and quantify how tree species diversity can be used to foster the provision of ecosystem services such as timber production, carbon sequestration and freshwater provisioning. Additionally, the implications of tree species diversity for the vulnerability of ecosystem services under climate change will be assessed by integrating field and modelling data on the performance of pure versus mixed species stands under</p>

		different climates. The policy relevant objective is to strengthen the science policy interface by delivering timely, relevant and understandable information to policymakers and stakeholders about the relationship of forest biodiversity and ecosystem services. This will help forest owners and forestry organizations to adapt management strategies to better utilize potential benefits of mixed species forests and ecosystem services.
RHEA		ROBOT FLEETS FOR HIGHLY EFFECTIVE AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY MANAGEMENT (RHEA) RHEA is focused on the design, development, and testing of a new generation of automatic and robotic systems for both chemical and physical mechanical and thermal effective weed management focused on both agriculture and forestry, and covering a large variety of European products including agriculture wide row crops (processing tomato, maize, strawberry, sunflower and cotton), close row crops (winter wheat and winter barley) and forestry woody perennials (walnut trees, almond trees, olive groves and multipurpose open woodland). RHEA aims at diminishing the use of agricultural chemical inputs in a 75%, improving crop quality, health and safety for humans, and reducing production costs by means of sustainable crop management using a fleet of small, heterogeneous robots ground and aerial equipped with advanced sensors, enhanced end-effectors and improved decision control algorithms. RHEA can be considered as a cooperative robotic system, falling within an emerging area of research and technology with a large number of applications as reported by the FP6 Network of Excellence EURON, Special Interest Group on Cooperative Robotics, funded by the European Commission.
FORESTERA-ERANET		Forest-Based Sector Technology Platform http://www.forestplatform.org/en/research-projects/era-net-projects
WoodWisdom		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERA-NET on wood material science and engineering, WoodWisdom-Net 1 • ERA-NET project WoodWisdom-Net 2 - "Networking and Integration of National Programmes in the Area of Wood Material Science and Engineering in the Forest-Based Value Chains" <p>The overall objective of WoodWisdom-Net 2 is to promote the transformation of the European forest-based industry from resource-intensive to value-added knowledge-intensive, innovative and globally competitive industry based on sustainable use of renewable raw materials.</p>

EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F11 EUPH Forestry WP5. Factors influencing priorities

Examples of different factors influencing on why certain quarantine pests have higher priority than other.

Many factors influence on how people working with phytosanitary problems regard the threat and importance of a specific quarantine pest. Some of the factors are: the status of the pest: is it absent, introduced, under spreading or established. The migration biology of the pest: naturally spreading by short or long distance migration; airborne, soilborne, waterborne; the influence of human transport. The number of host plants (one, few or many host plants) and the economical importance of each host plants. The habitat of the host plants: landscape, park plants, forestry etc.

All these and more factors influence why certain pests and associated crops are more in focus than other and initiation of research projects have different priority.

Examples:

1. The pest is strongly regulated and no interception or registration has been obtained the last many years: f. ex. *Atropellis* spp. (Atropellis cancer in pine). Very low priority.
2. No interception or registration of the pest has been obtained the last many years: f. ex. Oak wilt (*Ceratocystis fagacearum*). Very low priority, but research might still be relevant because of the risk to introduce the pest with import with wood chip from North America.
3. The pest has changed pathogenicity and spreads naturally by long distance transport, f. ex. Ash dieback (*Chalara fraxinea*). Eradication impossible, only isolated regions (islands) can maybe resist infection. Low priority.
4. The pest has changed pathogenicity and increases host spectrum and spreads naturally only by short distance transport, f. ex. Sudden Oak Death (*Phytophthora ramorum*). Eradication possible. High priority
5. The pest has invaded Europe and spreads naturally by the pests' migration, f.ex. horse-chestnut leaf-miner (*Cameraria ohridella*). Prevention of migration not possible, but impediment is. Low priority.
6. The pest has invaded Europe and spreads naturally by the pests' migration, f.ex. the red palm weevil (*Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*) Eradication not possible any more, but impediment is. Regulation has a high priority.
7. The pest has recently been established in one member country, where it is under eradication measures, f. ex. pine wood nematode (*Bursaphelenchus xylophilis*). High priority.
8. The pest has recently been introduced repeatedly in some member states and eradication initiated f. ex. citrus long - horned beetle. High priority.
9. The pest is established in small areas in many member states and repeatedly under eradication, f. ex. fireblight (*Erwinia amylovora*). Priority? Depends on many factors.

Annex F12 EUPH Forestry WP5. Forestry plant health topics proposed to the first call round in 2011 in EUPHRESCO-2.

EUPHRESCO II - Call 1 - PARKING LIST 20				Indications given for:				Exclusion at - elig. Check - preselect. (TC ass.) - topic descr.	
Topic	Previously/Potentially interested	Original text, heading, ...; EUPHRESCO comments WP3 comment in eligibility check of Call 1	Further comments on topic (e.g. Partners,...)	duration	start	funding mechan.	national budget		
Forest related topics									
Anoplophora sp.	BE-EV ILVO, Obs. Malta, Obs. Romania (CPL)	EUPHRESCO I Project just started (ANOPLORISK = Risk Management for the EC listed Anoplophora species, A. chinensis and A. glabripennis). Within this project the development and improvement of early and especially non-destructive detection methods is one of the main topics. All results of this project are used for the development of recommendations for the EU Commission and countries, of contingency plans and best practice manuals of the techniques developed/improved within this project. EU-FP 7 Project: QBOL: Development of a new diagnostic tool using DNA barcoding to identify quarantine organisms in support of plant health; http://www.qbol.org/UK/	BE-EV ILVO is participating in the EUPHRESCO I project, and especially on DNA-based A. species identification starting from wood samples with animal remnant. Early detection methods of Anoplophora chinensis; detection methods, ring test	short		NC		X	
Platanus spp.	IT-CRA	Topic: Resistance of Platanus spp. to canker stain; Description: Since several decades, canker stain continues to be a disease with a destructive impact on plane tree plantations in Europe. Application of eradication measures has not been effective for controlling disease spread. As a consequence it is urgent to deepen the knowledge on the mechanisms governing the host resistance response in order to identify genes that cover a key role in the process and that can be used as molecular/physiological markers to speed up genetic selection for obtaining multiple resistant genotypes; Comments: Climatic changes are under way worldwide. Although canker stain has not yet spread in Northern Europe, due to temperature limitations, it is conceivable to predict a spread of the disease northwards from southern Europe, in the future. Therefore availability of adequate molecularly-sustained breeding protocols would be crucial to face up this problem.		LONG	Not before Nov 2012	VP	IT-CRA 50 000	X	
Fusarium olivinum	PT-INRB, BE-EV ILVO; Ideas from EMN&EAP	http://www.polisca.be/ppt091125/TO.pdf ; IDEFOR (KBBE FP7); FORTHREATS (KBBE CA FFS); UK-Defra/Fera: There is a current EUPHRESCO Project on seed testing diagnostics	PT-INRB: Topic: Fusarium circinatum; Description: The diagnostics on seeds are already ongoing but we are interested in detection methods on other substrates such as the potting mix and on prevention/control methods in nurseries. BE-EV ILVO is interested in participating in ringtests EMN&EAP: Rapid diagnostics for seed borne quarantine fungal pathogens e.g. Fusarium circinatum and Plasmodiopsis halstedii		2012	VP/INC		X	
(1) Pine wood nematode / Bursaphelenchus xylophilus	SI-MAFF, LT-MoA, BE-EV ILVO, IT-CRA, UK-FR, Obs. Malta	Within the EU-FP7 project REPHRAME (April 2011-2014) some of the main topics are detection methods and the potential transfer of B.x. between trees without vectors (http://www.nri.org/research/pwn.html). Former EU-FP 5- Project: PHRAME: Development of improved pest risk analysis techniques for quarantine pests. Using pine wood nematode, bursaphelenchus xylophilus, in Portugal as a model system 2003-2006; http://cordis.europa.eu/data/PROJ_FFS/ACTIONeDndSEGGIONeq12482005919dDOceq706ndTBLegEN_PROJ.htm ; Pinewood nematode (PWN), Bursaphelenchus xylophilus: research in Russia and other countries. http://www.cabdirect.org/abstracts/20043115351.html?sessionid=8870071E7F1CE64DA136DC69332A2DB8	SI-MAFF - Topic: Bursaphelenchus xylophilus (PWN) - Bursaphelenchus spp. + Monochamus biology and ecology; Aspects: 1. Pest risk assessment for potential import, settlement and spreading of Bursaphelenchus xylophilus (PWN) 2. Estimation of potential economical impact, 3. Insect vectors present 4. Other Bursaphelenchus sp. present, 5. Improvement of early detection, 6. Modeling LT-MoA - interested in Topics: Pine wood nematode (Research on methods for the early detection of the Pine wood nematode and other wood borer insects) AND European insect vectors (Monochamus spp.) of Bursaphelenchus xylophilus (Examination of the species spectrum and the spread of the European insect vectors (Monochamus spp.) of Bursaphelenchus xylophilus with trapping methods)	medium	2012	NC/VP	10-50 k/year		X
			MMM-FI: Since there are already ongoing projects dealing with PWN it is very important first to figure out that no overlapping exists with the on-going PWN-projects. MMM-FI has contacted REPHRAME project (http://www.nri.org/research/pwn.html) and has asked if any overlapping exists with the needs indicated in the left column. We have not, however, received any response from the REPHRAME coordinator indicated in the above-mentioned www site. As far as this item is not clear MMM-FI will postpone this topic!						

<p><i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i></p>	<p>CH-FOAG, IT-CRA, PT-INRB, UK-FR</p>		<p>CH-FOAG - Topic: <i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i> (EPPO A2); Description: Current quarantine regulations for the chestnut blight fungus <i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i> demands that on <i>Castanea</i> and <i>Quercus</i> plants in nurseries "no symptoms of <i>C. parasitica</i> have been observed at the place of production or its immediate vicinity since the beginning of the last complete cycle of vegetation". In practice this means that if a single infected chestnut plant is found in a nursery the entire production of <i>Castanea</i> and <i>Quercus</i> is under quarantine for more than one year. Compared to other quarantine pathogens (e.g. <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>), the regulation for <i>C. parasitica</i> seems to be very rigorous. The project aims to evaluate the current quarantine regulation for <i>C. parasitica</i> by conducting a pathway risk analysis for spread of the pathogen on <i>Castanea</i> and <i>Quercus</i> plants for planting. Further description of FOAG:conduct a pathway risk analysis for spread of the pathogen on <i>Castanea</i> and <i>Quercus</i> plants for planting (in the frame of Euphresco the laboratories of WGL (Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research) are represented by FOAG) IT-CRA - Interested in topic of FOAG: <i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i>. In addition, it would also be important to study host-pathogen interaction to unravel response of chestnut spp. tree to fungal infection PT-INRB - Interested in topic of FOAG: <i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i> UK-FR - Interested in topic of FOAG: <i>Cryphonectria parasitica</i></p>	<p>medium (18 month)</p>	<p>NC/VP</p>	<p>< 40k/year</p>		<p>X</p>
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EUPHRESCO-2 Workshop: Exploring EUPHRESCO partners mandates to fund forestry research and important forestry plant health threats Vienna 17th – 18th January 2012

Annex F13 EUPH Forestry WP5. Short analyse of some of the background material.

The aim of the exploration is to analyse whether the forestry plant health sector is underrepresented in EUPHRESCO initiated projects.

The lists of the present (2011) most important phytosanitary threats in forestry according to NPPO's in 12 countries (see Annex 2 & 3)

In Annex 2 and 3 the pests are sorted after importance. However, it is important to be aware that regional differences might influence the overall picture. A pest only listed by one or two partners might be a very important threat in that specific region.

From Annex 3 it also appears that the NPPOs' underline the importance of some broader phytosanitary topics directed to handle and prevent many different quarantine pests. There are more broad topics as for example Influence of climatic changes and new developments in diagnostics to more specific topics as applications of image analysis and computer vision in plant health inspections and wood chips imported from other continents. These kinds of topics are in minority in the EUPHRESCO projects initiated until now.

The Council Directive 2000/29/EC (see Annex F4-F5)

The Council Directive 2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community comprises totally 189 pests, which are distributed in the following way:

1. Agricultural crops: total 59 pests
 - a. Potato: 19 pests
 - b. Vegetables (field grown): 15,
 - c. Maize: 8
 - d. Cereals including rice: 4
 - e. Grasses, clover and alfalfa: 4
 - f. Beets: 2
 - g. Sunflower, soybean, tobacco, Brassica (cabbage, rape etc.) and cotton: 4
2. Fruit with 89 pests
3. Viticulture: 7 pests.
4. Glasshouse (ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato)) and field ornamentals: 27.
5. Tomato: 13 pests.
6. Plants for planting: 22 pests.
7. Forestry: 27 pests.

The main crop sectors/crops calculated into % of the total list:

1. Agricultural crops: 31%

2. Potato: 10%
3. Vegetables (field grown): 8%
4. Maize: 4%
5. Fruit: 47%
6. Viticulture: 4%
7. Glasshouse (ornamentals and vegetables (except tomato)) and field ornamentals: 14%
8. Tomato: 7%
9. Plants for planting: 12%
10. Forestry: 14%

From the overview can be seen that forestry quarantine pests comprises 14 % of the pests included in Council Directive 2000/29/EC

The EUPHRESCO initiated projects (see Annex F6) split on crop sectors/crops and compared with the distribution of pests in the same crop sectors/crops listed in directive 2000/29/EC and the EPPO's Alert List

Crop sector/crop	No. of projects	No. of projects in % of sector / crop in column 1	The sector / crop in % in directive 2000/29/EC	The sector / crop in % in EPPO's Alert List
Potato	8	27	10	8
Maize	1	3	4	11
Tomato	2	7	7	27
Vegetables fields	1	3	8	3
Ornamentals glasshouse	2	7	14	3
Fruit	5	17	47	14
Vine	2	7	4	0
Plants for planting	4	13	12	16
Forestry	3	10	14	22
Other broader topics	3	10	0	0

From the table it appears that compared to the directive 2000/29/EC list there is a small underweight of EUPHRESCO initiated projects in forestry. Compared to EPPO's Alert List there is a clear underweight of forestry.

Examples on different factors influencing why certain q-pests have higher priority than other (Annex 11)

In Annex11 is given examples that illustrate why different quarantine pests are regarded as having different importance, actuality and priority.

The main conclusions from the forestry workshop were: There has been an increase in forestry plant health threats both in number and impact over the last decade, which hopefully will result in more EUPHRESKO initiated projects in forestry in the future. EUPHRESKO was recommended to:

- NOT to set up a permanent forestry working group under EUPHRESKO
- To invite national forestry research funders, who at present are non-EUPHRESKO-partner, to join or be associated to EUPHRESKO.
- To consider including more general topics in future topic call rounds.
- To consider arranging a European stakeholder/funder workshop on forestry plant health in cooperation with ISEFOR.

These conclusions were confirmed by the EUPHRESKO General Assembly at the first Annual Project Meeting 14–15 February 2012 in Rome. A reminder was sent by WP5 to all EUPHRESKO partners and observers at the start of the 2nd topic identification round in 2012 to remember to contact national forestry research funders, who at present are non-EUPHRESKO-partner, and inform them of the 2nd topic initiation round and invite them to suggest and fund forestry topics.